

*Dr M.A. Mwalaka
Dept. of Linguistics & African Lgs*

IGBO ENGLISH IN JOHN MUNONYE, CHUKWUEMEKA

IKE AND NKEM NWANKWO:

A LINGUISTIC STYLISTIC ANALYSIS

BY

IGBOANUSI, HERBERT SUNDAY
B.A. (Hons) Linguistic/Igbo (Abia)
M.A. Linguistics (Ibadan)

A THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF LINGUISTICS AND
AFRICAN LANGUAGES SUBMITTED TO THE FACULTY OF
ARTS IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE DEGREE OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN

SEPTEMBER 1995

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by Mr. Herbert Sunday Igboanusi in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

(Supervisor)

PROF. ADEKUNLE ADENIRAN, B.A.
Dip. Phon. & Ling. (Ibadan), M.A.
(Leeds), Ph.D. (Ibadan)
Professor,
Department of Linguistics and
African Languages
University of Ibadan, Ibadan

SEPTEMBER 1995

DEDICATION

To

**My Father,
Mr. Emmanuel Igboanusi**

and

**My Mother,
Mrs. Roseline Igboanusi**

for their love and support.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, I wish to express my profound gratitude to my supervisor Professor Adekunle Adeniran for thoroughly supervising this thesis. His encouragement, patience, understanding and useful comments and suggestions have contributed immensely to the success of this work.

I am also greatly indebted to the staff of Linguistics Department, particularly Professor Ayo Bamgbose, Professor Ben Elugbe, Dr. Olukoju, Dr. Owolabi, Dr. Olabode, Rev.Sis.(Dr.) Uwalaka, Dr. Oyetade, Dr. Egbokhare, Mrs. Regina Obaigbena, Chief Oke and Mr. Kelim for their useful contributions and assistance. I am also grateful to Professor Ayo Banjo, Professor Dan Izevbaye, Professor Niyi Osundare, Dr. Amayo, Dr. Oyeleye and Mr. Yemi Babajide for their contributions and also for making their books available to me.

The useful company of such good friends as Mr. Isaac Ohia, Dr. Chidozie Emenuga, Miss Ifeyinwa Mbakogu, Mr. Cyriacus Udah, Mallam Amfani, Mr. Sam. Agubosim, Steve Ufearo, Mr. Komolafe, Mr. Ben Mmadike, Mr. Udo Nwokocha, Mr. Isidore Diala, Dr. Simon Ajayi, Mr. Paul Ndoh, Dr. Osaro Mgbere and Mr. Oliver Uche will always be remembered.

Let me express my special appreciation to my dearest, Miss Edith Nnenna Ukuku for her priceless care and encouragement.

I am also specially grateful to my parents, Mr. Emma O. Igboanusi and Mrs. Roseline Igboanusi for their wonderful love and all the support that have seen me through to this stage of my life. My thanks also go to my brothers - Chukwuka and Philip, my sisters - Nkiru and Ndidi, my cousins - Sylva and Joshua Ezeigbo and my uncle Mr. Dennis Igboanusi for their support.

Most importantly, I thank God for giving me life, strength and good health throughout the period of the programme.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
TITLE PAGE	i
CERTIFICATION	ii
DEDICATION	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
ABSTRACT	xiii
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 GENERAL INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 THE ADOPTION OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA	3
1.1.1 The Impact of Colonization	6
1.2 IGBO WRITERS IN ENGLISH	9
1.3 THE BACKGROUND OF THE AUTHORS AND THE SUMMARY OF THEIR WORKS	13
1.4 THE CONCEPT OF OFFICIAL AND NATIONAL LANGUAGES	17
CHAPTER TWO	
2.0 VARIETIES OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH	22
2.1 THE TYPOLOGY OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH	22
2.1.1 Brosnahan's Approach	22
2.1.2 Banjo's Approach	24
2.2 THE CONCEPT OF THE "COMMON-CORE" FEATURES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE	27

2.3	THE FEATURES OF STANDARD NIGERIAN ENGLISH	...	29
2.3.1	Nativization	...	30
2.3.2	The Influence of Biblical Language	...	33
2.3.3	The Influence of American English	...	34
2.4	IGBO ENGLISH	...	35
2.5	CHARACTERISTICS OF IGBO ENGLISH	...	36
2.5.1	Igbonization	...	36
2.5.2	Influence of Other Nigerian Languages on Igbo English	...	37
2.6	THE INFLUENCE OF IGBO ON ENGLISH	...	39
2.6.1	Phonological Influences	...	39
2.6.2	Lexical Influences	...	40
2.7	THE INFLUENCE OF ENGLISH ON IGBO	...	43
2.8	LANGUAGE MIXING	...	44
CHAPTER THREE			50
3.0	LITERATURE REVIEW	...	50
3.1	INTERFERENCE	...	51
3.1.1	Interference from the Sound System of the Mother Tongue	...	55
3.1.2	Interference from the Grammar of the Mother Tongue	...	56
3.1.3	Interference from the Semantic or Lexical Pattern of the Mother Tongue	...	56

		Page
3.2	THE INTERFERENCE OF MOTHER TONGUE ON ENGLISH: A REVIEW ...	56
3.3	STYLE ...	59
	3.3.1 Style as Deviation ...	60
	3.3.2 Style as Coherence ...	62
	3.3.3 Style as Choice Possibilities ...	63
3.4	STYLISTICS ...	64
	3.4.1 Previous Studies on Stylistics which Relate Directly to the Present Work ...	66
	3.4.2 The Present Study ...	69
3.5	GRAMMATICAL MODEL ...	70
3.6	THE ORGANIZATION OF SYSTEMIC GRAMMAR	71
	3.6.1 Grammar ...	74
	3.6.2 Lexis ...	78
	3.6.3 Phonology ...	80
3.7	FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO GRAMMAR ...	85
3.8	STYLISTIC ANALYSIS ...	86
	3.8.1 Linguistic Stylistic Studies Based on Scale and Category Linguistics ...	87
	3.8.2 Linguistic Stylistic Studies Based on Systemic Functional Grammar ...	88
3.9	THE APPLICATION OF SYSTEMIC LINGUISTICS TO LINGUISTIC STYLISTICS ...	90

		Page
3.9.1	Cohesion ...	91
3.9.2	Clause Analysis ...	95
3.10	KACHRU'S TRANSFER THEORY ...	100
3.11	RESEARCH DESIGN ...	101
3.11.1	The Use of Contrastive Analysis in this Work: A Methodological Statement...	102
3.11.2	Contrastive Analysis Through Translation ...	103
3.11.3	Translation ...	104
3.11.4	An Explanation on the Marking of Tones	105
3.11.5	Assumptions ...	106
3.11.6	The Objective of Study ...	107
3.11.7	Methodology ...	108
3.11.8	Choice of Texts ...	109
CHAPTER FOUR: TEXTUAL ANALYSIS: LEXICO-SEMANTICS		110
4.0	LEXICO-SEMANTICS ...	110
4.1	TRANSFERENCE... ...	114
4.1.1	Items Transferred to Fill Lexical Gaps	115
4.1.2	Transferred Items with Partial Equivalents	118
4.2	MIXED TRANSFER ...	120
4.3	LITERAL TRANSFER ...	123
4.3.1	Those Derived from Igbo Language Pattern ...	124
4.3.2	Those Which are Grammatically Different from those of English English	127
4.3.3	Transferred Items with Contextual Units which are Absent in English Culture	130

		Page
4.4	NEOLOGISMS ...	136
4.5	THE SEMANTIC EXTENSION OF VERBS ...	137
4.6	THE SEMANTIC EXTENSION OF NOUNS/ PRONOUNS ...	138
4.7	KINSHIP TERMS ...	140
CHAPTER FIVE	...	146
5.0	TEXTUAL ANALYSIS: SYNTAX ...	146
5.1	THE STRUCTURE OF SPEECH FUNCTIONS ...	150
5.1.1	Curses ...	151
5.1.2	Blessing/Prayers ...	155
5.2	THE STRUCTURE OF COLLOQUIAL UTTERANCES ...	156
5.3	DE-PERSONALIZED UTTERANCES ...	160
5.4	TEMPORAL ADVERBS ...	164
5.5	THE STRUCTURE OF THE MIXED ITEMS ...	169
5.5.1	Igbo Items Used as Head Nouns in Subject Position (Singular) ...	169
5.5.2	Igbo Items Used as Head Nouns in Subject Position (Plural) ...	170
5.5.3	Igbo Items Used as Both Modifier and Head in a Subject Nominal Group ...	170
5.5.4	Igbo Items Used as Complements ...	170
5.5.5	Igbo Items Used as Complements (Plural)	171
5.5.6	Igbo Items Used as Adjuncts ...	171

	Page
5.5.7 Igbo Items Used as Complements in Possessive Constructions ...	172
5.6 THE IGBO NARRATIVE DEVICES ...	173
5.7 TRANSITIVITY ...	174
5.7.1 The Transitivity System of Proverbs	177
5.7.2 Proverbs with Rhetorical Questions ...	181
5.7.3 Transitivity System of Imagery ...	185
5.8 THE STRUCTURE OF RIDDLES ...	188
CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION ...	192
6.1 INTRODUCTION ...	192
6.1.1 Lexico-Semantic Level ...	195
6.1.2 Syntactic Level ...	195
6.2 THE CODIFICATION OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH ...	198
6.2.1 The Role of Literature in the Development of Nigerian English ...	200
6.3 THE USEFULNESS OF THIS STUDY TO LANGUAGE POLICY FORMULATION ...	201
6.3.1 Problems in the Implementation of National Language Policies ...	204
6.3.2 The Need for a Comprehensive Language Policy ...	206
6.3.4 The Language Attitude Factor ...	210

	Page
6.3.4 The Indian Experiment ...	210
6.3.5 Recommendation ...	211
6.3.6 Policy Implementation ...	212
6.4 THE IMPLICATION OF THIS STUDY TO THE TEACHING OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA ...	213
BIBLIOGRAPHY ...	218

·ABSTRACT

Every language consists of dialectal and diatypic varieties. The present study identifies two major dialectal varieties of English used in Nigeria. They are the national variety of English often referred to as Nigerian English and the ethnic variety of English exemplified here by Igbo English.

Using creative language in prose texts written by Igbo English bilinguals, specifically John Munonye, Chukwuemeka Ike, and Nkem Nwankwo, this thesis sets out to establish Igbo English as an ethnic variety of Nigerian English. In doing this:

- (a) It demonstrates language interference as deliberate but often non-deliberate stylistic device which gives this variety of English its identity;
- (b) It explores the contributions of Igbo language and culture to the development of the national variety otherwise known as Nigerian English;
- (c) In these ways, it contributes to our understanding of the characteristic features of Igbo English in particular and Nigerian English in general.

At the lexico-semantic level, Igbo English develops its characteristics by means of transfer, borrowings, neologisms and the semantic

extension of certain English lexical items. Igbo English is also created at the level of syntax through the translation of Igbo speech functions, colloquial utterances, de-personalized utterances, temporal adverbs, proverbs, riddles and imagery and also through language mixing.

Overall, what the thesis achieves is the realization of the contributions of Igbo language and culture (through prose texts written by Igbo English bilinguals) to the enrichment of Nigerian English. It is hoped that through this effort, the codification of a standard Nigerian English will be facilitated when the characteristic features of other ethnic varieties of English used in Nigeria are ascertained as has been done in this thesis in respect of Igbo English. In turn, it is hoped that this concerted effort will facilitate the choice of Nigerian English as a national or, at least, official language. This description will also help to produce a model variety of Nigerian English for teaching and examining.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 GENERAL INTRODUCTION

This chapter is a general introduction. It contains the reasons for the adoption of English as a second language in Nigeria, the style of Igbo writers in English, the background of the authors and a discussion on the concept of official and national languages.

The proliferation of articles and books on world-wide English, including the book, English around the World written in 1991 by J. Cheshire, and the existence of the Journal of English as a Second Language and two other journals devoted exclusively to this topic (English World-Wide and World Englishes), attests to the importance attached to the study of English variation in its social context. Cheshire rightly observes here that:

The diversity of form and function within what is nevertheless still thought of as a single language offers a unique opportunity to analyse and document the linguistic variation and change that is occurring on a far greater scale - as far as we know - than has ever happened in the world's linguistic history (p.1).

Although the subject, Nigerian English, has been on since after the publication of Amos Tutuola's fiction The Palm-Wine Drinkard in 1954, and the presence of Onitsha Market Literature, in addition to publications such as Bamgbose (1971), Adeniran (1974), Adekunle (1974), etc., the subject, however, became of greater interest to

scholars in the 1980's, perhaps, following the publication in 1979 of a collection of papers, emanating from a conference in 1978 under the title Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria, edited by E. Ubahakwe. Since then, notable works have been done on this subject; they include Bamgbose (1982b), Awonusi (1985), Ikonne (1986), Adetugbo (1987), Odumuh (1987), Kujore (1985, 1990), Jowitt (1991) and the various papers presented at a conference in 1993 on Language and Literature to mark the 50 years of the British Council in Nigeria, among others. These works have all looked at various aspects of Nigerian English, but the present study agrees with Bamgbose's (1982b) view that the greater need on Nigerian English is to get away from the overflogged issues of Standard vs. Non-standard, International vs. Intra-national, and to concentrate on the task of specifying, describing and analysing the forms of Nigerian English. The current trends in the study of Nigerian English are the questions of codification and the model of English to teach. We will return to these later.

From the volume of work on Nigerian English, we want to state here that Nigerian English is not only real but has constituent varieties (dialectal and diatypic varieties) which call for attention. Quoting Jeremy Warburg's "The Best Chosen English", Amafa (1990) writes:

There are ... different forms of communication employed by different individuals or in different regions, at different periods of time, in different 'culture' groups, or in the pursuit of different activities. Each of these Englishes - has features in common with all other Englishes by characteristics - sometimes unique features of its own, and/or by the characteristic frequency with which it uses features which it may or may not share.

The present study will investigate one of the dialectal varieties of Nigerian English (Igbo English) as used in prose texts.

1.1 THE ADOPTION OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA

The emergence of an "interlanguage" (Corder, 1981, Jowitt, 1991:52) which is today known as Nigerian English is the outcome of the contact of the English language and Nigerian language. The questions which require our answers here are: How do languages come into contact? In other words, how does a bilingual language situation come about? What social factors induce it?

In answer to these questions, Crystal (1987) states that bilingual situation is often of the people's own choosing, but may also be forced upon them by other circumstances which include:

- (i) **POLITICS** (including annexation, resettlement and other military acts which may force the indigenous population to learn the invader's language in order to prosper. A good example here is the Arabic invasion of North Africa which has today resulted in the use of the Arabic language by the indigenous peoples of North Africa.
- (ii) **RELIGION**: People may wish to live in a country because of its religious significance or to leave a country because of its religious oppression. In either case, a new language may have to be learned. For instance, during the 15th century, muslims left Spain to settle with their muslim brothers and sisters in North Africa because of religious intolerance then prevalent in Spain.
- (iii) **CULTURE**: A desire to identify with a particular ethnic group or social group usually means learning the language of that group. For example, most non-Hausa-speaking ethnic groups in Northern Nigeria learn and speak Hausa in order to be identified as Hausa people.
- (iv) **EDUCATION**: Learning another language may be the only means of obtaining access to education. This factor motivates the international use of English.
- (v) **ECONOMY**: Very large numbers of people have migrated to find work and to improve their standard of living. This factor

alone accounts for most of the linguistic diversity of the US and an increasing proportion of bilingualism in present-day Europe.

(vi) **NATURAL DISASTER:** Floods, volcanic eruptions, famine, and other such events can be the cause of major movements of population. New language contact situations emerge as people are resettled. The Bantu migration from the West African region towards the East African region provides a good example of how natural disaster could force a people out of their region.

On the other hand, Dittmar (1979:171) identifies colonization and trade relations as contexts which encourage the speakers of a certain language to learn and use another. But beyond learning and using other languages, it will be important to identify the factors which have led to the implantation and acceptance of English as an official and second language in Nigeria. Three aspects of European contact which have had the greatest impact on Africa in general and Nigeria in particular are trade relations, missionary activities and colonial rule.

Varieties of English in Nigeria date back to the 18th century (Banjo, 1993:2) through trade relations between Nigerians and Europeans. By the time the missionaries came to establish and run their schools, the English language presence was already being felt in

Nigeria. What the missionary schools did was to increase the number of Nigerians who spoke different varieties of English. But during the colonial rule, English became a second language.

So, trade relations and missionary activities could be said to have been the remote causes of the implantation of English in Nigeria by providing opportunities for early contact between the Europeans and the Nigerians. But the most important factor in the implantation of English in Nigeria and Igbo land is colonization.

1.1.1 THE IMPACT OF COLONIZATION

By the beginning of the 20th century, the colonial administration has been effectively established in Nigeria. This was possible because the colonizers who invaded Nigeria with superior arms were able to overcome the stiff resistance of the indigenous people. They imposed their system of government on the indigenes and, expectedly, the language of the colonial administration which was English. The acceptance of the British leadership also meant the acceptance of their culture, including language. The administrators helped to spread English, using the government machinery as well as their Nigerian staff such as court messengers, guards, gardeners,

stewards, etc., who learnt some English from their masters through interaction. The influence of English as the language of the administrator has persisted till today. Since English has remained the official language of education and government, almost all educated Nigerians are bilinguals in English and, at least, one Nigerian language.

Igbo, whose contact with English we are concerned with in this work, is spoken by the Igbo people who mainly live in Anambra, Enugu, Imo and Abia states, and some border areas of Delta, Benue and Rivers states of Nigeria. It is spoken by over 15 million people across the country (Nwabueze, 1985). Igbo (like its linguistic neighbours, Edo, Efik, Yoruba, etc.) is a tonal language, basically of register tone type (Pike, 1948) and a member of the Niger Congo Family.

The economic and social development of the colonial administration in Nigeria created the impression that the colonialists were on a "civilizing" mission. For instance, the 1945 and 1948 Acts of Parliament under the British Labour Government ushered in a period of economic development in British Overseas' Territories. The Colonial Government introduced a cycle of five year development plans which in Nigeria resulted in the development of rail services, roads,

air travel, post offices and postal agencies, sea ports, newspapers, cinemas and educational opportunities. With all these attractive developments, English was, therefore, seen as a language of "civilization". A knowledge of English conferred economic and status advantages on the possessor. This was the major beginning of the implantation of English on the Nigerian society.

Over the years, English has capitalized on the linguistic multiplicity of the country and the fact that majority of the ethnic groups would prefer the use of English as an official language to anyone of the indigenous group languages, to flourish. It has, therefore, become both a second language and an official language in Nigeria.

Defining the 'New English' which has developed as a result of the implantation of English as a second language in certain countries, Platt et al (1984:2) state as follows:

1. It has developed through the education system. This means that it has been taught as a subject and, in many cases, also as a medium of instruction in regions where languages other than English were the main languages. The degree to which English is used as a medium of education for other subjects varies considerably from nation to nation and from one type of school to another.

2. It has developed in an area where a native variety of English was not the language spoken by most of the population. For various reasons, ... pidgin and creole languages are not considered to be native varieties of English.
3. It is used for a range of functions among those who speak or write it in the region where it is used. This means that the new variety is used for at least some purposes such as: in letter writing, in writing of literature, in parliament, in communication between the government and the people, in the media and sometimes for spoken communication between friends and in the family. It may be used as a lingua franca, a general language of communication, among those who speak the same native language but use English because it is felt to be more appropriate for certain purposes.
4. It has been 'localized' or 'nativized' by adopting some language features of its own, such as sounds, intonation patterns, sentence structures, words, expressions. Usually it has also developed some different rules for using language in communication.

1.2 IGBO WRITERS IN ENGLISH

The study of an African writer who writes in English should be understood as a study of a writer who uses English in a second

have two classes of audience in mind - the Igbo or African audience and the European audience. Consequently, he tries not to distance himself from any of his two groups of readers. He uses the English language which is European in such a way that he incorporates the idiom and language resources of Igbo while ensuring that the English language grammar is not terribly distorted. This effort may be conscious.

The problem with the use of English in creative writing by African writers is largely a problem of culture. It is, no doubt, a fact that a society's language is an aspect of its culture (Goodenough, 1957). Language is a carrier of the people's culture. Culture, on the other hand, is a carrier of a people's outlook or consciousness, heritage, and sense of identity. African writers carry and transfer some of the cultural nuances of the indigenous African people into English. To be able to play this role effectively, the structure of native-speaker English has to be adjusted. It is on the basis of this postulation that this work supports Onwubu's (1976) view that for English to express, adequately, the way of life of a different culture, it must endure some internal structural changes. Also in his article, "English and the African Writer", Achebe (1965) advocates that the real African creative writer must alter the English language to suit

African surroundings. The English that emerges from this consideration must be "new" in the sense that it can "carry the weight" of the African writer's experience.

Nigerian writers who use English as their creative medium do so in the consciousness of the fact that they are presenting a Nigerian experience, and most of them reveal in their works a specific mode of imagination which derives from their Nigerian background (Taiwo, 1979:55). This is particularly true since these writers grew up within the Nigerian environment and acquired a Nigerian indigenous language in which they also think. The very fact that these writers now write in English in order to reach a wider readership does not make them English. In support of this premise, Shelton (1969) correctly points out that:

... the somewhat Europeanized Igbo writer is never so European that he is no longer Igbo. This means, precisely, that from an Igbo background one develops knowledge of and habits in the verbal arts which carry over into one's verbalizing abilities when one is using an alien language ... It is the English language which gives way to Igbo thinking and not Igbo thinking conforming neatly and exactly to the alien language.

It is on the basis of Shelton's assertion above that this work undertakes a linguistic stylistic analysis of the works of three Igbo writers - Nkem Nwankwo, Chukwuemeka Ike and John Munonye -

Europeanized Igbo writers whose thoughts in Igbo (their mother tongue) interfere with their use of English, in which they write. The fiction of these authors emanates principally from Igbo life and language. In exploring the Igbo life, they have had to "alter" the English language so as to incorporate the Igbo language features and thought processes which constitute the linguistic characteristics of Igbo English bilinguals.

This work shall examine and describe Igbo English or various instances of intereference (using contrastive analysis) as they occur in Nwankwo's Danda and My Mercedes is Bigger than Yours, Ike's Toads For Supper and The Potter's Wheel, and Munonye's The Only Son and Bridge to a Wedding. In other words, we shall describe (in this thesis) how the language used by the authors here studied exemplifies Igbo English language system.

1.3 THE BACKGROUND OF THE AUTHORS AND THE SUMMARY OF THEIR WORKS

JOHN MUNONYE

Born in 1929 at Akokwa in Imo State, Munonye was educated at Christ the King College, Onitsha, from 1944 to 1948 and in the University College, Ibadan, where he took a B.A. in Latin, Greek and History in 1952. He later did postgraduate work in education at London University, and has been an educator and a novelist.

The Only Son which was Munonye's first novel was first published in 1966 in the African Writers Paperback Series (AWS 21) by Heinemann

Educational Books Limited. In the novel, Munonye uses the relationship between mother and child to show the clash of cultures. Here, Nnanna, the only son of his widowed mother Chiaku, attends a western-run school against the wishes of most of his relatives. Eventually, he becomes isolated from his mother and most of the people in his village, and painfully must become a new kind of African.

Bridge to a Wedding (1978) is Munonye's sixth novel. The theme of broken bridge that has to be re-constructed shapes this novel about a feud and reconciliation set in town and country in post-independence Nigeria. Kafo had offended his cousin, Obieke, and therefore has to leave his home village for another town where he brought up his six children. Rose, his eldest daughter's school friendship with Maria brings the family in touch once more with the village, from where Kafo is excluded. Junior, who is Maria's brother, wants to marry Rose but the ancient feud must be settled before they can be united.

Apart from The Only Son and Bridge to a Wedding, Munonye has written a few other novels published by Heinemann Educational Books Limited: Obi (1969), Oil Man of Obange (1971), A Wreath for the Maidens (1973), and A Dancer of Fortune (1975).

CHUKWUEMEKA IKE

Born on April 28, 1931, in Ndikelionwu near Awka, in Anambra State of Nigeria, Ike went to Government College, Umuahia, University

College, Ibadan, and Stanford University, Stanford, California, U.S.A, where he obtained an M.A. degree. A Teacher and Administrator, Ike is presently a Professor at the University of Jos.

Toads For Supper which was first published by the Harvill Press Limited was Ike's first novel. It depicts the severe setbacks and complications in the life of Amadi, an undergraduate who is engaged to three girls simultaneously. He is accused by one of being the father of her child, and is rusticated by the University authority. Amadi returns to his village to face not only the anger of his parents but the shocked rage of the whole community, at whose expense he is being educated.

The Potter's Wheel which was first published in 1973 by Harvill Press was an outstanding attempt by Ike to demonstrate how damaging the over-emphasis on 'the male child' could be on the life of the child. Obuechina, the only brother of six older sisters has been over-protected and spoilt by his mother. In an attempt to salvage his character, his father decides to send him away as servant to a schoolmaster whose wife is reputed to be wicked. Obu goes and comes back transformed.

Apart from Toads For Supper and The Potter's Wheel, Ike has written several other works among which are: The Naked Gods (1970), The Bottled Leopard (1991), etc.

NKEM NWANKWO

Born on June 12, 1936, in Nofia-Awka, in Anambra State, Nigeria, Nkem Nwankwo was educated at King's College, Lagos and University College, Ibadan - where he studied English. He has been a Teacher and a Journalist.

His first novel, Danda, published in 1963, presents the story of Danda, the hero of the novel who constantly ignores the traditional Igbo virtues of hard work, ambition, and respect for the village elders. Despite being the son of a chief, he is seen as defying the rules of his elders, drinking palmwine, gossiping, dancing and making love to the young wives of the tired old men of the village. Although Danda's attitudes to life depict him as irresponsible, he is yet charming and irresistible to the people of his village.

My Mercedes is bigger than Yours which was first published in the African Writers Series in 1975 is an attempt by Nwankwo to satirize the hero of the novel, Onuma who returns to his village after fifteen years. With his Jaguar, he makes a big hit, especially with girls. However, his problems begin when the car plunges into a ravine. By that time, the money he earned in Lagos had been used up. The only way to replenish his money supply seems to be through working for the candidates on both sides in the run-up to a general election. He gets beaten up by thugs supporting one of the candidates,

and is left driving away in the Mercedes belonging to a cousin he has just shot.

Nwankwo was in 1962 awarded the short story prize of the Lagos Branch of the Nigerian Arts Council for his story "The Gambler". He has also written books for children, Tales Out of School (1963), More Tales Out of School (1965), etc.

1.4 THE CONCEPTS OF OFFICIAL AND NATIONAL LANGUAGES

Ikara (1987) and Elugbe (1990) have extensively discussed the uses of these concepts especially in the Nigerian context. According to Ikara, an 'official language' is the language used by the government for purposes of administration, law, commerce and education, and in all other official functions. But it is only accessible to the elite in society and has no bearing or relevance to the wider community. The English language, for example, is the official language of Nigeria, uniting only about 10% of the people in a common pursuit for material

well-being and cut-throat competition for power and affluence in society, at the expense of the vast majority of Nigerians.

On the other hand, Ikara uses 'national language' to mean a language that has the authority of government conferred on it as the lingua franca of all the ethnic groups in the country: as a matter of deliberate choice by the government, as a symbol of oneness, unity and nationhood and of the achievement of independence in an erst-while colonial state. It is the official language of the country which, apart from being used in the conduct of government business, cuts across the entire strata of society in its use and application. Ikara summarizes the distinction by stating that while an official language is a government-oriented or elite-oriented language, a national language is both an elite and mass-oriented language, integrating everybody into a single political community.

What is certain from Ikara's views on official language and national language is that whereas English has the status of an official language in Nigeria, there is yet no language sufficiently qualified to assume the status of a national language in Nigeria.

Elugbe has further identified three possible interpretations of the term 'national' which will aid our understanding of these two concepts as used in the Nigerian context. Firstly, 'national' may be

interpreted to mean Nigerian so that we are here referring to indigenous. Secondly, we could be discussing national languages in the same sense as of the 1979 and 1989 Constitutions of Nigeria which grant the status of 'national languages' to Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba but not to English. Thirdly, national languages may be languages which are national in terms of their geographical spread: their location is nationwide.

In the first interpretation above, every language that is indigenous to Nigeria, which has a definite location or locations, and is part of an indigenous culture, is a Nigerian language. The English language does not qualify as an indigenous Nigerian language.

In the second interpretation, a national language is a symbol of national oneness, of the achievement of independence and nationhood. English is not a national language in Nigeria. It is one of Nigeria's lingua francas and it is also the official language, being the language of administration, business, secondary and tertiary education, etc. While Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba can be national in so far as they have large constituencies in Nigeria, English lacks any such constituency and is clearly not a rallying point for even a meaningful minority. On the other hand, none of the 3 major Nigerian languages has an official status at the federal level.

The third sense misleads people into thinking that English is our national language. It is being taught nationwide and so has the whole country as its geographical constituency. Unfortunately, this kind of misconception is found even in some official documents. For instance, according to the published report of the survey team on English Language Teaching in Nigeria, which was co-sponsored by the National Universities Commission and the Federal Ministry of Education in 1966 and financed by the Ford Foundation:

Among the nations using English as a second language, few are using it more broadly than Nigeria. In this fore-runner among African nations, English is a 'second' language only in the sense that it is not learned as native language. In respect to the role it serves, it is the national language of Nigeria - the language of government, the language of instruction in the schools, the language of business and commerce, the language of internal communication among Nigerians of differing language backgrounds, and of course, the language of international communication (Jacobs, 1966).

In Elugbe's third interpretation, there is, today, no Nigerian language which qualifies for the title 'national'. In the absence of an indigenous national language, English is continually being used as an official language.

From the discussions above, both Ikara and Elugbe recognize the fact that for any language to become a national language for

Nigeria, it must, in addition to being Nigerian, be able to act as a symbol of oneness and also have a national spread. No language - indigenous or English (in its present form) - can be referred to as a national language in Nigeria. English is presently an official language in Nigeria.

We believe that it can start contesting for the status of a national language after the current effort at codifying the nativized or Nigerianized English. It is then that it will become truly Nigerian and better equipped to play a unifying role.

So far in this chapter, we have examined factors which have led to the adoption of English as a second language in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on the role of colonialism. We have also examined the general style of Igbo writers who write in a second language situation, in addition to clarifying the meanings of the concepts of an official language and a national language.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 VARIETIES OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH

The previous chapter has provided a general introduction to the entire work. The present chapter will attempt to investigate the varieties of Nigerian English by describing the typology of Nigerian English (NE) as well as the characteristic features of both the NE and Igbo English (IE).

2.1 THE TYPOLOGY OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH

Some linguists have identified the varieties of English spoken in Nigeria. They include Brosnahan (1958), Banjo (1971), Adesanoye (1973), Obiechina (1974) and Adekunle (1979). Brosnahan's approach and that of Banjo seem to be the most relevant to this work.

2.1.1 BROSNAHAN'S APPROACH

Brosnahan (1958) identifies four varieties of spoken English in Nigeria based strictly on educational attainments. He recognizes Variety I as that characteristic of Nigerians without formal education but who, through association with native English speakers or educated Nigerian bilinguals have acquired the capacity to speak some form of English. His Variety II is that characteristic of those

with primary education while Variety III is spoken by those with secondary education. Variety IV is used by the University products.

Although formal exposure via education is a vital factor in a second language situation, Brosnahan's typology is deficient in so far as it equates language proficiency with educational attainments on an almost one-to-one basis. It cannot account for other factors which influence linguistic performance. For instance, Brosnahan remains silent on the notion of a "gift for languages" (Wilkins, 1972:180). This explains why a person with a high aptitude for learning languages can perform better than a person with a low ability for learning languages, even though the former is less educated. Apart from language aptitude, exposure can also enhance one's performance in English. He has also failed to realize that a secondary school product who was fully motivated and has passed through good teachers of English can perform better than some undergraduates and even graduates. Similarly, some undergraduates, especially in the sciences are often found performing worse than some secondary school students in spoken English. Another important factor which he has ignored is the point that the degree to which some languages have phonological similarities with the English language can enhance oral performances in

English. For instance, speakers of languages that are intonational will fare better in speaking English than speakers of languages that are tonal (Tiffen, 1974).

2.1.2 BANJO'S APPROACH

Banjo (1971) too, recognizes four varieties of Nigerian spoken English based on the extent of mother tongue transfers and of approximation to a world standard. By categorizing varieties which emerge as a result of varying intensity and quality of exposure to a world standard of English, Banjo seems to have taken care of some of the shortcomings of Brosnahan's classification. His Variety I is spoken by Nigerians whose knowledge of the language is very poor. This variety is characterized by poor phonological, syntactic and lexical features resulting essentially from transfer. With transfer as a dominant feature of this variety, the speaker's ethnic background could easily be identified by someone conversant with Nigerian languages. Banjo regards this variety as not only internationally unintelligible but also socially unacceptable.

Variety II, which is an improvement on Variety I, is characterized by near perfect syntactic and lexical features. Though it is still easy for an informed listener to identify the speaker's ethnic background, there are obviously noticeable phonological features in

this variety. Banjo states that this category of speakers probably forms the majority of all users of English in the country. It is, therefore, acceptable in the country even though its degree of international intelligibility is low.

Variety III is characteristic of those Nigerians whose performances in the areas of syntactic, lexical, and phonological features are very near standard English, 'with RP deep structures and Nigerian surface structures'. This is the variety which Banjo has recommended as the model for educated Nigerian English. Spoken by less than 10% of those who speak English in Nigeria, it is both internationally intelligible and socially acceptable in the country. This variety is also characterized by certain phonological and lexical features of transfer from Nigerian languages to English.

Variety IV is used by a few Nigerians and is characteristic of those brought up in a native English speaking environment or those who have one of their parents being a native speaker of English. Their spoken English or their accent is identical to that of native English speakers. In spite of the high international intelligibility of this variety of English however, it is not socially acceptable in Nigeria. While Variety I exhibits the greatest density of mother-tongue transfer, Variety IV exhibits the least. Similarly, Variety II

exhibits more transfers than Variety III. Banjo recommends Variety III as the educated Nigerian English and not Variety IV because Variety III, unlike Variety IV, is a "home-grown Variety" (Banjo, 1993: 5).

Although Banjo's classification sounds good, there have been some important reactions. For instance, Ayodele (1981, 1983) has noted (especially with Varieties II and III) that it is possible to notice a fairly wide range of differences between performances. He revealed that speakers (particularly of Variety II), whose utterances still bear sufficiently heavy imprints of their mother tongues, have ended up achieving similar intelligibility scores although they came from different ethnic groups.

In the same manner, both Bamgbose (1982b) and Ayodele (1983) question the inclusion of Variety IV in the typology since it does not arise in the same kind of circumstances as the other varieties. Banjo himself has acknowledged the second reaction and has tried to explain in a paper in 1993 that he included Variety IV for "completeness of analysis".

From the on-going analysis, we agree with Ugwu (1990:51) that the variety of English which would qualify as the model for standard educated Nigerian English should possess two essential features:

- a. It should share the common-core features of the English language with the other standard national varieties of English used around the world.
- b. It should possess some indigenous linguistic features which point to its Nigerianness.

2.2 THE CONCEPT OF THE "COMMON-CORE" FEATURES IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

The concept of "Englishness" consists of a common-core or nucleus which can be termed 'English' (Quirk, et al., 1972:13). This nucleus of the language is realized in the various actual varieties of English that are spoken and written in various parts of the world. It is essentially the common-core features of English that impart a high degree of uniformity to these varieties of English so that they are mutually intelligible despite the phonological, lexical and grammatical differences that may exist between them.

Some common-core features of English include the conventions of English orthography, the grammar of English, and the English vocabulary which is presented in the lexicon of the language (Quirk, 1962:99). Quirk also observes that there are some differences between British and American spelling. There is also a recognized

independent orthography for Scottish English. In most cases, however, these differences are so minimal that all the varieties of the language can be said to have a fairly clear and consistent standard conventional English orthography. In the same manner, English syntax is governed by the grammatical rules of the language. Here, Quirk (1962:98) asserts that "a greater part of English grammar is common to all dialects." Consequently, all standard varieties of English are expected to obey the general rules of English grammar.

Similarly, some differences occur in the various national varieties of English in the area of vocabulary. It is often the case that in a situation where target English vocabulary becomes inadequate for the expression of certain concepts, non-native speakers of English usually resort to some linguistic operations such as the creation of neologisms, translation, and so on.

From the discussion above, a conclusion can be reached that the model of English which can serve as standard Nigerian English in the capacity of a national dialect of World Standard English should be the educated variety. As noted earlier in this chapter, this model can be represented by Banjo's (1971) Variety III. This standard model should obey the rules of English grammar and should

preferably adopt the British spelling convention so long it is consistent with this pattern. In addition, its lexicon should, to a large extent, reflect the indigenous culture of Nigeria. In line with our postulation, we maintain that all errors of grammar, pronunciation, spelling, punctuation, etc. are not to be seen as the features of NE. These errors should rather be identified for correction in NE expressions. However, let it be noted here that the influence of Nigerian languages which we find in our use of NE should not be identified and included as errors or as evidence of imperfect learning of English. But since the greatest influence on English in Nigeria is the socio-cultural context in which it is used (Olagoke, 1981:36), the influences of the indigenous languages on English should be considered as possible signs of healthy acculturation, and of the creative capability that we normally associate with mother tongue learning and use.

2.3 THE FEATURES OF STANDARD NIGERIAN ENGLISH

Adetugbo (1979:137) defines NE as "the varieties of English used in Nigeria". These varieties include not only dialectal varieties but also diatypic variants of NE. But Ugwu's (1990) definition of NE seems to be more precise. She defines NE as the "dialect of

the World Standard English which is generally a grammatically correct variety of English language used in Nigeria" (p. 55). It possesses certain linguistic features which are specifically related to some aspects of the Nigerian environment, culture and indigenous languages. These features tend to nativize the use of English in Nigeria and can be identified in all registers of English language use, especially in culture-bound usages.

Among scholars who are committed to the study of NE, there is yet no consensus as to what the distinguishing features of NE are. There is also no generally acceptable criteria by which standards of correctness and acceptability of NE can be measured. However, some scholars, notably Bamgbose (1971, 1982b, 1993), Bokamba (1982), Kujore (1985, 1993) and Odumuh (1987, 1993) have extensively discussed the features of standard NE.

Bamgbose (1993) has identified three important characteristics of standard NE. They are nativization, the influence of the biblical language and the importation of Americanisms.

2.3.1 NATIVIZATION: This consists of three aspects—linguistic, pragmatic and creativity.

(a) LINGUISTIC NATIVIZATION: Linguists have concentrated more on the description of linguistic nativization than the other two.

The process of linguistic nativization includes substitution of Nigerian language vowels and consonants for English ones, e.g. the realization of /θ/ and /ð/ as [t] and [d] respectively in NE; the replacement of stress by tone; and the introduction of culture-specific vocabulary items such as agbada, akara, egusi, suya. Others are semantic shift e.g. academician for English English (EE) 'academic', fellow to refer to an individual, chop for 'food', globe for 'electric bulb', go-slow for 'traffic-jam', long-leg for 'undue influence'; the pluralization of some non-count nouns e.g. equipment, advice; and some Nigerian L1-induced syntactic structures such as:

1. They enjoyed (NE), for They enjoyed themselves (EE)

S P S P C

2. He pregnated her (NE), for

S P C

He made her pregnant (EE)

S P C C

Both Kujore (1985) and Odumuh (1987) have discussed this aspect of nativization in greater detail.

(b) PRAGMATIC NATIVIZATION: There is also the pragmatic use of English in a second language situation. Pressure from cultural practices of the Nigerian environment often modifies the rules of language use typical of English in native situations. The pattern of indigenous greetings is reflected in such NE greetings as sorry (expression of sympathy e.g. to a person who sneezes), well done (greeting to anyone at work), thanks for yesterday (appreciation for a favour done the previous day), till tomorrow (a greeting which may stand for goodnight), etc. Forms of address are formalized to reflect social status and age, with the result that offence may be taken if multiple titles (e.g. Alhaji, Honourable, Chief, Dr. X) are omitted. Another instance of the influence of Nigerian culture on English language use is the peculiar use of kinship terms. Someone who is introduced as 'Uncle Z' may be no more than a family friend. More examples of pragmatic nativization can be found in Bamgbose (1971), Adetugbo (1979) and Akere (1982).

(c) CREATIVITY NATIVIZATION: This manifests in two ways. Firstly, expressions are coined to reflect the Nigerian experience or world-view. Expressions that have emerged following this trend are: to be on seat (to be available in the office), to take in (to become pregnant), been-to (one who has travelled abroad, particularly to

England), four-one-nine (a dupe), etc. Secondly, the Nigerian native idiom is translated into English to reflect the mood of the situation. This is depicted here when Nwafọ Ugo tells Onuma:

3. "You and your like are the lucky ones. You eat the world. If I had read books I would now be equal to the white man. But I couldn't. My chi gave me a dry head" (Danda, p. 102).

Although the words (with the exception of chi) are English words, the idiom is distinctly Igbo and what we have here is like a translation of what would have been said in Igbo into English. Bamgbose (1971, 1993) has more examples of this aspect of nativization.

2.3.2 THE INFLUENCE OF BIBLICAL LANGUAGE: Bamgbose (1993 :12) provides some examples to illustrate the continuing influence of biblical language. They include such common expressions as the evening is far spent, sufficient unto the day is the evil thereof, sing your nunc dimitis, the spirit indeed is willing, coming like a thief in the night, it came to pass, the alpha and the omega, etc.

2.3.3 THE INFLUENCE OF AMERICAN ENGLISH: The third important characteristic of Standard Nigerian English is the influx of Americanisms. This situation is attributable to the highly improved electronic communication (cable television, videotapes, movies), exposure through travel, pop music, increasing number of American trained professionals, the craze for American fashion and way of life (including language style), and the availability of printed material such as magazines and computer software materials in American English.

The influence of American English on NE is obvious in vocabulary and syntax. Some of the popular American vocabulary items used in NE are sidewalk, shorts, station-wagon, custom-made, vacation. Also common in NE are such expressions as Monday through Friday, protest an action, passed away, check out a book, pass the buck, go downtown, step aside, etc.

In so far as the above features contribute to the Nigerianization of English, they can be said to be the markers of Nigerian English. NE is, therefore, a dialect of World Standard English which enjoys a high degree of social acceptability in Nigeria and a fair degree of international intelligibility. It is a national variety of English which is used by the educated Nigerians.

2.4 IGBO ENGLISH

Apart from the national variety of English, there are also ethnic dialects of English used in Nigeria. The study of ethnic dialects is the approach which Odumuh (1987:19) has recognized as ethnolinguistic influences in the study of variation in NE. These influences, according to him, affect all levels of linguistic analysis - phonological, lexical, semantic and syntactic. It is also the same approach which Jowitt (1991:131) refers to as 'ethnic criterion' in the study of NE. This approach involves determining NE usage by way of associating particular phonological, grammatical, or semantic usage to particular ethnic groups, for instance, Yoruba English, Igbo English, Hausa English, etc.

Ikonne (1986:30) has earlier observed on English dialects in Nigeria as follows:

It is no exaggeration to say that there are as many English dialects in Nigeria as there are many Nigerian languages and their dialects.

What Ikonne's assertion implies is that there are noticeable differences in NE usage resulting from ethnic languages. According to him, what we have are "Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, Ibibio, Edo, etc. standards rather than a single unified standard". In a similar research,

Odumuh (1987) identifies three dialects of NE. They are "EngHausa", "EngIgbbo" and "Yoruba English". Similarly, Banjo (1979:8) identifies ethnic language influence while asserting that the numerous indigenous languages still continue to superimpose their phonology, lexis and structure on the various ethnic varieties of English. But in spite of these indigenous language influences, NE demonstrates common-core features which mark it out from other Englishes (Odumuh, 1987).

2.5 CHARACTERISTICS OF IGBO ENGLISH

Igbo English emanates from the influence of Igbo language on English. This influence creates an accent, structure and lexico-semantic patterns which characterize the spoken English of the Igbo people. IE has two major characteristics - Igbonization and the influence of other Nigerian languages.

2.5.1 IGBONIZATION: The first noticeable aspect of IE is the way it has been Igbonized. Such Igbonization consists of three aspects - phonological, lexico-semantics and syntactic.

(a) PHONOLOGICAL IGBONIZATION: This includes the substitution of Igbo vowels and consonants for English ones e.g. the English sounds / ʌ /, / ə / and / ɜ: / become / ɔ / in the IE realization of love, rector and sword respectively; Igbo-influenced syllable

structure e.g. /læmp/ and /pəlis/ in EE will in IE acquire the syllable structure /læmpv/ and /pɔlisi/. Other aspects of phonological Igbonization include the use of epenthetic vowels, vowel harmony, consonant elision and vowel reduplication.

(b) LEXICO-SEMANTIC IGBONIZATION: Igbonization also takes place at this level in the form of lexical borrowing, neologisms, mixed formations and the semantic extension of certain words. This will be exemplified in Chapter Four.

(c) SYNTACTIC IGBONIZATION: As we shall notice in Chapter Five, IE contains Igbo-induced syntactic structures reflecting speech functions, colloquial utterances, language mixing, idioms, proverbs, riddles, imagery and de-personalized utterances.

2.5.2 INFLUENCE OF OTHER NIGERIAN LANGUAGES ON IGBO ENGLISH

Another important feature of IE is the presence of words which are traced to neighbouring ethnic languages. This practice is a reflection of the high degree of bilingualism/multilingualism among the Nigerian people. The Yoruba and Hausa languages have influenced IE more than the other languages. Some Yoruba words

easily used in IE are oba (king), Agbada (flowing gown worn by men), eba (garri), akara (fried bean cakes), moin-moin (a kind of bean-cake, but boiled to taste), etc. Words which have come to IE via Hausa include sultan (the head of the Sokoto Caliphate), suya (roasted meat), Alhaji (muslims who have gone to Mecca on holy pilgrimage), Mallam (muslims who have not been to Mecca), etc.

It is normal, therefore, to find Yoruba and Hausa words and expressions in the novels of Igbo English writers.

IE is the variety of NE in which Igbo writers of English write. As we shall later demonstrate in our analysis of some prose texts in Chapters Four and Five, some features of IE have been identified in the following areas:

- (a) The translation or transliteration of culturally rich expressions from Igbo into English.
- (b) The translation of Igbo speech functions and Igbo narrative devices.
- (c) The transference of words and expressions from Igbo into English.
- (d) The semantic extension of some English lexical items in Igbo contexts.
- (e) It is also characterized by language mixing (involving English and Igbo), mixed formations and colloquial utterances.

NE is a national variety of English which represents the English of the educated Nigerians. On the other hand, IE is an ethnic dialect of English used in Nigeria among the educated Igbo bilinguals. While NE is characterized by a central core of Nigerianness provided by centrally identifiable features which relate to the Nigerian environment, culture and worldview, IE is characterized by a regional core of Igbo-ness provided by certain identifiable features which relate to the Igbo environment, culture and world-view.

2.6 THE INFLUENCE OF IGBO ON ENGLISH

We have demonstrated that there is a variety of English in Nigeria which is different from World Standard English or English English. Similarly, there is also a variety of NE used among the Igbo speakers which can be said to be an ethnic dialect of English. We shall now demonstrate the contribution of this variety to the overall development of NE.

2.6.1 PHONOLOGICAL INFLUENCES

Just as Hausa, Yoruba and other Nigerian languages have influenced NE pronunciation, Igbo has also influenced the pronunciation of NE. These influences have more greatly affected the realization of some English vowels and consonants. Those affected are either

lacking in Igbo or are used in environments which are not permissible in the Igbo language. Consequently, the Igbo speaker has adopted some ways of realizing them by using corresponding vowels and consonants. Igbo influence manifests through the introduction of the Igbo vowel harmony, consonant elision, epenthetic vowels, syllable structure and vowel reduplication.

2.6.2 LEXICAL INFLUENCES

Lexical influences are manifested in two different forms which include lexical borrowing and the extension of the meaning of available English words.

Many Igbo words are used as loan-words in NE. A mother tongue word counts as a loan-word in Nigerian English, provided, according to Jowitt (1991:133), it satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) (a) It has no exact English equivalent, or
- (b) It is used in preference to the English equivalent if such equivalent exists.
- (ii) It occurs regularly and systematically in the English speech of Nigerian users.

Based on Jowitt's criteria for classifying mother tongue words as loan-words, examples of Igbo words which have been borrowed into

Nigerian English would include:

ogbono	-	a kind of soup
egusi	-	a kind of soup
onugbo	-	bitter leaf
ngwongwo	-	meat prepared with much pepper (<i>'pepper soup'</i>)
isi ewu	-	goat head prepared for consumption
eze	-	king
obi	-	title for the traditional ruler of Onitsha
Ogbuefi	)	
Ikemba	)	
Owelle	)	
Igwe	)	
ozo	-	Igbo social rank (title holder)
mazi	-	title standing for <i>'Mr.'</i>
Chukwu/Chineke	-	God
ogbanje	-	a child that dies and comes back
osu	-	Igbo caste system
ego	-	money

chei!	)	
	)	
ewo!	)	- exclamations expressing surprise
	)	
hei!	)	

Also in NE, the meanings of such lexical items as father, mother, son, daughter, brother, sister, uncle, etc. have been extended to embrace the Igbo socio-cultural connotations. Thus, the word father refers to any male who is as old as one's biological father. The same goes for mother. The term brother may be used to include one's half brother, uncle, cousin, and even anybody from one's village depending on the context. This meaning may be so extended that sometimes any Igbo person (wherever he comes from) seen outside Igboland may be referred to as one's brother. The same goes for sister.

The Igbo influence on English has been more prominently felt at the phonological and lexical levels. These influences have resulted in a variety of Nigerian English which has been identified here as Igbo English. The study of Igbo English demonstrates one major way by which the language and culture of a speech community (Igbo) can enrich and enhance the development of another language (Nigerian English).

It is important to demonstrate the influence of English on Igbo in order to illustrate certain bilingual features which are highly relevant to the present study.

Just as English has been greatly influenced by Igbo in the sense that bilinguals often transfer the patterns and features of Igbo into English, Igbo has also been influenced by English which is in contact with it.

One obvious evidence of the linguistic influence of English on Nigerian languages is the large number of vocabulary items which can be traced to loans or loan translations (Bamgbose, 1993:13). Some of the loan words are so old that they can hardly be recognized by the average speaker as having their origins in English. For instance, such items as kop (cup), foto (photo), peelù (pail), windo (window), lampu (lamp), koròta (coal tar), etc. as used in Igbo, have been so well integrated into Igbo that they are often thought of as Igbo items.

This influence also extends to sound patterns. The presence of such spellings as Orlu (for Ọlụ), Onitsha (for Ọnicha), Awka (for Ọka), Anambra (for Anambara), Enugu (for Enugwu), and Owerri (for Oweri) are all evidence of English phonological influences on Igbo.

English consonant clusters in place of the insertion of Igbo epenthetic vowels - broshu (brush), skulu (school), dosta (duster), sweta (sweater). The permission of consonant-endings in words instead of the normal vowel-endings permitted by the Igbo phonology is yet another type of ~~EE~~ phonological influence of Igbo. Examples include items such as kop (cup), stov (stove), botul (bottle), etc.

However, the most obvious influence of English on Igbo is evident from the way the educated Nigerians mix their mother tongue with English. This is the idea of language mixing.

2.8 LANGUAGE MIXING

Linguists have done much work on codemixing and codeswitching (see Aboderin, 1978; Kachru, 1978; Banjo, 1982; Adeniran, 1990b, etc.). What is also certain is that they have used these terms in a somewhat confusing manner. While some writers have used codemixing in a wider sense to include codeswitching, others have equated it with lexical borrowing. Yet others restrict the use of codeswitching to dialect switching. But Banjo has made an important distinction between codemixing and codeswitching in the following terms:

For our own purposes, we will define codeswitching as a phenomenon in which, in a language event, two interlocutors (or the same speaker) make utterances sometimes in Language A and sometimes in Language B. Language-mixing on the other hand, refers to a speech act in which the utterance

contains elements of Language A and Language B. In syntactic terms, we may say that codeswitching occurs in a discourse which is made up of sentences of Language A as well as sentences of Language B, whereas language-mixing occurs in a sentence made up of elements of Language A and Language B. In other words, the domain of codeswitching is the discourse, whereas that of language-mixing is the sentence (1982:18-19).

Sridhar (1978:109) observes that in many bilingual and multi-lingual communities, one often comes across a type of language interaction in which two or more languages in the speakers' linguistic repertoire interact to produce a new 'mixed' code characterized by distinct formal properties and fulfilling specific functional roles. This type of language interaction to which Sridhar refers has been termed 'codemixing' by Kachru (1978), 'language mixing' by Banjo (1982) and 'language interlarding' by Adeniran (1990b). This is also the sense to which we want to restrict the use of the term 'mixed language' or mixed variety.

Igbo English is ~~also~~ a study which focuses on linguistic elements from two different languages. Our study of Igbo English has made a startling revelation. While it is true that in most bilingual

situations, the two languages in contact are complementary in the sense that they are equally mixed to facilitate communication based in any one of the languages, it is also true that in the Nigerian context (as earlier studies have indicated), language mixing is undirectional in that it is only English that always interferes in mother tongue-oriented speech.

A look at the following examples will throw more light on the nature of the bilingual pattern under consideration.

1. Nwaànyị na - acòmplain nà afo nà-ànụ ya ọkụ mà ọ bù nwaànyị na- enwe painful menstruation, mà ọ bù painful miscarriage, ì mara nà ọ bù worm à nà - arīā yā.

English Translation

Any woman that complains of painful warmth in her stomach, or any woman who experiences painful menstruation or miscarriage is suffering from this kind of worm.

2. Speaker A1: The only aspect m chè mà ndị ā gārā Liberia gà na- ème Nigeria affect wụ the economic aspect.

Speaker B1: Of course, the economic aspect dī there.

Speaker A2: And I am sure nà ego oil boom gà - àlacha there.

Speaker B2: Mba, o gaghi alacha there

English Gloss

Speaker A1: The only way in which I think that our involvement in the Liberian crisis would affect Nigeria is in the economic aspect of it.

Speaker B1: Of course, the economic aspect is there.

Speaker A2: And I am sure that the money realized from the present oil boom would be squandered there.

Speaker B2: No, it won't be squandered there.

Note that in (1) and (2), we have a combination or mixture of items from Igbo and English. Observe that the mixed elements above are not single, isolated lexical items. The mixture takes place on every level of grammatical category - single nouns such as worm, Liberia, and Nigeria; verbs such as acòmplain, the entire nominal group at the complement position such as painful menstruation and painful miscarriage; and nominal group at the subject position such as the only aspect and the economic aspect.

The conversation above (which was drawn from a recorded data collected for an earlier work on codemixing) is initiated in Igbo while English items are mixed in such a way that they fit into the Igbo grammatical pattern. A look at the two excerpts reveals that the

mixed elements are not just new or imported concepts for which there are no equivalents. Rather, the mixed elements, to a large extent, involve commonly known items for which perfectly acceptable equivalents exist in Igbo.

The kind of language mixing discussed above is considered as a characteristic of informal speech used mainly in conversation involving educated Igbo English bilinguals. It rarely occurs in written Igbo except for few drama or other literary texts where the artist has employed mixing for special effects. It is also hardly employed on a highly formal occasion where a speaker reads a prepared speech. Factors that motivate this kind of language mixing include topic, habit formation, audience, rhetorical intentions, etc (see Igboanusi, 1990).

However, the kind of language mixing found in most English novels of Igbo authors (as the present study will show) provides a different direction in the nature of language mixing. Unlike the one discussed above, the speech is initiated in English, and we find a situation where Igbo items, structures and thought processes interfere with the use of English. In the same manner, the Igbo concepts and world view also interfere with the writers' use of English. The outcome of this interference is the emergence

of structures which incorporate elements from Igbo and English in the prose texts. In most cases, this kind of language mixing is used to fill lexical gaps. Its nature will be demonstrated in Chapters Four and Five.

Let us state here that this kind of mixing can be a stylistic device as will be demonstrated later in this work.

So far in this chapter, we have identified the features of NE and IE and stated that while NE is a national dialect of World Standard English, IE is an ethnic dialect of NE. Finally, we have also illustrated certain bilingual features with particular attention to language mixing.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

In Chapter Two, we demonstrated that there are common-core features of English that impart a high degree of uniformity to the various varieties of English spoken in different parts of the world so that they are mutually intelligible despite the differences that may exist between them. We also identified the features that characterize both NE and IE. The present chapter will attempt a review of past works on interference and stylistics which are relevant to our study. We will also review more literature that relate to the grammatical and linguistic stylistic models with a view to depicting the application of concepts and findings of systemic linguistics as well as the findings of linguistic stylistics to the analysis of style. Finally, we will present the research design.

Three major issues of concern to linguists in Nigeria today are the development of indigenous languages, the nature and the status of Nigerian English, and the new National Policy on Education, especially as it affects the teaching of indigenous languages along with English. Also connected with the above are the nature of the contact of English and Nigerian languages, the consequent interference problems the contact raises, and their pedagogical implications.

Languages in contact (Weinreich, 1953) in bilingual or multilingual societies result in certain linguistic and cultural changes. The changes may manifest in the form of 'lexical innovation' (Açılönü and Penfield, 1980), 'codemixing' (Kachru, 1978), or in what has come to be known in contrastive analysis as 'linguistic interference', following Weinreich.

3.1 INTERFERENCE

When speakers who have acquired the habits of one language want to learn a second language, there is the tendency for the speech habits of their first language to interfere in their efforts at learning and using the second language. Merio (1978:27) identifies one definition of interference to be "the influence exerted by the grammatical system of the first language on that of the secondary language in violation of the latter's normative grammar". What is not clear here is the scope covered by what Merio refers to as 'grammar' in this definition, since interference is noticeable in all the levels of linguistic abstraction.

For Weinreich, "those instances of deviation from the norms of either language which occur in the speech of bilinguals as a result of their familiarity with more than one language, i.e. as a result of

language contact, will be referred to as interference phenomena" (1953:1). With regard to this type of contact situation, Weinreich suggests that "the differences and similarities between languages in contact must be exhaustively stated for every domain-phonetic, grammatical and lexical - as a prerequisite to an analysis of interference (p.2).

Smith (1979:345) uses the term interference to mean the same thing as "negative transfer". For him, negative transfer pertains to difficulties in using the target language which are mainly attributed to mother tongue interference. He uses 'positive transfer' to imply the ease or facilitation in learning the L₂ resulting from similarities between the L₁ and L₂.

Rather than equate interference with 'negative transfer', Odlin (1989) uses transfer to mean interference. He defines transfer as "The influence resulting from similarities and differences between the target language and any other language that has been previously acquired" (p.26). What Odlin's definition implies is that any language (whether his mother tongue or not) which a child had opportunity to have acquired previously is capable of causing transfer. He considers as interference or transfer a wide range of phenomena, including positive transfer and negative transfer

(including over-generalization, production errors and misinterpretation).

Also interesting in Odlin's findings is his identification of non-structural factors in transfer-personality factor (such as anxiety and empathy), and cognitive abilities or aptitude-given, the fact that individuals vary dramatically in their second language abilities, even when their exposure and motivation seem comparable. He also seems to support Taylor's (1975) study purporting to show that less proficient learners (in terms of achievement) will rely more on transfer than more proficient ones. The following conclusions contained in his work may be necessary for a greater understanding of language transfer.

- (i) Transfer occurs in both informal and formal contexts;
 - (ii) Transfer occurs in all linguistic subsystems;
 - (iii) Transfer occurs among children as well as among adults;
 - (iv) Language distance is a factor that affects transfer;
 - (v) Typological factors can affect the likelihood of transfer;
 - (vi) Transfer can sometimes involve unusual structures; and
 - (vii) Non-structural factors can affect the likelihood of transfer
- (pp. 152-153).

Apart from the interference resulting from the mother tongue, some scholars have identified other causes of interference. For instance, Adeniran (1990a) states that some of the errors may, in fact, have nothing to do with the learner's mother tongue and may instead be traceable to either the target language itself or the method and context of its teaching and learning. Apart from the reasons identified by Adeniran, Tiffen (1969) claims that other types of interference may come from sub-standard forms of English, from pidgin, or from faulty language habits acquired in the primary school.

Although we are concerned only with mother tongue interference in this work, we do not intend to look at errors in the bilingual's performance caused by the interference of his mother tongue. It is rather a study of the influence of the mother tongue on another language within a bilingual context. This powerful influence of the mother tongue on individuals has earlier been highlighted by Whorf (1956:240) when he says:

We cut up and organize the spread and flow of events as we do, largely because, through our mother tongue, we are parties to an agreement to do so... Languages differ not only in how they build their sentences, but also in how they break down nature to secure the elements to put in those sentences.

Past studies (for instance, Tiffen 1969) have located mother tongue interference at three levels - the level of sound, the level of grammar, and the level of lexis.

3.1.1 INTERFERENCE FROM THE SOUND SYSTEM OF THE MOTHER TONGUE

Each language has a different set of phonemes, differing stress and intonation system. The learner transfers the sounds of his own language (or their nearest equivalents) and the stress and intonation system of the language which he is learning. This accounts for the reason why most non-native speakers of English speak it with a different accent.

Another source of phonological interference lies in the irregularity of English spelling which causes many learners to pronounce words as they are spelt. This is known as spelling pronunciation. Nigerian languages have a comparatively regular orthography, i.e. there is a close correspondence between sound and letter. This is not the case with English spelling where the same letter or a combination of letters may represent different words. For instance, the English sound [e] is spelt as e in words like ten, tell; spelt ea in words like head, dead; spelt ai in a word like said. This sound is not written consistently in English orthography and it is capable of causing

interference in that learners employ spelling pronunciation. Spelling inconsistency is more common with English vowels than the consonants.

3.1.2 INTERFERENCE FROM THE GRAMMAR OF THE MOTHER TONGUE

The structure of the mother tongue may be transferred into English, especially in cases where English structures are problematic. Areas of major difficulty usually lie in the handling of English tenses, number, articles, prepositions, passive constructions, gender, and the problem of correct answer to a negative question.

3.1.3 INTERFERENCE FROM THE SEMANTIC OR LEXICAL PATTERN OF THE MOTHER TONGUE

Since language involves the expression of culture, there are usually areas of difficulties in the expression of certain concepts. The major ones include the kinship terminologies, colour, weather or season, cookery/food, building, agriculture, flora-fauna, and time concept.

3.2 THE INTERFERENCE OF MOTHER TONGUE ON ENGLISH:

in the culture, interfere with his learning and using another language (Omoniyi, 1988).

Along the same line, Ervin Tripp has noted that:

When after becoming a practical expert in his own first language, a person starts learning a second language, new sets of decoding and encoding habits are being formed in competition with the old. When the bilingual shifts from language to language, similarly two systems of decoding and encoding habits come into conflict to a greater or lesser degree (1973:15).

Bilinguals can be ranked on a cline of bilingualism depending on their proficiency in the learning of the L2. The movement of individuals along the cline represents different degrees of proficiency in the L2 from sub-standard ability in the use of English to almost native-like control in the use of English.

Some interesting investigations had earlier been carried out on the interference of Nigerian languages on the English language. These include Afolayan (1968), Banjo (1969), Dunstan (1969), Tiffin (1969), Kirk Green (1971), Awoniyi (1974), Oluikpe (1978) and Amayo (1992).

While Afolayan identifies the linguistic problems of Yoruba learners of English, Banjo makes a comparison of the syntactic and lexical rules of English and Yoruba using the Transformational Generative model. Similarly, Awoniyi has also concentrated on

Yoruba while making a sociolinguistic study of Hausa. Both Tiffen and Kirk-Cohen have drawn largely from Hausa examples in their study of interference.

Dunstan in her own study of English Nigerian Languages, including Hausa and Yoruba, makes mention of Igbo phonology. In the same manner, Amayo, who draws his examples from Ibibio, Edo and Efik phonology, has had to explain how Igbo speakers try to tackle some English problem sounds.

So, except for Olukege and the mention of Igbo phonology in Dunstan's and Amayo's works, all other works mentioned above have concentrated more on Yoruba and Hausa. Olukege's work is concentrated on interference at the level of syntax, using transformational grammatical approach and did not employ data from prose texts. The present work is planned to be a comprehensive study of the interference of Igbo on English, covering the levels of lexis, and grammar. It has also viewed interference, not from the point of view of errors (as past studies have done), but as the influence of the mother tongue on the second language with both stylistic and pedagogical significance.

The present study has employed the functional systemic model in the analysis of interference. This model is discussed in detail

later in this chapter. It must, however, be pointed out that the systemic model has earlier been adopted by certain individuals in the analysis of style. Such stylistic studies may be divided into two major groups - those which take scale and category linguistics as the basis for structural analysis (see Halliday 1964 and 1970a, and Sinclair 1966 and 1968; and those which investigate the systemic choices made in text construction (see Halliday 1971b, Short 1976, Osundare 1979, Oyeleye 1985, Ugwu 1990 and Adejare 1992).

The effects of bilingualism manifest in the influence which the native language exerts on the second language phonology, grammar, lexis and meaning. The sound and grammatical patterns of the native language often interfere with the bilingual's use of the second language. It is these features which constitute the focus of this study of the works of certain Igbo writers. Our concern in the works of the writers is to describe the interference observed in their works resulting from their bilingual background. This will involve the identification of Igbo or non-native elements in the authors' use of English or style.

3.3 STYLE

Style has been variously defined by different literary and linguistic theorists. In its commonly used meaning, style refers to

"a way, manner, or form of doing or saying something" (Ellis, 1970: 67). Ohmann (1964:423) says "A style is a way of writing - that is what the word means." Ohmann's definition sounds very authoritative and conclusive, as if to suggest that all issues involved in defining style have been exhausted. But Crystal and Davy (1969) go beyond ordinary definition to distinguish four occurring senses of the term "style" - (i) style as the language habits of an individual; (ii) style as the language habits shared by a group of people at one time or over a time; (iii) style when used in an evaluative sense; and (iv) style used to refer to literary language.

However, according to Freeman (1970:4), recent work in "linguistic stylistics" (Halliday, 1964:302) may be divided into three types: (i) style as deviation from the norm, (ii) style as a recurrence or convergence of textual pattern, and (iii) style as a particular exploitation of a grammar of possibilities.

3.3.1 STYLE AS DEVIATION

'Foregrounding' (Mukařovský, 1970) or 'motivated deviation' (Leech, 1966: 121) from linguistic or other socially accepted norms has been claimed to be a basic principle of style. The norms of the language form the 'background' against which features are prominent because their abnormality is placed in focus. According

to Widdowson (1974), "it has been frequently pointed out that literature, and in particular poetry, contains a great deal of language which is grammatically and semantically deviant". Deviation is a departure from the norm.

The deviation principle stems from the fact that beyond the established norms and regularities, the writer has a reasonable degree of freedom to choose from the linguistic resources of his language, freedom in his use of paralinguistic resources like capitalization, emphatic punctuation, etc. Style as deviation from the norm has been applied more in poetry than in any other genres. Let us point out here that deviation does not mean the same thing as deviance. The distinction lies in the fact that while deviation is well motivated, deviance has the status of errors. The two sentences below illustrate the use of deviant forms in Tutuola's Feather Women of the Jungle:

S P C P

(a) They chased me to kill (p.59)

Won le mi (lati) pa

'They tried to kill me'

S P C P

(b) It was not contain both of them to pass (p. 121)

Ko gba awon mejeeji (late) koja

'There was not enough space for two people to pass'.

The imposition of the serial verb system of Yoruba on English by Tutuola has resulted in the production of deviant forms like those above.

3.3.3 STYLE AS COHESION

The view of style as cohesion and convergence of patterns has been advanced by Halliday (1964) and Leech (1965) in their works on cohesion, which Halliday has described as a grouping of descriptive categories organized around the lexical and grammatical means of unifying a literary text (1970a). Cohesion can be grammatical (such items as anaphoric determiners, pronouns, demonstratives, and certain adverbs (e.g. such, so), or lexical (repetition of lexical items or sequential occurrence of items from the same lexical set). Cohesion or lack of it can be an important factor in the tone of literary prose. Cohesion is a dimension of linguistic description which is important in the study of the literary text (Halliday 1964). This means the way in which independent choices at different points of a text correspond with or presuppose one another (Leech, p. 120).

3.3.3 STYLE AS CHOICE POSSIBILITIES

But "style", argues Todorov (1971:32) "is neither coherence, nor is it deviation." He sees style as choice possibilities. This is also the view held by Ullmann (1959:6) who states that there can be no question of style unless the speaker or writer has the possibility of choosing between alternative forms (Ullmann, 1959:6). The theory of style has so far been essentially based on the concept of "stylistic choice". What constitutes style are the choices which a speaker or writer makes from among the phonological, lexical and grammatical resources of his language.

In the view of Enkvist (1964b:28), the style of a text is "a function of the aggregate of the ratios between the frequencies of its phonological, grammatical and lexical items and the frequencies of the corresponding items in a contextually related norm". This definition accounts for one's choice of certain word typologies rather than others. For example, a writer or a speaker may have preference for active over passive verb constructions. It also accounts for the choice of certain structural patterns over some others. The choices which a language user or a writer makes will constitute the focus of our linguistic analysis in this work.

3.4 STYLISTICS

The name given to the study which looks at style from the linguistic point of view is linguistic stylistics. Halliday (1961:242) equates stylistics with the linguistic study of literature. By the linguistic study of a literary text, one is, in fact, referring to the study of the language of literature from the perspective of linguistics. It is an analysis based on descriptive linguistics—"the study of how language works" (Halliday 1970a:66). It is this approach that qualifies the study to be called 'linguistic stylistics'. In linguistic stylistics, the linguist is interested in knowing why the author chooses to express himself in a particular way, using particular syntactic or lexical structures, (Leech and Short, 1981:13).

In addition, Widdowson (1975:3) defines stylistics as "the study of literary discourse from a linguistic orientation." It is his view that what distinguishes stylistics from literary criticism on the one hand and linguistics on the other is that it is essentially a means of linking the two. Widdowson also maintains that while the ultimate purpose of literary criticism is to interpret and evaluate literary writing as works of art, the linguist aims at describing how an author's peculiar use of language exemplifies the language system.

Interpretation which is the primary aim of the literary critic may only be an aid to the linguist's analysis.

In another article titled "Stylistics", Widdowson (1974:202-203) gives a summary of what could be regarded as a genuine classification and scope of linguistic stylistics as follows:

Stylistics then is the study of the social function of language and is a branch of what has come to be called sociolinguistics. It aims to characterize texts as pieces of communication. It is not part of its purpose to provide a means of discovering the different social functions of language: it is technological rather than scientific in that it works on data provided by others. Texts are assumed to be given.

Linguistic stylistics is, therefore, a branch of linguistics which deals with "the social function of language." It is concerned with the linguistic study of style. What this means is that linguistic stylistics applies techniques and concepts of modern linguistics to the study of literature (Leech and Short, 1981:1). In this regard, linguistic stylistics builds on linguistics.

Style results out of context (Enkvist, 1964b, Crystal and Davy, 1969). This is because language is part of human social behaviour which operates within a wide framework of human activity. So, any piece of language is part of a situation and has a context. Several contextual features that affect one's style could be summarized under

the field of discourse, mode of discourse and tenor of discourse (Gregory and Carroll, 1978). The mode of discourse, for instance, accounts for the reason why, in the written discourse, we are concerned with graphic and not phonic substance. Of these contextual factors, the tenor of discourse - one's relationship with one's audience or readers, influences most, the style of a writer.

It is from this point of view of style as modification of the utterance or piece of writing which results mainly from a consideration of audience or readers (which has resulted in Igbo English) that we are looking at the style of Chukwuemeka Ike's Toads for Supper and The Potters Wheel, Nkem Nwankwo's Danda and My Mercedes is Bigger than Yours and John Munonye's The Only Son and Bridge to a Wedding.

3.4.1 PREVIOUS STUDIES ON STYLISTICS WHICH RELATE DIRECTLY TO THE PRESENT WORK

There have been some previous studies that relate to the present study in terms of research scope and grammatical and stylistic models. They include Young (1969), Osundare (1979), Oyeleye (1985), Ugwu (1990) and Adejare (1992).

Peter Young's Ph.D thesis entitled "The Language of West African Writing in English with Special Reference to Nigerian Prose

Fiction" is relevant to the present study. Though he did not restrict his scope to the treatment of a particular writer's literary style, the work provides some insight into some distinctive features of the West African Literary English variety.

Like Peter Young's work, Osundare's Ph.D thesis, "Bilingual and Bicultural Aspects of Nigerian Prose Fiction" is a work on the application of linguistics to African literature. Working within the systemic linguistic framework, Osundare examines the influence of bilingualism and biculturalism on the content and style of Nigerian fiction. Osundare, like Young, did not direct his study to the style of any particular writer, but his analysis of the Nigerian variety of English employed by some of the writers is directly relevant to the present study.

Unlike Young and Osundare's work, Oyeleye's Ph.D thesis "The Language of Achebe's Early Novels (in the Context of Nigerian English): A Study in Literary Stylistics" is a work on literary stylistics concentrated on a particular writer. His identification of "translation" and 'transference' as stylistic features, following Young and Osundare, has been found useful to the present study. Also relevant to the present study are his choice of Achebe (an Igbo writer in Nigerian English) and his choice of the systemic functional model.

Like Oyeleye, Adejare's book Language and style in Soyinka: A Systemic Textlinguistic Study of a Literary Idiolect, which was earlier published as a Ph.D thesis, concentrates on the style of a particular writer. In analysing the style of Soyinka's works as the features of Nigerian English variety, Adejare adopts systemic text-linguistics which according to him is "an interpretative text model developed from Halliday's popular systemic grammar" (p.6). The relevance of this work to the present work lies in the description of the Nigerian English variety through the use of systemic linguistics.

Ugwu's Ph.D thesis entitled "A Study of some Aspects of Nigerian English in Nigerian Prose Fiction" is highly relevant to the present study. Ugwu's work identifies the distinguishing features of Nigerian English in the literary register of Nigerian Prose Fiction against the background of bilingualism and biculturalism. Her choice of many novels written by Igbo writers, Halliday's functional model and her detailed treatment of certain features of bilingualism have been found very useful.

All the previous studies above have focused on Nigerian or West African writers in second language situations. They have also concentrated more on literary stylistics, while looking at Nigerian

English as a national dialect of the World Standard English used in Nigeria.

3.4.2 THE PRESENT STUDY

The present study has adopted contrastive analysis through translation in its linguistic stylistic analysis of Igbo English (a variety of Nigerian English) in the works of Ike, Nwankwo and Munonye. It considers Igbo English as interference or influences of the mother tongue on the second language, which are here seen as a stylistic device. It also considers Nigerian English as an interlanguage resulting from the contact of English and Nigerian languages. Igbo English is an ethnic dialect of English resulting from Igbo influence on English.

The present work acknowledges the fact that linguistics has relevance for literary criticism just as literary criticism has relevance for linguistics (Bateson, 1971). It is also true that most linguistic stylistic analyses that purport to follow strictly linguistic lines have tended to indicate some judgements, no matter how incidental, that relate to literary criticism. However, this work will attempt an entirely linguistic perspective. This means that we will describe literary texts using the methods provided by descriptive linguistics, particularly systemic functional linguistics.

communication. It essentially gives a proper description of the linguistic features of the text. It must also be pointed out that we will not be analyzing our sentences in isolation but as part of the text as a whole. We will be dealing with features which are regular or prominent in the novels as long as they constitute the significant linguistic features.

GRAMMATICAL MODEL

Systemic linguistics which started in the early sixties with Halliday developing a theory of language known as Scale and Category Grammar is now interested in relating the internal organization of language, the various kinds of patterning which language exhibits to the functions of language and to the social situations of language. Halliday's major claim in this theory is that language structure reflects the social uses to which language is put.

3.6 THE ORGANIZATION OF SYSTEMIC GRAMMAR

The theory requires that linguistic events should be accounted for at a number of different levels. This is found to be necessary because of the differences in the kind of processes of abstraction involved.

The primary levels are "form", "substance" and "context". The substance is the material of the language: 'phonic' (audible noises) or 'graphic' (visible marks). The form is the organization of the substance into meaningful events. The context is the relation of form to non-linguistic features of the situations in which language operates, and to linguistic features other than those of the

item under attention: these together are the 'extratextual features'.

The framework of levels according to Halliday (1961:243-244) and Kress (1976:53) is as follows:

- (a) Substance may be either 'phonic' or 'graphic'.
- (b) If substance is phonic, it is related to form by 'phonology'.
- (c) If substance is graphic, it is related to form by 'orthography' (or 'graphology'), either:
 - (i) if the script is lexical, then directly or
 - (ii) if the script is phonological, then via phonology.
- (d) Form manifests, in fact, in two related levels - 'grammar' and 'lexis'.
- (e) 'Context', like phonology, is an interlevel relating form to extratextual features.

The levels of analysis of descriptive linguistics may be illustrated as below:

	Phonetics ----- Linguistics -----			
SUBSTANCE		FORM		SITUATION (environment)
Phonic	Phonology	Grammar Lexis	Context	extra-textual features

Language is, therefore, made up of substance (phonic substance

of phonic substance. Linguistics covers the study of form and also of phonology from the standpoint of form. Linguistics also studies the relation between non-linguistic features and linguistic form, otherwise known as context.

The levels of analysis of descriptive linguistics, therefore, are phonology, grammar, lexis and context.

3.6.1 GRAMMAR

According to McIntosh and Halliday (1966:5-6), the most fruitful criterion for defining grammar is that it deals with "a closed system". A closed system is a series of terms with the following characteristics:

- (i) The list of terms is exhaustive - it contains (say) a, b, c and no more;
- (ii) each term excludes all the others - i.e. if a, then not b and not c;
- (iii) one cannot create new terms - if a, b, c then one cannot add d.

The fundamental categories of the theory of grammar are 4: "unit", "structure", "class" and "system".

UNIT: It is characteristic of language that patterns occur over stretches of varying extent. In discussing a grammatical item or

category, one may thus ask, in what unit is it operating? Where in the language is this particular choice made? The category set up to account for the stretches that carry grammatical patterns is the 'unit'. The units of grammar form a hierarchy i.e. a taxonomy, such as:

Each unit is made of the unit or combinations of the units next below it in rank.

The theory requires that each unit should be fully identifiable in description. This means that if the description is textual, every item of the text is accounted for at all the ranks.

STRUCTURE: Structure is the second of the general categories of grammar. A structure is an arrangement of elements ordered in 'places'. In the statement of the English clause structure, for example, 4 elements are needed, for which the widely accepted terms

'subject', 'predicator', 'complement' and 'adjunct' are appropriate. Using the capital letters SPCA to symbolize them, we allow for SPC, SAPA, ASP, etc. specifying that every item operating in every clause is an exponent of S,P,C or A. For example:

	S	P	C	A
1.	Obi	bought	some rice	from the market

For one type of group (or phrase), we may have the names 'modifier', 'head', 'qualifier' - M.H.Q with a total range of possible structures H, MH, HQ, MHQ; these possibilities can be stated as (M) H (Q) where the parenthesis mean that M and Q may or may not be present. For example, in the sentence.

	S	P	C	A
2.	I	saw	him	a few months ago

the adjunct is an adverbial group which can be described as follows:

(m)	h	(q)
a few	months	ago

CLASS: We have been able to specify the items according to their functions in the structure of the unit above. This gives us classes - clause, group, word and morpheme classes. There seems to be

three main classes of the group in English: the verbal group (which operates as predicator), the nominal group (subject and complement) and the adverbial group (adjunct). For instance, in example (2) above, the nominal group is made up of the subject I and the complement him. The verbal group is made up of the predicator saw while the adverbial group is made up of the adjunct a few months ago.

The class then is a grouping of the members of a given unit that have the same potentiality of occurrence.

SYSTEM: The fourth grammatical category is the system. Systems are lists of choices which are available in the grammar of a language. For instance, in English, there is a system of number, with the choice between singular and plural; a system of person with a choice between first, second and third; a system of mood with a choice between declarative, interrogative and imperative; a system of gender with a choice between masculine, feminine and neuter; and a system of tense with a choice between past, present and future, etc.

These four categories - unit, structure, class and system - provide the framework for grammatical description. They are also interdependent, for example, the formal item "has eaten" may be the exponent of:

- (i) the unit 'group';
- (ii) the element P in structure;
- (iii) the class 'verbal'; and
- (iv) the term passive in a system.

3.6.2 LEXIS

According to McIntosh and Halliday (1966:18), the relation between lexis and grammar might be put as follows: if one analyzes the grammatical units of a language, one will find that there is one unit below the sentence, many of whose members enter into a different sort of relation with each other in addition to their relations in grammar. This is the unit known as the "word". The word is a grammatical unit like all the others, with its own classes and structures; but it is distinguished from the other grammatical units in that, after it has been treated exhaustively in the grammar, there always remains much to be said about it.

In lexis as in grammar, the items have a contextual and a formal meaning: the definition aims at relating the lexical item, which is a linguistic item, to extra-linguistic phenomena. "Acceptability", for example, has formal and contextual aspects - having a wide range of collocations and operating in a wide range

of situations. In the dictionaries, for instance, words are defined in association. This relation between one word or lexical item and another with which it is associated is called collocation. The collocation of words is the basic formal relation in lexis. Collocation is set up to account for the tendency of certain items in a language to occur close to each other. If, for instance, we say "break the glass" or "a broken glass", or "the breaking of glass", it is in each case the same collocation of the item "glass" with the item "break".

The relation of collocation enables us to group items into lexical sets. The lexical set is formally defined as a grouping of words having approximately the same range of collocations. For instance, the item "economy" is likely to occur in the same linguistic environment as items such as 'affairs', 'policy', 'plan', 'program', 'disaster', etc. If 'finance' collocates with 'economy' and with 'industry', the three items can be grouped together in a set. They, therefore, form a lexical set. Contextually, the set is a grouping of words having the same contextual range, functioning in the same situation types.

A few kinds of collocation include:

- (i) the 'fixed' collocation of lexical items involving 'cliches', e.g. 'In the nick of time'.

- (ii) a case of one or more lexical items which are always tied to a particular grammatical structure. This involves the 'idioms', e.g. "Let the cat out of the bag". You cannot say 'the cat is in the bag'.
- (iii) there are also compound words or what Halliday prefers to call 'compound lexical items', e.g. 'honey-moon'. The list of probable collocations of honey-moon is different from that of honey or of moon and is certainly not the sum of the two.

Collocation and set are, therefore, two fundamental categories required for the formal description of lexis.

3.6.3 PHONOLOGY

Phonology links the substance of a language to its form, as an 'inter-level' (Halliday, 1961: 244). Languages exploit their phonic resources in ways that are too complex to allow us to match phonetic statements directly to grammatical and lexical statements; the bridge is provided by phonology.

The variations in the sounds of language can be subdivided. Acoustically, there is variation in fundamental frequency, harmonic frequency, amplitude and duration; to these correspond what are perceived as pitch, quality, loudness and length.

Phonology is concerned with the phonetic resources as they are used in a given language. Here, we can recognize phonological units which like grammatical units carry patterns; but this time the patterns lie in the distinctive sounds. The units naturally differ from language to language just as phonetic features vary.

For each language, we recognize the phoneme which is the smallest of the phonological units. Normally contrastive at this rank are the articulatory features which shape the consonants and vowels. Above the phoneme, every language has the unit syllable, though in its role there may be considerable variation. In some languages, the syllable often carries stress contrasts and thus enters into rhythmic patterns, while in others such as Igbo, for instance, the syllable carries the pitch. In some languages while pitch is contrastive, it is not in some other languages.

Syllable structure also has to be stated. Every language has a certain number of possible structures at syllable rank. Vowels are the most likely to be syllabic but r, l, m, and n are sometimes syllabic in English and some other languages. English has such syllable structures as v, vc, cv, vcc, ccv, vccc, cccv, etc.

The context will not be discussed as a separate level because according to McIntosh and Halliday, "it is less systematized and more

controversial" (1966:27). McIntosh and Halliday have further explained that it is a principle of general linguistics that defining criteria should be formal and particular. 'Formal' implies first stating the linguistic relations and the items acting as terms in these relations; one then tries to state the contextual meanings, which however, are never given as principal criteria. "Particular" implies that categories are derived first from the language to be described: we can then go on to compare this with another language if this is useful to our purpose. Formal meaning is necessary to an understanding of contextual meaning, because the first is internal to language while the second concerns its external relations.

In An Introduction to Functional Grammar (Halliday, 1985), transitivity, mood, theme, etc. are seen not only as grammatical, but also as realizing a semantics which embodies the ideational, interpersonal and textual functions of language.

A brief explanation of these functions may be necessary in showing how language really works because the structure of language can be explained in terms of these functions.

(i) **IDEATIONAL FUNCTION:** Language is used for the expression of content, that is, our experiences of the real world and of the inner world. In this function, language is used to convey information

about things, ideas, concepts and the processes that exist in the world. One instance of this function at the level of the clause is the system of transitivity. For example, the simple clause Obi died expresses a content in terms of a process ("dying") and one participant ("Obi"). But the content of this clause has been changed in the clause Ibe killed Obi. We now have two participants in the process - the agent and the affected.

(ii) **INTERPERSONAL FUNCTION:** The interpersonal function refers to the use of language for all kinds of linguistic interaction and participation among people in all kinds of context. All instances of dialogue or speech which involve the participation of two or more speakers fall within this aspect. Here, we achieve communication by taking on speech roles in our communication. We can, for instance, assume the role of a questioner or a declarer. This function is reflected in the system of mood, as in the examples below:

- (a) Obi died (declarative)
- (b) Did Obi die? (interrogative)

Also included in the interpersonal function is the use of language to express an attitude towards the content of what is being said, for instance, our expression of the degree of probability. This is reflected in the system of modality.

(iii) **TEXTUAL FUNCTION:** This is the use of language to construct a 'text', that is, the use of language for the production of a coherent piece of spoken or written utterance which forms a meaningful whole. Language here provides a means of making links with itself and the situational context in which it is used. One aspect of the textual function is the establishment of cohesive relations between sentences.

Though these functions reflect the structure of language, they can be present at the same time in the same utterance. For example, in Obi died, the speaker is simultaneously expressing a content (what he has to say), his involvement (his speech role and attitude to the content) and the way he has organized his text as a message. These functions can be summarized as follows:

Ideational	expression of content	e.g. transitivity
-------------------	------------------------------	--------------------------

GRAMMAR

We have earlier stated that all the functions stated above are related to grammar. Each function is expressed in a block of options which may be called components of grammar. Hence, there is the ideational component of grammar corresponding to the ideational function; there is the interpersonal component corresponding to the interpersonal function; and there is the textual component corresponding to the textual function. The ideational component of grammar would include such components as transitivity, nouns, tense, lexical content, polarity, modification, sequence of tense, prepositional relations, co-ordination, aposition, etc.

The interpersonal component would include such options as mood, modality, person, attitudinal modifiers and intensifiers, comments, register, etc. Similarly, the textual component would include such options as theme, predication, reference, substitution, voice (active or passive), deixes, conjunction, collocation, information, presupposition, etc.

The relationship between the functions of language and grammar is that the function of an utterance helps to determine its grammatical structure (Halliday, 1973). Although these functions can be available in a particular utterance, one function is usually more prominent than others.

What we have done so far can be said to be a general outline, organization and operations of the systemic model as contained in the works of Halliday, Berry, Kress and Butler. This is the model we intend to adopt in our analysis.

3.8 STYLISTIC ANALYSIS

Stylistic analysis is very closely related to linguistic analysis. A good stylistic analysis purports a linguistic analysis. But not all linguistic analyses can be said to be stylistic analyses. Linguistic analysis is analysis based strictly on modern linguistic theories while stylistic analysis is a study of style. Linguistic analysis is only a means to achieving stylistic analysis.

In stylistic analysis, linguistic features which are stylistically significant are identified and analyzed. Linguistic stylistic analysis would therefore, imply the analysis of stylistically significant features based on linguistic methods and findings. Linguistic stylistics explores the possibility of describing literary texts independent of any attempt to evaluate the literary effects of its linguistic features.

Two major models of linguistic stylistic analysis based on systemic linguistics exist - those which take scale and category as a basis for a chiefly structural analysis, and those which investigate functional choices made in text construction.

We will here exemplify some of the earlier applications of these models.

3.8.1 LINGUISTIC STYLISTIC STUDIES BASED ON SCALE AND CATEGORY LINGUISTICS

Systemic grammar started in the very early sixties with Michael Halliday developing a theory he called Scale and Category Grammar (see Halliday, 1961). Scale and Category Grammar was a surface description of language. It was taxonomic or structural in the sense that it provided a set of categories into which any grammatical item could be put to show its similarities to and differences from comparable items.

This model has been adopted in the analysis of certain texts (including literary texts). We will here illustrate this approach with a brief analysis of four texts.

Halliday first investigates the use of the definite article in Yeats' poem "Leda and the Swan", pointing out that this differs from the use of 'the' in another of 'Yeats' poem, "His Phoenic", and also in most modern English prose, in that out of ten nominal groups having 'the' plus a modifier or qualifier, only one has a cataphoric use of 'the'. Halliday also examines the collocational patterning of verbal lexical items in 'Leda and the Swan', concluding that those

items with the greatest power to predict their collocates tend to be those in which the 'verbness' is most reduced. He then goes on to contrast three short prose passages, each describing a room, showing differences in three areas: complexity of nominal group structure, the distribution of lexical items belonging to particular lexical sets, and types of grammatical and lexical cohesion.

Also using the scale and category framework, Sinclair (1966 & 1968) attempts two exercises in linguistic stylistic description. He presents a detailed analysis of the grammatical structure of Philip Larkin's poem "First Sight". The structures of sentences, clauses and groups are discussed. And in Robert Graves' poem "The Legs", Sinclair examines the structures of sentences, clauses, nominal, verbal and adverbial groups in some detail.

3.8.2 LINGUISTIC STYLISTIC STUDIES BASED ON SYSTEMIC FUNCTIONAL GRAMMAR

The systemic functional grammar developed by Halliday takes as its base the functionally organized networks of meaningful choices available to the speaker or writer. According to the functional approach, language performs a number of different functions and any piece of language is likely to be the result of choices made on different functional levels. Halliday's (1973) functional model of

language acknowledges three major functions which he calls 'ideational', 'interpersonal' and 'textual'. Halliday goes on to claim that the theme of every novel in a way is "transitivity", the linguistic pattern of choices (a term which for Halliday comprehends relations between verbs, noun phrases and adverbials in the clause).

The systemic functional model has been adopted as the basis for a number of studies in linguistic stylistics.

In William Golding's novel, The Inheritors, Halliday (1971b) investigates transitivity relations. The Inheritors tells the story of a small group of Neanderthal people whose world is invaded by a more advanced group. The processes in this passage are almost all actions, locational, possessional, or mental processes, and they are expressed in the most direct narrative form (simple past tense, active, finite). There is almost always one participant, the "Affected". That is, the clauses contain subjects, but objects and complements are rare.

Short (1976) also applies the same approach to the analysis of a passage from Steinbeck's Of Mice and Men. This passage gives an account of a fight between two characters, Curley and Lennie, which is witnessed by a third character, George, who constantly attempts to keep a simple minded Lennie out of trouble. Short's principal thesis is that the transitivity options adopted in the passage

contribute to the reader's feeling of sympathy for Lennie, and also to the portrayal of George's lack of control over him. All but one of the clauses in which Curley is Actor have Lennie as Goal. They also contain centrally transitive verbs of a lexically powerful nature such as 'slash', 'smash' and 'slug'. On the other hand, the clauses with Lennie as Actor have less centrally transitive verbs with less lexical power, for example, 'look (at)', 'reach for', 'hold on (to)', and do not consistently have Curley as Goal, but are diverse in the persons and things towards which the actions are directed. George's lack of control over Lennie is signalled in a rather different way: here Short briefly leaves the area of transitivity and turns to that of speech function. Lennie and Curley have a distribution of sentence types ranging over statements, commands, questions and exclamations.

3.9 THE APPLICATION OF SYSTEMIC LINGUISTICS TO LINGUISTIC STYLISTICS

Although systemic linguistics was originally intended for a general linguistic description, Halliday has demonstrated in his writings that he is not only interested in language as a system, but also in the application of linguistic techniques in the study of other areas. Particularly, Halliday (1964, 1970b, 1971b), Sinclair (1966 & 1968),

Short (1976) and Butler (1985) have clearly demonstrated that linguistic techniques can be applied to the analysis of style.

The linguist using the systemic model takes as his starting point the text (seen as a semantic unit) and then proceeds to identify and analyze the features of language projected in the text at all the levels of linguistic abstraction.

Text is the basis of linguistic stylistic analysis. The word 'text' is used in linguistics to refer to "any passage, spoken or written, of whatever length that does form a unified whole" (Halliday & Hasan, 1976:1). The linguistic study of literature is textual analysis, and according to Halliday, it is not different from other textual descriptions, but merely involves the application of existing linguistic theories and methods.

There are two major approaches to textual description in systemic linguistics - cohesion and clause analysis.

3.9.1 COHESION

One (linguistic) way of identifying a text is to look at the features of cohesion. A text must be integrated. It is a connected piece of writing. Halliday and Hasan (1976) identify five major ways by means of which cohesion is achieved in English - reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction and lexical cohesion.

(i) **REFERENCE:** This is achieved by the use of pronouns (for instance, anaphoric pronouns such as he, she, it, they, etc.), demonstratives (such as this, that, these, those, etc.) and comparative items (such as the same, similar, likewise, etc.).

In a passage containing more than one sentence, there must be certain linguistic features linking the sentences, thereby contributing to their total unity. Consider the example below:

3. Nigerian athletes performed creditably in the just concluded Olympic Games. They won four medals.

It is clear from the example above that they in the second sentence refers back to (or is anaphoric to) Nigerian athletes. This anaphoric function of they gives cohesion to the two sentences so that we can interpret them as whole. The two sentences together constitute a text. The texture here is provided by the cohesive relation that exists between they and Nigerian athletes. It must also be pointed out that cohesion is achieved not only by the presence of the referring items alone, but by the presence of both the referring item and the item that it refers to.

Like anaphor, cataphor is another type of reference that is used to achieve cohesion. But unlike anaphors, cataphors refer forward to something in the text. Consider the following examples:

- 4.
- (a) Here is a puzzle. How did he enter?
 - (b) Greater love has no more than this - that a man should lay down his life for another.

In the two examples above, the first parts of the short texts above refer forward to certain actions within the texts.

(ii) **SUBSTITUTION AND ELLIPSIS:** Substitution is the replacement of one item by another, while ellipsis is the omission of an item. Essentially, these two types of cohesive relation are the same process. Ellipsis can be interpreted as that form of substitution in which the item is replaced by nothing. Consider the examples below:

- 5.
- (a) Obi was disappointed at your action.
He said so. (substitution)
 - (b) Can she do it? Yes she can. (Ellipsis)

In §(a) above, so is a substitute for Obi was disappointed at your action. In §(b), do it is omitted in Yes she can.

(iii) **CONJUNCTION:** There are three possible areas of meaning in which conjunction can be located - elaboration (e.g. that is, for example, etc.), extension (e.g. and, also, in addition, etc.) and enhancement (e.g. then, finally, likewise, therefore, etc.).

6. (a) I have seen some students who are visually impaired, that is, some students who are blind.
- (b) They had some food to eat and some wine to drink at the party.
- (c) His father is very tall and likewise his mother.

In 6(a), that is is an appositive used to elaborate some meaning. In (b), and is an additive conjunction used to extend meanings while likewise in (c) is a comparative conjunction used to enhance meaning.

(iv) **LEXICAL COHESION:** This refers to the choice of lexical items related to the ones earlier used. There are four types of lexical cohesion - repetition, synonym, hyponym and collocation. Examples include:

7. (a) He wanted to buy a bag but there was no bag. (repetition).
- (b) They wept but the tears made no difference. (synonym)
- (c) Rose is my best flower. (hyponym)
- (d) Ladies and gentlemen, permit me to introduce Dr. Okeke. (collocation).

A look at 7: (a) shows the repetition of the item bag. Wept and tears in (b) are synonyms while in (c) the rose is a kind of flower. Ladies and gentlemen in (d) collocate.

As Halliday (1970b) and Leech (1965) have demonstrated, cohesion can be an important device in the linguistic description of literary texts. However, our data cannot be adequately accommodated for in terms of the analysis of cohesion. This is because cohesion will not enable us to demonstrate all the features or components of systemic functional grammar represented in the novels.

3.9.2 CLAUSE ANALYSIS

There is also clause analysis which may involve any one of the following: transitivity, theme, mood, or structural analysis. This is the approach that we want to explore in our analysis.

(i) **TRANSITIVITY:** In English grammar, for instance, we make choices between different types of process, between different types of circumstance, between different roles for participants and circumstances, between different numbers of participants and circumstances, between different ways of combining processes, participants and circumstances. These choices are known collectively as transitivity choices (Berry, 1977). There is a choice between

three main types of process - a physical or material process, a mental process and a relational process. Each clause chooses between a number of different types of process. Examples include:

8. (a) Ije threw the bucket to Chika (material process).
 (b) I saw him yesterday (mental process).
 (c) Uche is a Lecturer (relational process).

(ii) **THEME:** One way of looking at the clause is to see it as a message. It embodies in thematic structure which consists of two parts - the theme (which is the point of departure of the message about which the clause is concerned) and rheme (the part of the clause that deals with what is said about the theme).

9. The man had gone home
 Theme - the man
 Rheme - had gone home

(iii) **MOOD:** This is a means of achieving communication by taking on speech roles in communication. The English mood consists of indicative (interrogative and declarative) and imperative. Here are examples:

10. (a) Did he die? (interrogative)
 (b) He has died (declarative)
 (c) Go out (imperative)

(iv) **STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS:** As has been noted earlier, in structural analysis, four elements - 'subject', 'predicator', 'complement' and 'adjunct' are appropriately adopted.

S P C A

41. She has exhausted the soup in the pot

It is in clause analysis that our data can be adequately handled, and precisely with the analysis of mood, transitivity and structure.

What are the methods of linguistic stylistic analysis provided by systemic functional linguistics? As we have noted above, the primary unit for linguistic stylistic description is the whole text, seen as a semantic unit. All the levels of description - phonology, graphology, syntax, lexis and context - are seen in relation to the whole text. Also relations within each level are to be explored. For instance, we will relate the writers' isolated lexical or grammatical statements to one another. We will also describe points of contact between the various levels. For example, we will connect the lexical with grammatical details, and the phonological with contextual details. One instance of phonological details being linked up with contextual details is where the sounds of part of a text are genuinely onomatopoeic. For example, the onomatopoeic sounds Kporotokpoto, chololom and fiam can only be understood within the contexts in which they are used.

We will, however, in this work, concentrate on - syntax and lexico-semantics. Graphological features displayed in these novels are not genuinely significant. Context will not be treated as a separate level. Apart from being less systematized, it will be treated as a component part of other levels since it will aid their explanations. Particularly, context has been merged with lexis to form lexico-semantics since most of the features displayed by the lexical items also have contextual explanations.

Although we have some phonological features in the novels which are stylistically significant, we shall however, not describe these features. This is because since we are dealing with written texts, it may be difficult to determine all the motivations for certain peculiar patterns of spelling, pronunciation and syllable structure exhibited in the prose texts.

At the syntactic level, we are interested in the identification of patterns formed by the arrangement of groups and clauses, which have been influenced by the patterns of Igbo structure. Here, we

will adopt Halliday's functional grammar for the analysis of mood (for speech function), the structure of colloquial utterances, temporal adverbs, de-personalized utterances, mixed items and for the analysis of the transitivity systems of proverbs, riddles and images.

At the lexico-semantic level, we shall use collocation and set to describe the lexis while showing how the meanings of some of the lexical items have been extended to embrace the Igbo socio-cultural connotations. To complement the fundamental categories of collocation and set required for the formal description of lexis, we intend to apply the transfer theory as contained in the work of Kachru (1965). Kachru's transfer theory will be discussed later in this chapter.

The distinction between lexis and grammar has not been too sharply insisted upon because, as we shall find in our analysis, lexical items may have grammatical functions.

As for the linguistic stylistic models to be adopted, we will adopt Halliday's model of functional approach which investigates functional choices in-text construction to be able to describe collocational patterning of lexical items and the analysis of grammatical patterns.

Since we have data from more than one author, we shall do a stylistic comparison. In doing a stylistic comparison, we shall take one type of pattern at a time and note its occurrence in several other

texts. We shall also proceed to find out how certain occurrences of some regular linguistic patterns are characterized as distinct styles. Patterns investigated are linguistically and stylistically significant. This is because these features occur frequently within our variety and are also peculiar to this variety.

3.10 KACHRU'S TRANSFER THEORY

In his study of "The Indianness in Indian English", Kachru (1965) attributes the sources of Indian English or Indiannisms to transfer. He uses transfer not only in the sense of interference at any linguistic level, but also in a broader sense to include non-linguistic elements. He considers the process of transfer in Indian English in terms of the following three types:

- (i) **TRANSFER OF CONTEXT:** This involves transfer of those cultural patterns (units) which are absent in those cultures where English is used as L_1 .
- (ii) **TRANSFER OF L_1 MEANINGS TO L_2 ITEMS:** Here the transfer of meaning may result in the extension of the register-range of an item of L_1 . Formal transfer may involve units like the sentence, clause, phrase, collocation or compound words.

(iii) **TRANSFER OF FORM-CONTEXT COMPONENT:** This is essentially determined by those contextual units which are typically Indian and which are not normally used in the L₁ varieties of the English language. Such contexts may be called Indian contexts as opposed to purely English contexts.

Kachru also considers Indiannisms, hybrid formations, the use of lexical items in extended semantic domain and restricted expressions as the outcome of transfer.

So far, we have tried to describe the grammatical and linguistic stylistic models to be adopted for this study. Our linguistic analysis shall, therefore, be based essentially on systemic functional models as contained in the works of Halliday, Berry, Kress and Butler with little modifications, and these models shall be complemented with ~~the transfer theory as contained in the work of Kachru.~~ The ~~linguistic stylistic analysis will adopt Halliday's functional model.~~

3.11 RESEAP CH DESIGN

Our research design will include a methodological statement on contrastive analysis and translation, an explanation on the marking of tones, object: .e of study, assumptions, methodology and choice of texts.

102

3.11.1 THE USE OF CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS IN THIS WORK: A METHODOLOGICAL STATEMENT

McIntosh and Halliday (1966) have observed that there are cases where the influences of the mother tongue have affected the grammatical structure of the foreign language, the pronunciation and even the conceptualization of items in the foreign language. They, therefore, suggest that valid methods of comparison between the two languages which must depend on a general linguistic theory, are needed.

The actual value of contrastive analysis lies in the realization that in learning and using a second language, one is confronted with interference from the native language (Nickel and Wagner, 1968). The interference could be at the phonological, syntactic, or lexical level. This work has adopted the use of contrastive analysis in analyzing the data in the texts since it recognizes the powerful influence of the first language in learning and using a second language. Like the systems and practices adopted in contrastive analysis, we shall compare the various items or structures in the two languages and identify the likely influence of the native language on the writers' English. What is different in our analysis from most other analyses based on this approach, is that we are not identifying errors but influences as stylistic devices. Our approach

to contrastive analysis has further been justified here in the light of the postulation by Nickel and Wagner (p. 254) that:

A contrastive analysis must go beyond mere comparison of rule systems; it must also take into consideration the distribution of rules, with respect to register and style.

Contrastive linguistic analysis has, therefore, been adopted in this work for 'comparability' (James, 1971:58) in order to locate and identify the point of interference of the mother tongue (Igbo) with the target language (English).

3.11.2 CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS THROUGH TRANSLATION

In contrastive analysis, translation may be adopted to compare two different languages. In making comparisons in any two languages, Krzeszowski (1971) suggests that it is necessary to find out which constructions in the two languages are comparable, and to what extent the compared constructions are formally similar. Of great relevance here are Halliday, McIntosh and Strevens (1964) who proposed the criterion of translational equivalence. According to them, only those constructions which exhibit contextual equivalence are comparable. Equivalent constructions are those constructions which, at least sometimes, are mutually translatable (Krzeszowski, p. 37).

Still talking about a contrastive analysis of interference through translation, Kirkwood (1966:178) states that:

At a more advanced level of language learning, contrastive analysis through translation - translation as a means and not as an end in itself, and in small but intensive doses - is a way of bringing to the student's attention points of difference and conflict on semantic and syntactic levels, of coming to grips with these differences and conflicts and to some extent of resolving them. The material selected for translation should be neutral prose rather than passages in a unique and idiosyncratic language bristling with syntactic problems.

What must be emphasized here is Kirkwood's observation that a contrastive analysis in any interference situation will show up the points of difference and conflict. We are of the belief that it is point of difference which often results in conflict (in which we are interested).

3.11.3 TRANSLATION

Translation has been defined as "the replacement of textual material in one language (SL) by equivalent textual material in another language (TL)" (Catford, 1965:20). The question of translation thus is an interlingual exercise which applies to more than one language.

There could be full or partial translation (Catford, p. 21). In a full translation, the entire text is submitted to the translation process: that is, every part of the SL text is replaced by TL text material. In a partial translation, some part or parts of the SL text are left untranslated: they are simply transferred to and incorporated in the TL text. The aim of translation is to provide semantic equivalence between source and target language (Crystal, 1987:344).

In this work, all the instances of interference listed are translated into Igbo with a view to making comparisons between the structures showing where the influences lie. However, in making our translations here, we entirely agree with Nida (1975:27) in his observation that the process of translation may involve loss of information, addition of information and skewing of information.

3.11.4 AN EXPLANATION OF THE MARKING OF TONES

Igbo is a tone language, i.e. one which makes use of the pitch of the voice to make a difference to the meaning of the word or utterance.

Igbo has two distinctive tonemes, High which is unmarked, and Low, marked (\), as well as the tonal phenomenon known as downstep, marked (—) (Emenanjo, 1978:11).

3.11.5 ASSUMPTIONS

This work is based on the following assumptions:

- i. That differences between the bilingual's native language (Igbo) and the target language (English) often result in interference;
- ii. The interference results from the identification of Igbo elements with those of English;
- iii. Patterns of identification and hence interference are regular, and here take the form of transference, translation, and transliteration;
- iv. These patterns are predictable on the basis of contrastive analysis;
- v. Interference can be a linguistic stylistic device;
- vi. It is the English language which is influenced by Igbo thinking, and not vice versa;
- vii. Igbo English will facilitate the teaching of English as a second language in Nigeria and also enhance the development of Nigerian English.

3.11.6 THE OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The interference phenomenon is not new in language studies. Much work has been done on interference especially with a view to finding out the learning problems of bilinguals as well as identifying errors and proffering solutions.

There is, however, the need to look at interference at a more sophisticated level, this time, not only for pedagogical purposes but also as a linguistic stylistic device.

Stylistics is the study of language use. The present study is a work on linguistic stylistics rather than literary stylistics. We have used the theories and methods available in linguistics in order to describe how the author's peculiar use of language exemplifies the entire language system.

The style of the authors here focused on has been identified in this work as Igbo English. This study will explore the usefulness of ethnic dialects of Nigerian English to the teaching of English as a second language in Nigeria. It will also contribute to our understanding of the characteristic features of IE in particular and of NE in general.

We also expect to discover how the systems of one language and the culture of a speech community (Igbo) can enrich and enhance the

development of another language (NE). We will, in addition, bring to view, the implications of the codification and acceptance of NE for language policy formulation in Nigeria.

More importantly, we hope to contribute to the growing literature on the National Language Policy, National Policy on Education, Nigerian English, language development and Igbo stylistics. This investigation will also be a very big boost to Igbo studies which have not attracted sufficient attention. Though this study has been restricted to Igbo language, it can be extended to other languages used in second language situations in future investigations.

3.11.7 METHODOLOGY

The data used in this work are drawn from six prose texts - Danda, My Mercedes is Bigger than Yours, Toads for Supper, The Potter's Wheel, The Only Son and Bridge to a Wedding. The use of data from prose texts drawn from three highly educated and most prolific writers of Igbo origin is deliberate. We have chosen long prose texts rather than passages with unique and idiosyncratic problems of language use, for proper contextualization and comprehensive analysis.

Our data are drawn from two levels: the linguistic performance of the authors themselves and the linguistic performance of the fictive characters of the novels. These two levels are inter-related in that

the author is both the writer of the narrative and the dialogue of his characters.

In carrying out this investigation, this writer has relied heavily on his own Igbo English bilingual competence. However, occasional reference has been made to the judgements of other competent persons. The choice of informants is based on the conviction that they are competent Igbo-English bilinguals.

3.11.8 CHOICE OF TEXTS

Some factors were taken into consideration in the choice of texts for analysis. Firstly, the choice of prose texts instead of poetry or drama texts was motivated by the conviction that all the components of systemic functional grammar will be fully represented within the novel. There is also the desire to choose texts which will facilitate the full description of linguistic stylistic component of systemic grammar.

Secondly, we have chosen the writers' earlier and later works to be able to establish that the variety under study is a regular feature in the writings of the authors. For John Munonye, we have chosen The Only Son (or TOS) 1966 and Bridge to a Wedding (or BW) 1978, Chukwuemeka Ike - Toads for Supper (or TFS) 1965 and The Potter's Wheel (or TPW) 1973, and for Nkem Nwankwo - Danda (1963) and My Mercedes is Bigger than Yours (or M.M.) 1975.

CHAPTER FOUR

TEXTUAL ANALYSIS: LEXICO-SEMANTICS

We have, in Chapter Three, discussed the grammatical and linguistic stylistic models we intend to adopt for our study. In Chapters Four and Five, we shall be engaged in textual analysis at the levels of lexico-semantic and syntax, using the grammatical and linguistic stylistic models discussed in Chapter Three.

4.0 LEXICO-SEMANTICS

Differences in world-view or cultural set up usually result in the use of different terminologies. Culture, according to Lyons (1968) is reflected by language while language also determines our perceived reality. The language of a particular society is an integral part of its culture, and lexical distinctions drawn by each language will tend to affect the culturally important features of objects, institutions, names, events and activities in which the language operates. According to Oyesoro (1988), both the physical and social environments affect language.

Contextually determined Igbo lexical items used here may involve the transfer of meaning from the native culture of the Igbo writers. We will, therefore, adopt collocation, lexical set and transfer theories for our lexical analysis.

Items organized into lexical sets (as used in the texts) include flora-fauna, food, musical objects, religious institution, political institution, days, and kinship terms. These are some of the sources of Igbo English as demonstrated in the prose texts.

HEADING	LEXICAL SET
i. Flora-fauna	`utazi, `ukwa, cassava, bitter leaf, `ora, cocoyam, umunē, `nkakwū, `nchi, amalocha, etc.
ii. Food	`abacha ncha, aku `okukoro, garri, `afufu, `ngwo `ngwo, `egusi, `okro, `ogbono, `ojiugo, cola, ose oji, etc.
iii. Musical Objects	`Ogene, ekwe, `uyọ, samba, `oja, koso, etc.
iv. Religious Institution	chi, `ogbanje, `mbedikē, afa, alū, agwū, alūsī, amosū, dibia, `ikenḡa, `ofọ, etc.
v. Political Institution	`obi, `ozọ, umunna, eze, etc.
vi. Days	`nkwo, oyè, `afọ, `eke, etc.
vii. Kinship terms	mother father, mothers, fathers, brother, sister, father's sister, son's wife, son's child, father's father, father's brother, etc.

These items which reflect the Igbo world-view have been organized into lexical sets to enable us to have an idea of their meanings.

In the case of (i) above, the Igbo society has some names of animals such as òchì, òkàkwū, amalọcha, etc. and some names of plants such as cocoyam, ùtazi, ụkwà, akpụ, ụdalà, umunē, ụra, bitter leaf, etc. which may be absent in societies where English is used as a mother tongue. Instead, the English societies may be more familiar with such plants as tobacco, mangoes, oranges, etc. and such animals as elephant, lion, tortoise, snake, etc.

While the Igbo society is familiar with such names of food items as àbàchà nchà, àfufū, ògwò ògwò, ògbòòò, oji ùgò, osè oji, etc., the English society may be familiar with such food items as bread, tea, coffee, spaghetti, rice, etc.

In Igbo society, names of musical instruments popularly used are ògenè, òjì, ekwe, ùyò, samba, etc. In the English society, more sophisticated musical instruments such as brass, guitar, saxophone, etc. are known.

Names associated with religious worship in the Igbo world-view include chi, ògbañjē, alūsī, agwù, amōsū, òkèngà, òfò, etc. On the other hand, names associated with religious worship in the English world-view include God, satan, amen, church, etc.

The Igbo political institution revolves around titles/institutions such as *eze*, *òbi*, *ozò*, *umunnà*, etc. The English political institution revolves around titles/institutions such as king, Queen, president, governors, rulers, etc.

Igbo days are named after such market days as *̀nkwọ*, *̀eke*, *̀afọ*, and *oyè*. English days go by the names Sunday, Monday, Tuesday, etc.

The important kinship relations in Igbo are mother, mothers, father, fathers, father's sister, mother's sister, father's father, mother's mother, son's wife, etc. The important kinship relations in English are mother, father, son, daughter, brother, sister, grandson, grand-daughter, uncle, aunt, cousin, etc.

The result of these differences in the use of vocabulary is that translation equivalents for such Igbo items that are absent in the English world-view may be difficult to achieve. This fact explains the presence of Igbo nouns at the lexical level in the novels.

In addition to the concepts of collocation and lexical set outlined in Halliday's model of systemic linguistics, we also want to describe the linguistic process of transfer as outlined in Catford (1965) and also Kachru (1965), which determines the choice of lexical items as will be shown below.

4.1 TRANSFERENCE

In the sense used in this work and the sense used in most other linguistic literature, the process of transfer is used not only in the sense of interference at any linguistic level but also to include the transfer of language and cultural habits. Kachru, in his study of Indian English, identifies three types of the process of transfer which are also relevant to this study. They are:

1. transfer of context;
2. transfer of L₁ meanings to L₂ items; and
3. transfer of form context component.

Catford has tried to explain the meaning of transference by differentiating it from translation. He notes that in normal translation, the TL text has a TL meaning as there is no carry-over into the TL of values set up by formal or contextual relations in the SL. It is, therefore, possible to carry out an operation in which the TL text or parts of the TL text, do have values set up in the SL: in other words, have SL meanings (Catford, p. 43). Culture-bound features pose the greatest problem for the African writer, and are more manifest at the level of lexis. In the face of this difficult situation, the African writer could not avoid transference, which manifests in various forms. Transfer, therefore, becomes a major source of IE at this level.

4.2.2 ITEMS TRANSFERRED TO FILL LEXICAL GAPS

One aspect of transference is where the writer is dealing with words that have no direct lexical equivalents in English. These words are, therefore, used as loan-words in English. A mother tongue word counts as a loan-word in Nigerian English, provided, according to Jowitt (1991:133), it satisfies the following conditions:

- i. (a) It has no exact English equivalent, or
 - (b) It is used in preference to the English equivalent if such equivalent exists.
- ii. It occurs regularly and systematically in the English speech of Nigerian users.

Based on Jowitt's criterion for classifying mother tongue words as loan-words, the following Igbo items may have been transferred to fill a lexical gap:

- 12' (a) "You have probably heard that music: the nervous agony of the ekwe, the poignant melancholy of the òjà, the clamorous swell of the drums and the plaintiveness of the ògene" (Danda, p. 20).
- (b) "For it was in this section that the chieftain of Amocha and most of the ozò men sat" (Danda, p. 21).

- (c) "It is my misfortune ... I have a weak lkenqà, I think" (Danda, p.26).
- (d) "Mazi Laza retired to his Obi ..." (TPW, p.57).
- (e) "On the advice of Nwakaku, that woman who had such ill luck with ogbanje children" (TPW, p. 43).
- (f) "Use some utazi and cook it so that I'll have plenty of pottage water to drink" (TPW, p. 106).
- (g) "A few days after Chiaku had arrived, Oji invited all the umuñnà to his house" (TOS, p. 18).
- (h) "Then the umuāda, direct female descendants of Ojamba, sent word that they would come and open the new house" (TOS, p. 19).
- (i) "He will be here on next afò day" (TOS, p. 135).

Though the full Igbo meanings of the transferred items may not be understood by an English reader, the contexts in which they are used may give some insight into their meanings.

The use of ekwe, òjà and ògenè in the context of music in (a) above signals that the words so used have to do with musical instruments.

In (b), the presence of chieftain in the same sentence with ozò is a pointer that ozò must also be something that has to do with leadership, high status, and perhaps, a title.

In Igbo traditional religion, Ìkèngà stands for spiritual strength. Whatever fortunes or successes accruing to someone are attributed to one's Ìkèngà. In the same vein, whatever misfortune or ill-luck is attributed to one's inactive or weak Ìkèngà. So, the presence of weak Ìkèngà in the context of misfortune in (c) assists the reader in understanding the meaning of Ìkèngà.

In (d), the use of obi in reference to retired to links the meaning of obi to a habitable place (a kind of house).

In (f), ùtazi is used together with cook. That shows that ùtazi is an edible material. The presence of invitation and his house while talking about umunna indicates that umunna in (g) must be referring to a group of human beings (who are related).

The meaning of umuāda in (h) is easier to understand because it occurs in apposition with its real meaning - direct female descendants. The use of afò as a modifier of day in (i) shows that afò must be a type of day.

All these instances of transference above can be seen as lexical borrowing where words in Igbo are borrowed into English to fill lexical gaps.

4.1.2 TRANSFERRED ITEMS WITH PARTIAL EQUIVALENTS

These are instances of transference where some Igbo words have equivalents in English, but their equivalents may not accommodate all the social and semantic nuances of the Igbo language items. Here too, the contexts within which the items occur facilitate their understanding.

Examples include:

- 13 (a) "Let the gods wipe out this thing that has come into the land in our time"
 "Òfo!" they chorused.
 "May the spirits of our fathers prevail"
 "Òfo".
 "May custom prevail!"
 "Òfo!" (TOS, p. 77).
- (b) "Chiakụ had adopted this plant as the abode of her chi"
 (TOS, p. 30).
- (c) "... he would build up the homestead and keep the ama
 - the approach to the homestead - open and broad...."
 (TOS, p. 63).
- (d) "Giant ukwà, fried without being burnt, and nicely shelled ready for the mouth" (TPW, p. 126).

- (e) "Samuel spewed moist earth as a dibia sprays masticated alligator pepper on a patient" (TPW, p. 132).
- (f) "That fan contained a powerful ogwu without which the izagā would be blown off his spindle legs and come crashing to the earth". (Danda, p. 18).

In 13 (a), the lexical item ofo is retained in its Igbo version without being given an English equivalent. Contextually, one may interpret it to mean a refrain that expresses joint assent to the particular course of action. It may also be a ritualistic interjection. To this extent, the near equivalent English item amen may not bring out all the required meanings of ofo, and is thus retained in its original Igbo form.

In the Igbo traditional religion, in addition to 'Chukwu/Chineke' which stands for "God", we also have 'chi' - one's own "personal god". English does not have any word for one's personal god. The use of God in that context may conceal some meanings which the author wants to represent. This explains why the writer retains "chi", which is an Igbo word, in (b).

Homestead in English may mean a "farm house" or a house with land and out buildings round it. In Igbo, ama may mean a homestead, the approach to a homestead or a village square. The English item

may not bring out all these meanings associated with ama and so the writer retains the Igbo version, as in (c).

A near English equivalent of ukwà is the seeds of a variety of the breadfruit tree. In Igbo, ukwà may mean the breadfruit seeds fried or boiled or cooked to be eaten. It may also refer to its raw form or even to the tree itself. This explains why the author chooses to retain the Igbo form rather than the English equivalent, in (d) above.

In English, the lexical item "doctor" (medical) is used to refer to somebody who has been trained in medical science as a physician or surgeon. In Igbo, the lexical item dibia as in (e) can be used to mean a herbalist, a diviner or a 'native doctor'. The word dibia suits the author's context more and so he prefers to adopt it.

In English, the item medicine means a substance taken to prevent or cure diseases. In Igbo, ogwù in addition to the English meanings may also stand for poison, charm or drugs. Ogwù, therefore, affords the writer a larger scope of meanings to express his culture.

4.2 MIXED TRANSFER

Another type of transfer which has featured prominently in the works of our authors is what can be regarded as "mixed transfer"

or in Kachru's terms "mixed formations". Mixed formations are those formations which comprise two or more elements and in which, at least, one is from the native language and one is from English. Kachru has also stated that these items need description in terms of the composition and also in terms of contexts in which such formations function in the native language.

In mixed transfer, the item from the source language and its partial equivalent from the target language are placed side-by-side to form a nominal group. In the nominal group, the English word functions as the head word while the Igbo item functions as the modifier. This is a direct influence from Igbo in the sense that Igbo often adopts the use of a head word and a modifier to describe or specify the type of tree, title, family, bird, soup, day, market, festival, masquerade, market, leaf, etc. The reason is that since each of the above mentioned items or activities comprises several other types, it then becomes pertinent to specify the type of item or activity referred to.

This type of transfer is more prominent in Danda than the other novels. Consider the following examples:

<u>IGBO ENGLISH</u>			<u>IGBO</u>	
<u>MODIFIER</u>	<u>HEAD</u>		<u>HEAD</u>	<u>MODIFIER</u>
Ọgbụ	tree (p.5)	FROM DANDA	Osisi	ògbụ
ọzọ	title (p.7)		echlchi	ozọ
uruọjị	gathering (p.18)		mgbako	uruọjị
umụèzè	family (p.18)		ezi nà ụlọ	umuèzè
akwalà	string (p.23)		eriri	akwalà
amōsū	birds (p.55)		nnunụ	amōsū
ègusi	soup (p.70)		ofe	ègusi
akpakā	tree (p.83)		osisi	akpala
ube	tree (p. 140)		osisi	ùbe
ọra	soup (p.31)		ofe	òra
ụdalà	fruit (p.78)	ogbe	ụdalà	
mgbedikē	meeting (p.26)	ogbako	mgbedikē	
okwè	tree (p.29)	osisi	okwe	
ègusi	seeds (p.84)	mkpuru	ègusi	
okro	soup (p.84)	ofe	okro	
umunē	leaf (p.66)	akwukwo	umune	
iroko	leaf (p.154)	akwukwo	ọjị	
iroko	tree (p.55)	osisi	ọjị	
oyè	day (p.102)	ụbochi	oyè	

àfò	day (p.135)		ụbọchị	àfò
àfò	market (p.18)	} FROM <u>TFS</u>	ahịa	àfò
Ikeji	festival (p.60)		emume	Ikeji
odo	mask (p.60)		mmonwu	odo
mgbèdikē	mask (p.61)		mmonwu	mgbèdikē
ogbono	soup (p.97)		ofe	ogbono

While Igbo structure permits the occurrence of the modifier following the head word, the English structure permits the occurrence of the modifier before the head-word. As we have seen from the IE examples above, the source language item (Igbo) somewhat modifies the English item collocating with it. The English items which are the head words help the reader to understand the meaning of the Igbo items. Mixed transfer or mixed formation provides a good source of IE vocabulary especially in the prose texts.

4.3 LITERAL TRANSFER

We have also identified three types of collocational pattern which may be regarded as aspects of literal transfer. This is another device by which IE vocabulary is created in prose fiction. Three aspects of literal transfer has been identified:

- (i) Those that are derived from Igbo language pattern;
- (ii) Those which are grammatically different from those of English; and
- (iii) Those with contextual units that are absent from English culture (Kachru, 1965).

4.3.1 TRANSFER DERIVED FROM IGBO LANGUAGE PATTERN

The Igbo lexical patterns are here transferred into English through a process which may be regarded as literal transfer. We see in these collocations, compounds that follow the process of analogy of Igbo compound system. This pattern is more prominently adopted in Danda, as the examples below indicate:

14 (a) IE: "The many people who had followed the progress of the land-boat with awe now came from several directions and surrounded it." (p.5).

IGBO: Ndi nīlē jībū ụjō na-esò ugbo àlà ahụ sịzìrì ebe dī ichè ichè bià gbaa γā gbùrù gburù.

EE: Many people who had followed the progress of the car with awe now came from several directions and surrounded it.

(b) IE: "True word" (p.6)

IGBO: Eziokwū

E.E: Truth

(c) I.E: "We have done it, son of our fathers" (p.9).

IGBO: Ànyị e meela yā, umù nnā ānyī

EE: Our kinsmen, we have done it

(d) IE: "Go and get me the hot drink" (p.10)

IGBO: Gaa wètere m̄ mmanya okū ahụ.

EE: Get me the hard liquor.

(e) IE: "I will go to her parents and ask for my bride price" (p.41).

IGBO: Aga m̄ aga nàrà nne nà nnà ya ego àkù nwaanyi m̄.

EE: I will go to her parents and ask for my dowry.

(f) IE: "They are giving him the water of God there, and he has a new name" (p.62).

IGBO: A nà-ème yā mmiri Chukwu ebè ahụ.

O nwèzìrì ahà oḥurụ.

EE: He is getting baptized there. He now has a new name.

(g) IE: "Two market weeks later, they came to Araba's compound". (p.63).

IGBO: Oge izu ahia abụọ gachara, ha were bịa n'ezị na ụlọ Araba.

EE: Two weeks later, they came to Araba's compound.

(h) IE: "So you were drinking with spirit worshippers" (p.63).

IGBO: Ya bụ na gị na ndị ọgọ mmụọ na-anụko mmanya.

EE: So you were drinking with heathens.

A look at the above formations shows that the Igbo collocation patterns (as illustrated in the Igbo translations) have been transferred into IE by the author. This practice justifies the definition of transference which according to Catford involves "an implantation of SL meanings into the TL text" by the bending of English and the moulding of it into a new shape (Oyeleye, 1985:119).

The interference in 20 (a) lies in the fact that ugbo ('boat') is used in Igbo to refer to anything that is capable of carrying people to different destinations. Hence there is ugbo elu (literally meaning 'up-boat' i.e. aeroplane), ugbo ala (literally meaning 'land-boat' i.e. car) and ugbo mmiri (literally 'river boat' i.e. canoe or boat).

In (b), eziokwu is a compound word with the components ezi ('true') and okwu ('word'). So, true word is a literal transfer from

the Igbo language pattern of eziokwu meaning truth.

The same explanation is also applicable to the use of son of our fathers in (c) instead of our kinsmen; hot drink instead of alcoholic drink in (d); bride price instead of dowry in (e); water of God instead of baptism in (f); market week instead of week in (g) and spirit worshippers instead of heathens in (h)

4.3.2 ³TRANSFER WHICH ARE GRAMMATICALLY DIFFERENT FROM THOSE OF ENGLISH ENGLISH

We have examples of this type of literal transfer from TOS, especially with the use of Igbo number system. Examples include:

15 (a) IE: "She counted them in units of five heads, one head being six shells. They totalled up to fifty heads and five" (TOS, p. 15).

IGBO: Ọ gụrù hà n'isi isē isi ise. Otù isī bù àyàrì ìsiī.
Ha ñchā gbàrà àrì àto nà ìri ato.

EE: She counted them in units of five and they totalled three hundred and thirty in all.

(b) IE: "She announced: Twenty heads and ten in five places. Twenty heads and ten in five places is what we give to you" (TOS, p.26).

- IGBO: O kwuru na ihe ha nwere bu ogu isi na iri n'uzo
ise.
- EE: She announced that they had nine hundred in all.
- (c) IE: "Far and wide, even in parts of Umudiobia of ten
villages and two ..." (TOS, p.28).
- IGBO Ma ya burugodu n'umu mba iri na abuo nke
Umudiobia
- EE: Far and wide, and even in parts of the twelve
villages of Umudiobia.
- (d) IE: "That would give us twenty pounds and five.
Twenty and five" (Danda, p.125).
- IGBO: Nke ahụ ga-enye anyị ohu ego na ise. Ohu na
ise.
- EE: That would amount to twenty-five pounds.
Twenty-five.

A careful examination of the above formations shows strong traces of interference both in the use of units as quantifiers and the grammatical structure of the units. Here, units of measurement are not just forms like one, two, three, four, etc. but in heads and places.

Before the white man introduced the modern money system, the Igbo people traded and made purchases with beads. These beads were

usually arranged in shells and counted in units. The Igbo number system was then very limited, and to be able to express the unlimited English numeration, there had to be groups of numbers counted and kept differently with a view to recounting them in units.

Another important feature of the Igbo counting system then was that the Igbo counting system was done in 'twenties' or ogu in Igbo. This means that after counting from one to twenty, every subsequent count depended on twenty. It was such that forty would be counted as ogu àbuō or "two twenties" (twenty into two places) while thirty would be counted as ogū nà ìri or "twenty plus ten." Today, the Igbo counting system is done in tens for convenience. Instead of ogū standing for twenty, we now have ìri àbuō (ten into two places).

In the examples listed in (15) above, there is a constant combination of the usual figures such as twenty, five, ten, and two, with Igbo units of heads.

These units were also modelled after the grammatical pattern of the Igbo counting system and not after the grammatical pattern of English, even though English figures are used. As we tried to explain above, in the Igbo counting system, the use of the conjunction "na" meaning 'and' or 'plus' is very vital when counting figures above ten. For instance, the figure eleven is iri na otu (literally meaning ten + one or ten and one); twenty five is iri abuo na ise (twenty and five or twenty + five, etc.) Consider, for instance:

15. (a) Fifty heads and five instead of fifty five heads.
 (b) Twenty heads and ten, instead of thirty heads.
 (c) Ten villages and two, instead of twelve villages.
 (d) Twenty pounds and five, instead of twenty five.

The interference pattern here is regular. This counting pattern can only be meaningful when used in the context of the Igbo world-view. This type of transfer is a vital source of IE at this level of linguistic description.

4.3.3 TRANSFERRED ITEMS WITH CONTEXTUAL UNITS WHICH ARE ABSENT IN ENGLISH CULTURE

The process which operates here is the process of transliteration. Transliteration rules, according to Catford specify transliteration equivalents in two ways. First, in not necessarily being relatable to the same graphetic substance as the SL letters; second, in being (in good transliteration) in one-to-one correspondence with SL letters or other units (p.66). Transliteration may, however, be regarded as a form of translation which is almost word-for-word.

Transliteration is prominent mainly when the authors are using expressions that may be termed "igboisms". Igboisms are usages that reflect traditional Igbo life and cultural habits. These expressions are easily understood in Igbo but are lacking in English

contexts. What we have covered in our use of igboism have been reflected in Danda and TOS, as well as in B.W. and T.F.S. as shown below:

16. (a) I.E.: You have unfortunate legs (Danda, 37).
 IGBO: I nwèrè ukwu ojoõ.
 E.E: Sorry, I have just finished eating.
- (b) I.E.: Call them to feast and they would start very early to watch the sun, every now and then saying to their wives: Is it time? (Danda, p.143).
 IGBO: Kpọọ hā n'òriri, ha gà-èbido n'ùzọ ututù na-àcho anyanwū mà na-àjụ ndi nwunyè ha mà ogè ò ruola.
 E.E: Once it involves feasting, they will be very conscious of time.
- (c) I.E.: He flutes from the cry of the cock to the time the chicken return to roost" (Danda, p.26).
 IGBO: O nà-ègbugide òjà site n'ogè òkukō kwàrà akwa rukweē mgbè ha labàrà nà mpie.
 E.E: He flutes from morning till night.

- (d) I.E.: "We shall leave very early in the morning before the chicken come out from the pen" (TOS
- IGBO: Anyị gà-apū n'uzọ ututù - tupu umū okukò esi na mpie pūta.
- E.E.: We shall leave very early.
- (e) I.E.: "The shadow was almost at her feet when Chiakụ reached the entrance door of her house" (TOS, p.1).
- IGBO: Enyo anwū nò n'ukwu yā mgbe Chiakụ rūrū n'ihu uzọ ya.
- E.E.: It was almost noon when Chiakụ got to the entrance of her house.
- (f) I.E.: "He didn't speak with two mouths. When he said yes, it was yes." (Danda, p.114).
- IGBO: O kwughi onu abuo. Ee ya bụ ee.
- E.E.: He spoke the truth. He is honest.
- (g) I.E.: "Yours is a bad tongue, mother". (B.W. p.98).
- IGBO: Nne, i nwere onu ojoo.
- E.E.: Mother, you speak provokingly.

(h) I.E.: "What I have come to tell you is that you must wash your eyes in water" (T.F.S., p.43).

IGBO: Ihe m biara igwa gi bu na i ga-asa anya gi na mmiri.

E.E.: I have come to ask you to be very careful.

In 16(a) above, unfortunate legs or ukwu ojoo in Igbo is used when a visitor has arrived just at a time the host is finishing his food. The context is lacking in English culture.

Examples (b) to (e) reflect the Igbo yardstick for measuring length of time. This yardstick for measuring time is quite different from that which obtains in societies where English is used in a first language situation. The English determines time through the use of watches and clocks so that they can talk in seconds, minutes and hours. They also use temporal adverbs to determine period of time such as days, weeks, months and years.

The Igbo determine time differently. The use of watches and clocks is unknown, so that such minute details of time as seconds, minutes and hours are also absent. The Igbo determine time by monitoring nature, such as the position of the sun at any given time or the size of the shadow. This is reflected in the statements contained in (b) and (e) above.

The use of two mouths in Igbo as in (f) above usually refers to the state of dishonesty or unreliability. Any person that speaks with two mouths is not to be trusted in the Igbo culture. Similarly, bad tongue is used to describe the attitude of talking rudely. Wash your eyes in water as in (h) is an advice which the parents or elderly ones usually give to the younger ones when they fear that the younger ones could be charmed or poisoned by the enemies. These expressions make meanings only when they are spoken within the Igbo context.

The Igbo, apart from monitoring the position of the sun and the size of the shadow, also determine time by monitoring the crow and movements of cocks. Morning begins in the Igbo world-view with the crow of cocks. There are three stages of this - the first crow, the second crow, and the third crow. The movement of the fowls out or back to the roost marks a particular stage in time. This concept of time is reflected in (c) and (d).

The Igbo also use events and temporal adverbs with Igbo cultural background to determine a particular period of time.

17. (a) I.E.: "It took him two market weeks to recover completely" (Danda, 109).
- IGBO: Sò izù ukà abuo kà o riàrà ihe tupu ò dīchāā ya mmā.
- E.E.: It took him two weeks to recover completely.
- (b) I.E.: "I think, though, Okaka is a few moons younger (TOS, 45).
- IGBO: O jiri onwa ole na òle tōta Okaka.
- E.E.: I think, though, Okaka is a few months younger.
- (c) I.E.: "The five of them were doing very well ... would probably give birth within four moons or five". (TOS, p.79).
- IGBO: Ha anō na-eme ofuma ... ha nwekwara ike imū nwa n'ime onwa anō mà ò bù ise.
- E.E.: The five of them were doing well and would probably give birth within the next four or five months.

We can see the contrasts from the IE and EE versions. All the contexts described above are lacking in English culture. These contexts are, therefore, some of the devices for creating IE collocations.

4. NEOLOGISMS

These are newly coined words resulting from the prevailing socio-linguistic factors in Igboland in particular and Nigeria in general. Most of these coinages appear in the form of compound English words which merely paraphrase the Igbo concepts. Some of the examples include:

18. (a) chewing stick (TPW, p.110) - washing stick
'òtita osisi' - 'atu'
- (b) long throat (TFS, p.44) - covetousness
'ogologo akpìrì' - 'àkpìrì ogologo'
- (c) bitter leaf (TFS, p.37) - bitter vegetable
'ilu akwukwọ' - 'òlugbò'
- (d) wooden bowl (TFS, p.39) - bowl
'osisi efere' - 'ikwè'
- (e) mud house (TFS, p.41) - house
'aja ụlọ' - 'ụlò ajā'
- (f) small cough (TFS, p.83) - tuberculosis
'nta ụkwara' - 'ụkwara ntà'
- (g) up wine (TFS, p.52) - palmwine
'elū nkwụ' - 'nkwụelū'

Neologisms are important sources of IE vocabulary.

4.5' THE SEMANTIC EXTENSION OF VERBS

As the examples below illustrate, some English verbs have been used to collocate with some nouns which have enabled them to acquire extended meanings.

- 19: (a) I.E.: "Do you know book?" (M.M., p.137)
 IGBO: ì mà akwukwo?
 E.E.: Are you educated?
- (b) I.E.: "You eat the world" (Danda, 102)
 IGBO: ! nà-èri ùwà
 E.E.: You are enjoying yourself.
- (c) I.E.: "For long, they have been eating my money (Danda, p. 110).
 IGBO: Kamgbè kà ha nà-èri egō m̄
 E.E.: They have been extorting ~~some~~ money from me for some time.
- (d) I.E.: "A man's heart eats many sad things" (TOS, p.121).
 IGBO: Obì nwokē nà-èri ọtụtụ ajọ Thē.
 E.E.: Man is very enduring.

- (e) I.E.: "Please get a good priest-doctor to look into his head" (TOS, p.9).
- IGBO: Bikō kpòta ezigbo dibìà kà o lebànye anyā n'isi yā.
- E.E.: Please get a good doctor to observe him.

In 19(a), know collocates with book, and it is used to mean being educated instead of its basic meaning which is 'to be able to recognize'. Eat in (b) collocates with the world. Eat in English means 'to take (solid food) into the mouth and swallow it'. But it is used here to mean 'to enjoy oneself'. However, eat in (c) has a different meaning from its meaning in (b). In (c), eating collocates with my money, and it means 'to extort money from someone'. Similarly, eat as used in (d) is used to mean endure. In English, look means 'to use one's sight', but it has been used in (e) to imply 'to observe one's innate activities'.

4.6 THE SEMANTIC EXTENSION OF NOUNS/PRONOUNS

Just as the meanings of some verbs have been extended, some English nouns have acquired new or extended meanings in the context of their use in the novels. Examples are:

- 20 (a) I.E.: "Anyway that boy never looked as if he was going to be something in life" (TOS, p.56).
 IGBO: È nwebèghì m̀gbè nwa ahū ỳrì onye ga-awụ ihē na ndụ ya.
 E.E.: It has never appeared as if that boy was going to be useful in life.
- (b) I.E.: "Who should divide the thing in the soup?" (TOS, p.59).
 IGBO: Kèdu onye kwēsīrī ikè ihē dī n'ōfē?
 E.E.: Who is supposed to share the meat in the soup?
- (c) I.E.: "Are you in doubt about who should share the thing in the soup?" (TOS, p.59).
 IGBO: Ọ gbagwòjùrù ụnụ anya màkà onyē ga-ekè ihē dī n'ōfē?
 E.E.: Are you in doubt about who should share the meat in the soup?

The pronoun - something - refers to an object, event, etc. of an indefinite nature. Thing, on the other hand, refers to any material object. But in 20 (a) above, something is used to mean 'being useful' while thing is used in (b) and (c) to refer to meat.

4.1 KINSHIP TERMS

A society's kinship is generally reflected in its kinship vocabulary. Beattie (1964) says of kinship: "A kinship system is not just a collection of distinct mutually exclusive terms, each denoting a different kind of geneological and social relationship ... rather than a whole way of life, and it can be understandably a thorough investigation of the language, values, and behaviour of the people who have it". Kinship terms, however, vary from one social context to the other.

At this level of lexical analysis, we will observe that the various uses of kinship terms to illustrate the relationship between persons are greatly influenced by the Igbo culture which is sharply different from the English culture.

In English, we have such kinship terms as father, mother, brother, sister, uncle, aunt, nephew, niece, grandson, grandfather etc. These distinctions are based on sex. In Igbo, apart from mother and father, the others are not distinguished according to sex. Again, while the English operate the nuclear family system, the Igbo operate the extended family system. The result is that while you can make a distinction between a brother, uncle, nephew, etc., in Igbo they are all your brothers. The individual, in the Igbo society sees

his kinship system as a reflection of the inter-personal relationships between parents and children, siblings such as brothers and sisters, and grand parents and grand children.

The man addressed as father may not be one's biological father. It may refer to any male who is old enough to be one's father. The same goes for mother. Nwanne which translates for the English brother or sister covers the English sense of siblings, nephews, and cousins. The farther you are from your home the more the meaning widens.

The following examples illustrate the various uses to which kinship terms have been put by the novelists.

21. (a) I.E.: "Men of our land, did you not tell me that this land-boat belongs to one of my brothers?
(Danda, p.7).
IGBO: Ndi be anyị, ọ kwà ụnụ gwàrà m nà ụgbọ àla à bụ n'kè otù n'ime ndị nwannē m nwokē?
E.E.: Gentlemen, did you not tell me that this car belongs to one of my kinsmen?
- (b) I.E.: "He's staying with Oboka for the night. Oboka who is his father's sister? (TOS, p.13)

IGBO: O ga-anọ̀ nà òkè Òbòkà n'abàlị̀ à-Òbòkà òkè bụ̀ nwanne nnā yā.

E.E.: He's staying with his aunt, Oboka, for the night.

(c) I.E.: "Fetch one or two more pots for your son's wife" (TOS, 15).

IGBO: Kùtekwuoro nwunyè nwa gị otù mà ò bụ̀ ìtè mmirì àbụ̀ò.

E.E.: Fetch one or two more buckets of water for your daughter-in-law.

(d) I.E.: "Nwanòlue, his father's father was a good friend of our father ..." (TOS, p.17).

IGBO: Nwanòlue, òkè bụ̀ nna nna ya bụ̀ ezigbo enyi nna anyị.

E.E.: Nwanòlue, his grandfather was a good friend of our father.

(e) I.E.: "Have you greeted your mothers?" (TOS, 18).

IGBO: Ì kèlego ndi nne gị?

E.E.: Have you greeted your relations?

- (f) I.E.: "Chiàkù, your sisters have come to open your new house" (TOS, p.19).
 IGBO: Chiàkù, ndi umù nne gī nwaanyi biàrà imēpē ụlò ọhụrụ gī.
 E.E.: Chiakù, your relations have come to commission your house.
- (g) I.E.: "His father's brother who is a member took him ..." (TOS, p.40).
 IGBO: Nwanne nnà ya òke bụ onye òtù kpògàrà ya.
 E.E.: His uncle who is a member took him.
- (h) I.E.: "Don't forget that he is your late brother's son and therefore your own flesh and blood" (TOS, p.9).
 IGBO: E chefukwana nà ò bụ nwa nwanne gī nwokē òke nwurụ anwụ mà bụrụkwa otu ọbara gī.
 E.E.: Don't forget that he is your nephew and, therefore, your own flesh and blood.
- (i) I.E.: "In addition, you are my husband's father come to life" (TOS, p.170).
 IGBO: Ọzọ kwa, ò bụ nna di m lórò gī.
 E.E.: In addition, you are my father-in-law come to life.

In 21)(a) above, one would presuppose that the speaker is talking about somebody of the same parents with him. He uses brothers where the English would use kinsmen. In (b), the father's sister is used where the English would have used aunt. In (c), the term son's wife is used instead of the more likely English daughter-in-law. His father's father in (d) replaces the more likely English term grandfather.

The use of mothers in (e) instead of just a mother is an instance of cultural transfer, where a child is regarded as a son to all the elderly female members of his extended family. A child is often expected to use the term mother not only for his mother, but for all his mother's female friends and all the elderly members of his extended family. The same applies to the way father is used in the same context.

In (f), Chiaku is said to have sisters which contradicts what we have read in the novel which identifies Oji and Chiaku as the only brother and sister, and not with brothers or with sisters. The term father's brother as used earlier is equivalent to the English uncle. In (h) brother's son refers to the English nephew while husband's father in (i) refers to father-in-law.

The use to which kinship terms are rendered into English are instances of interference resulting from the extended family structure

in which the use of the normal English kinship terms would be interpreted as lacking affection, emotion, and solidarity that the extended family system projects.

We have so far analyzed how differences in world-view or differences in ways individual societies conceptualize the world can create differences in vocabulary, meanings and usages. In the face of the fact that the Igbo society has different experiences of the world, different cultures and different environmental influences, it is little wonder that these differences are reflected in the people's attempt at using English. So, the examples we have described above are good instances of interference or IE at the lexico-semantic level. In other words, all the various kinds of transfer, semantic extension of words, borrowing and neologisms described in this chapter, are sources of IE at the lexico-semantic level.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 TEXTUAL ANALYSIS: SYNTAX

In chapter four, we identified and described interferences at the lexico-semantic level. At the syntactic level, we are going to analyze how the structures of the Igbo language have influenced the structures of English. The influence of Igbo structures on English will be concentrated on speech functions (such as threats, abuses, greetings, curses, praises and blessings), colloquial utterances, temporal adverbs, de-personalized utterances, and the structure of codemixing. We shall also analyze the structures of proverbs, imagery and riddles.

As we shall notice at this level, interference occurs through the process of translation (with the exception of the structure of codemixing). Translation has been defined as "the replacement of textual material in one language (SL) by equivalent textual material in another language" (TL) (Catford, 1965:20). Though the African writer writes in English, his reality is different from that of the English writer in Britain or the United States. For the African writer, he has been used to conceptualizing his African experiences in his mother tongue. Faced with the task of rendering these experiences in English, his thought processes interfere with his use of English. He has, therefore, to translate his experiences into English.

Translation of this nature could be conscious or unconscious (Oyeleye, 1985). The question of translation is an interlingual exercise which applies to more than one language, and so the problems of translation will relate to the nature of language acquisition and usage. Experiences with African writers show that conscious translation applies to such writers with little education as Tutuola and Onitsha pamphleteers. Unconscious translation pertains to cases of highly educated writers as Soyinka, Achebe, Nwankwo, Munonye, Osundare, etc.

There could also be full or partial translation (Catford, p.21). Partial translation which Catford defines as a kind of translation where some part or parts of the SL text are left untranslated and are simply transferred to and incorporated in the TL text, is common in literary translation. This is also particularly so in literary works written in second language situations either because some SL lexical items are regarded as "untranslatable" or for the deliberate purpose of introducing 'local colour' into the TL text.

Translation is normally easier where the writer is dealing with universal features, but where the literary features are culture-bound or where they are restricted to a particular social group, translation becomes very difficult.

In the present chapter, we will describe attempts by writers

at translating speech functions, colloquial utterances, temporal adverbs, de-personalized utterances, proverbs, images and riddles from Igbo into English. The translation of these Igbo speech habits are some of the sources for creating IE structures.

In doing a syntactic analysis of these Igbo speech habits, we will adopt ~~the~~ systemic functional approach of Halliday. Halliday identifies three major functions of language - ideational, interpersonal and textual functions. He states that most utterances combine more than one of these functions simultaneously, even though one of the functions may be emphasized in a given utterance. For example, in Obi has died, the speaker is simultaneously expressing a content (what he has to say), his involvement (his speech role and attitude to the content) and the way he has organized his text as a message. The content of that statement which performs the ideational function is about a particular subject (Obi) who went through a process of action (dying). The interpersonal function is our realization of the fact that somebody made the statement expressing his emotion to someone. The textual function here is the organization of this statement into an acceptable clause structure using S.P. (Subject - Obi, and Predicator - has died) to convey the information.

A look at the structure (Obi has died) indicates that it is a

declarative statement. In declarative statements, the ideational function is usually emphasized because it is the content of the message that is made explicit. On the other hand, interrogative and imperative structures emphasize the interpersonal function because of the involvement of the speaker and the listener at a given time.

The example above illustrates Halliday's theory of sociological semantics which defines the relationship between the social functions of language and the grammatical structures of the utterances which encode them in terms of meaning. According to Halliday (1973), the meaning of an utterance is realized as one or more of these macro-functions (ideational, interpersonal and textual) determines the nature of the grammatical structure of the utterances. Halliday, therefore, postulates that the grammar of the clause is the most appropriate structure for conveying information about things, processes, etc.

We will fully explore Halliday's functional grammar in the present chapter. In doing this analysis, we should realize that like the other varieties of English, the IE structures described in this chapter are grammatically correct. Errors which are not stylistically significant are not to be accepted as IE structures. We will identify the

sources of IE structures and attempt to describe them with a view to demonstrating the structural features that make them IE.

5.1 THE STRUCTURE OF SPEECH FUNCTIONS

The term "speech functions" has been used by Kachru (1965: 399) to describe certain forms of communication such as abuses, curses, greetings, blessings, flattery, mode of address, reference, threats, praise names, titles, etc. Speech function is not the same thing as speech act. Speech act (also known as locution) is a meaningful utterance. It serves two basic functions - illocutionary function and perlocutionary function. Illocutionary function is one's own intention in an utterance while perlocutionary function is the effect of one's utterance on another person. If, for example, one says to another person, "Look behind you", the speaker's intention may be to warn the listener about danger. This utterance performs illocutionary function here. But if the listener gets frightened as a result of the utterance, the utterance here performs perlocutionary function. Speech functions are uses of speech with fixed forms in any language while speech act refers to any meaningful utterance in a language.

Igbo speech functions have been rendered into English by the

authors through translation. Some of the speech functions identified in the novels include:

5.1.1 CURSES

These are emotional utterances made in certain contexts often prompted by anger, disgust, frustration or the desire to frighten or intimidate someone. In Igbo, most of this type of utterances are made in the form of wishes intended to bring evil or misfortune to someone. Usually, the Igbo item "Ka" meaning "Let" or "may" which may be regarded as an auxiliary operator is often used in making wishes. Even when certain wishes are made in Igbo without Ka, it is still assumed to be there. This explains why the curses which we are going to illustrate below may be written with or without Ka, and in both cases they mean the same.

22. (a) IE: "Amaǹzè and his wives, may an iroko tree fall on their heads" (TOS, p.26)
- IGBO: Amaǹzè nà ndị nwunyè ya, kà osisi oji dàgbukwā hā.
- EE: That a big tree shall fall and kill Amanze and his wives.

- (b) IE: "Amanze and his wives, may they never meet good luck in this life (TOS, p.30)
 IGBO: Amanze na ndi nwunye ya, ka ha gharakwa ihu ihe oma n'uwa a.
 EE: That Amanze and his wives should always encounter misfortune.
- (c) IE: "May dysentery purge you to death there
 IGBO: ka afo sagbukwaā gi ebe ahụ.
 EE: That one should die of purgation.
- (d) IE: "May God bend your neck there" (TPW)
 IGBO: ka Chukwu gbajikwaā gi olu ebe ahụ.
 EE: That God should bend one's neck.
- (e) IE: "May the food choke you, lazy one" (TOS, p.110).
 IGBO: Nni ahụ gbàgbukwaā gi, onye ahụhụ.
 EE: That food should choke you the lazy one.

All the utterances above have a peculiar structural description. They are all imperative constructions. This is because they all have subject-operator inversion. As we may have known, the normal subject-operator inversion results in interrogative utterances in English. Consider the examples below:

- 23 (a) Declarative: $\overbrace{\text{John}}^{\text{Subject}}$ $\overbrace{\text{will}}^{\text{Auxiliary operator}}$ go to school tomorrow
- (b) Interrogative: $\overbrace{\text{Will}}^{\text{Aux}}$ $\overbrace{\text{John}}^{\text{S}}$ go to school tomorrow?

23 (b) is the structure of interrogative sentence in English with the inversion of the subject - auxiliary operator demonstrated in the declarative structure in 23(a) above. The subject - operator inversion has been adapted in IE to form imperative constructions as demonstrated below:

- 24 (a) Declarative: $\overbrace{\text{Iroko tree}}^{\text{S}}$ $\overbrace{\text{may}}^{\text{Aux}}$ fall on their heads
- Imperative: $\overbrace{\text{may}}^{\text{Aux}}$ $\overbrace{\text{iroko tree}}^{\text{S}}$ fall on their heads
(curse)
- (b) Declarative: $\overbrace{\text{They}}^{\text{S}}$ $\overbrace{\text{may}}^{\text{Aux}}$ never meet good luck in this
life
- Imperative: $\overbrace{\text{May}}^{\text{Aux}}$ $\overbrace{\text{they}}^{\text{S}}$ never meet good luck in
(curse) this life
- (c) Declarative: $\overbrace{\text{Dysentery}}^{\text{S}}$ $\overbrace{\text{may}}^{\text{Aux}}$ purge you to death
there

- Imperative: $\overbrace{\text{Aux}}$ $\overbrace{\text{S}}$
 May dysentery purge you to death there
- (d) Declarative: $\overbrace{\text{S}}$ $\overbrace{\text{Aux}}$
 God may bend your neck there
- Imperative: $\overbrace{\text{Aux}}$ $\overbrace{\text{S}}$
 (curse) May God bend your neck there
- (e) Declarative: $\overbrace{\text{S}}$ $\overbrace{\text{Aux}}$
 The food may choke you lazy one
- Imperative: $\overbrace{\text{Aux}}$ $\overbrace{\text{S}}$
 May the food choke you, lazy one

A look at the description above shows the inversion of the normal word order of declarative statements which go without subject operator inversion. The auxiliary operator may which is used is a direct translation of the Igbo ka. This has essentially resulted in the IE structures described above. To the extent that the constructions above are imperative clauses, they have the interpersonal function as the dominant function because they are commands given by someone to another.

5.1.2 BLESSINGS / PRAYERS

Blessings or prayers like curses are wishes which unlike curses are meant to bring someone some fortune or good luck. Also like curses, blessings or prayers begin with ka which is equivalent to the modal auxiliary may. This is also a direct structural influence from Igbo and has resulted ⁱⁿ the IE structures below:

25
25. (a) IE: "May each man have what is due to him" (Danda, p.123)

IGBO: Kà onye ò bu₁la nwetakwa ihe ruoro yā

EE: Let every person's desire be fulfilled.

(b) IE: "May the spirits of our fathers prevail"

IGBO: Kà e mezùo uchè nnā anyị hà

EE: Let the spirits of our fathers prevail.

(c) IE: May custom prevail

IGBO: Kà e mezùo omenàlà

EE: Let custom prevail.

All the IE structures above have the same pattern as curses. They are all imperative constructions which can be subjected to the same structural analysis as curses, and therefore, belong to the inter-personal component of grammar.

5.2 THE STRUCTURE OF COLLOQUIAL UTTERANCES

Colloquial utterances are styles of usages that are only suitable for ordinary or informal conversation. The Igbo usually have colloquial contexts. These colloquial contexts reflecting the style of Igbo life have been infused into English expression through translation. This has resulted in IE structures.

Certain utterances may be regarded as colloquial in these novels, particularly Danda and TOS, in terms of their semantic interpretation, the collocation of their lexical items and the informality associated with their use. These expressions have been translated into English with some of their Igbo patterns still being retained. Examine the following examples:

26
36 (a) IE: $\frac{S}{I}$ $\frac{P}{know}$ $\frac{C}{\text{some people who breathe alu out of their nostrils, speak alu with their mouth, look alu with their eyes" (Danda, p.122)}$

IGBO: $\frac{P}{\text{Amà}}$ $\frac{S}{\text{m}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{ùfọdu ndị jì imī ha ekuru alū, wèrè ọnū ha kwuru alū, à hụkwa alū n'anya hā}}$

EE: $\frac{S}{I}$ $\frac{P}{know}$ $\frac{C}{\text{some people who breathe evil, speak evil and look evil.}}$

The complement is an embedded structure containing three clauses which can be analyzed as follows:

<u>S</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>	<u>A</u>
who	breathe	alū	out of their nostrils ...

<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>	<u>A</u>
speak	alū	with their mouths

<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>	<u>A</u>
look	alū	with their eyes

The above structure can be said to have been influenced by the Igbo equivalent.

<u>S</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>
ndi	ji	imī ha	ekuru	alū

<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>
were	onū ha	kwuru	alū

<u>S</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>	<u>A</u>
a	hukwa	alū	n'anya ha

The English English equivalent is:

<u>S</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>
who	breathe	evil

<u>P</u>	<u>C</u>
think	evil

P
look C
evil

Other instances of colloquial utterances are:

(b) IE: S P C A
"You have refused to hear with your ears
(TOS, p.126)

IGBO: S P C P C
! jūnā ijí ntì gị ànụ ihē

EE: S P C
You have refused to hear

(c) IE: P A P C A
Go home straight and think yourself to death
(TOS, p.124)

IGBO: P C P C A
Làa ụlọ chégbuō onwe gị n'echiche

EE: P C P A
Go home and die of sorrow

(d) IE: S P C
"I am two bodies" (TOS, p.131)

IGBO: P C
Adì m̀ àhụ àbụọ
S

EE: S P C
 I am pregnant

26(a) is a complex sentence whose embedded structure consists of three clauses with the structures, SPCA, PCA and PCA for the I.E., SPCPC, PCPC and SPCA for Igbo, and SPC, PC, and PC for E.E. The colloquialism and hence interference is evident in the units realizing the predicate and adjunct in (a). There is also an informal repetition in the use of the lexical items breathe (verb) and nostril (noun); speak (vb) and mouth (noun); and look (vb) eyes (noun).

In the same manner, example (b) is a simple sentence with the structure SPCA for I.E., SPCPC for Igbo and SPC for E.E. The interference here lies in the units realizing the complement and adjunct. There is also an informal repetition of the use of ~~the~~ lexical items hear (vb) and ears (noun).

(c) is an imperative utterance because of the presence of the verb "go" at the initial position. It is made up of two clauses. The first clause consists of the structure PA while the second consists of the structure PCA for I.E. The Igbo version has the structures PC and PCA, while the structure of the E.E. is PC and PA. The verbal item think is used transitively in the IE, thereby deriving its influence from its Igbo equivalent.

(d) is a simple declarative statement with the structure SPC for all the versions. The interference here lies in the use of the Igbo copula verb di and its I.E. equivalent am, and the complement ahu abuo which is also a direct translation of two bodies as used in I.E.

Sentences (a), (b) and (d) are declarative constructions and relate more to the ideational than the other components of grammar. (c) on the other hand, is an imperative construction and it is more closely related to the interpersonal than the other components of grammar.

However, all the colloquial utterances are contextually meaningful and their understanding depends on the proper placement of such utterances in specific contexts.

5.3 DE-PERSONALIZED UTTERANCES

The device whereby a speaker mentions his personal name instead of using the first person pronoun to refer to himself is made prominent in TOS. He mentions his name or in some cases uses a third person pronoun as if he is referring to someone else. Examples include:

		<u>S</u>		<u>P</u>		<u>C</u>
27 (a)	I.E.	Your brother Oji		knows		nothing

A
about it (TOS, p.21)

IGBO: S P C
Ọjì nwan̄nē gị amághị́ ihé ọ́ bulà

A
gbasara yā

E.E: S P C A
I don't know anything about it

(b) I.E: S P A
The way you women behave at times

P C
Surprises Ọjì (TOS, p. 21)

IGBO: S P
Etu ụ́nụ́ bụ́ ụ́mụ́ nwanyị́ sí' eme

A P C A
ogē ụ́fọ́dụ́ nà-atù Ọjì́ n' anya

E.E: S P
The way you women behave

A P C
at times surprises me

(c) I.E: $\frac{P}{\text{Let}}$ $\frac{S}{\text{Chiàkà}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{rest}}$ (TOS, p. 23)

IGBO: $\frac{P}{\text{Kwèrè}}$ $\frac{S}{\text{Chiàkù}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{Zùru}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{ikē}}$

E.E: $\frac{P}{\text{Don't bother}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{me}}$

(d) I.E: $\frac{C}{\text{What they find in this place}}$ $\frac{S}{\text{Ejimadu's son}}$

$\frac{P}{\text{does not know}}$ (p. 100)

IGBO: $\frac{C}{\text{Ihe ha hùrù ebe à}}$ $\frac{S}{\text{nwa Èjìmadù}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{amaghì}}$

E.E: $\frac{S}{\text{I}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{don't know}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{what they find in this place}}$

(e) I.E: $\frac{P}{\text{Don't ask}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{your sister}}$ (p. 144)

IGBO: $\frac{S}{\text{A}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{jūnā}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{nwannē gī nwanyì}}$

E.E: $\frac{P}{\text{Don't ask}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{me}}$

In all the examples above, we witness Igbo influence in that we have utterances where a speaker is presented as neither the subject of the sentence nor the complement of the verb in the referring expression. Instead, the speakers present themselves in ways that suggest they are passing comments on other people by using proper nouns instead of the first person pronoun (singular). ~~Tanade (1989)~~ calls this practice "de-personalized referring expressions".

In 27 (a), in a reply to a question which Chiaku asked Oji, instead of using the pronoun 'I' in a subject position, he uses his real name Oji. In a debate over the possibility of Oji in providing wine for a particular ceremony involving Chiaku, he uses his name, Oji to replace the pronoun me in a complement position (to express his surprise), as in (b) above.

Apparently disenchanted with Oji in an argument, Chiaku replied him "I accept whatever you say. Let Chiaku rest". So, Chiaku replaces me in a subject position in (c) above. In (d), Ejimadu's son replaces I in a subject position. Here, Oji is expressing his surprise as to why many people are rushing to fellowship with the white men in their church. The name of his father is Ejimadu, and so he chooses to refer to himself as Ejimadu's son in the statement.

In (e), a fiercely bleating goat has angered Chiakụ. So, when a sympathizing Ego's mother tries to find out from Chiakụ the goat's problem, all that Chiakụ could reply is "Don't ask your sister" instead of Don't ask me. Your sister here replaces me in a complement position.

This device reflects the peculiar speech habits of the Igbo speakers. Any attempt at interpreting their structures in isolation of their contexts will lead to misinterpretation of meaning. The structures of the utterances above when interpreted within proper contexts constitute IE structures.

Although sentences 27 (a), (b) and (d) are declarative constructions and (c) and (e) are imperative constructions, it is the interpersonal function that is emphasized in all the sentences. This is because all the constructions are made in response to earlier remarks in a conversation. A conversation usually involves, at least, two people.

5.4 TEMPORAL ADVERBS

Temporal adverbs are used as adverbial elements of time. English uses temporal adverbs such as now, then, a few minutes ago, today, yesterday, tomorrow, last night, two d̄ s ago, two weeks after, last month, last two years, a few months ago, etc.

Similarly, Igbo uses such temporal adverbs as ugbu a (now), mgbe ahu (then), nkeji ole na ole gara aga (a few minutes ago), taa (today), echi (tomorrow), uyaahu (yesterday), abali uyaahu (last night), ubochi abuo gara aga (two days ago), izu uka abuo gara aga (two weeks ago), onwa gara aga (last month), afo abuo gara aga (last two years). In addition, Igbo makes a distinction between the seven-day week known as izu uka (literally meaning "Sunday Week") and a four-day week known as izu ahia ("market week") Igbo also uses market days such as nkwo, oye, afo, and eke; and the appearance of the moon otherwise known as "Onwa" as the equivalent of month. So, temporal adverbs mostly used in these novels are translations of Igbo temporal adverb system which has resulted in a combination of Igbo nominal items with English particles or IE structures.

28 (a) I.E: "It took him two market weeks to recover completely"
(Danda, p. 109).

IGBO: O were ya izu ahia abuo tupu oria adichaa ya ma.

E.E: It took him two weeks to recover completely.

(b) I.E: "I think, though, Okaka is a few moons younger"
(TOS, p. 45).

IGBO: O jiri onwa ole na ole tota Okaka

E.E: I think, though, Okaka is a few months younger.

- (c) I.E: "The day was nkwo ..." (TOS, p. 145)
 IGBO: Ubochi ahụ bu nkwo.
 E.E: The day was "Tuesday"
- (d) I.E: "... who came from Onitsha every afo market day." (TFS, p. 18)
 IGBO: Ndị si Onitsha abia ahia afo o bula .
 E.E: Those that came from Onitsha weekly
- (e) I.E: "The five of them were doing very well ... would probably produce within four moons or five" (TOS, 79)
 IGBO: Ha anọ na-eme ofuma ... ha nwekwara ike imụ nwa n' ime onwa ano ma o bu ise.
 E.E: The five of them were doing very well and would probably give birth within four or five months.
- (f) I.E: "I had, in fact, been expecting it in you for a few moons now ..." (TOS, 97).
 IGBO: N' ikwū eziokwū, anà m̀ atubukwa anyā yā kemgbe onwa ole nà ole ugbu a
 E.E: I had, in fact, been expecting it for a few months now

The structure of the temporal adverbs can be analyzed as follows:

- (a) I.E: $\frac{(m)}{\text{two}}$ $\frac{(m)}{\text{market}}$ $\frac{\text{head}}{\text{weeks}}$

IGBO: $\frac{h}{Izù}$ $\frac{(m)}{ahia}$ $\frac{(m)}{àbuò}$

E.E: $\frac{(m)}{two}$ $\frac{h}{weeks}$

(b) I.E: $\frac{(m)}{a\text{ few}}$ $\frac{(m)}{moons}$

IGBO: $\frac{h}{Ọnwa}$ $\frac{(m)}{ole\ nà\ òle}$

E.E: $\frac{(m)}{a\text{ few}}$ $\frac{(m)}{months}$

(c) I.E: $\frac{S}{The\ day}$ $\frac{P}{was}$ $\frac{C}{nkwo}$

IGBO: $\frac{S}{Ụbòchì\ ahù}$ $\frac{P}{bù}$ $\frac{C}{̀nkwo}$

E.E: $\frac{S}{The\ day}$ $\frac{P}{was}$ $\frac{C}{"Tuesday"}$

(d) I.E: $\frac{(m)}{afò}$ $\frac{(m)}{market}$ $\frac{h}{day}$

IGBO: $\frac{h}{Ụbòchì}$ $\frac{(m)}{ahia}$ $\frac{(m)}{àfò}$

E.E: $\frac{(m)}{Monday's}$ $\frac{h}{market}$

(e) I.E: $\frac{(m)}{\text{four}}$ $\frac{h}{\text{moons}}$

IGBO: $\frac{h}{\text{onwa}}$ $\frac{(m)}{\text{ano}}$

E.E: $\frac{(m)}{\text{four}}$ $\frac{h}{\text{months}}$

(f) I.E: $\frac{(m)}{\text{a few}}$ $\frac{h}{\text{moons}}$ $\frac{(q)}{\text{now}}$

IGBO: $\frac{h}{\text{onwa}}$ $\frac{(m)}{\text{ole na ole}}$ $\frac{(q)}{\text{ugbu a}}$

E.E: $\frac{(m)}{\text{a few}}$ $\frac{h}{\text{months}}$ $\frac{(q)}{\text{now}}$

The interference in (a) lies in the items constituting the modifier-ahia abuo which has been translated to mean two markets. Igbo uses two market weeks where English uses two weeks. The item constituting the head word in (b) causes interference in that onwa which means moon occupies the position of the head instead of the E.E. month. Nkwo which has been used as a complement in (c) and afo which has been used as a modifier in (d) are adopted in I.E. as direct lexical transfer. (e) and (f) have the same pattern of interference as (b).

5.5 THE STRUCTURE OF THE MIXED ITEMS

In all the novels in question, Igbo nominal elements are freely used in English sentences. An examination of their functions in the sentences shows that they are used as head, modifier or both. They are used as subjects or complements of the sentences, as possessives and as adjuncts. Examples include:

5.5.1 IGBO ITEMS USED AS HEAD NOUNS IN SUBJECT POSITION

29 (a) "My Ikenga was blind the day Danda was born" (Danda, p.28)

(b) "One's chi brings one so much trouble" (Danda, 26).

In the nominal groups,

$\frac{(m)}{\text{My}}$	$\frac{h}{\text{Ikengà}}$
-------------------------	---------------------------

$\frac{(m)}{\text{one's}}$	$\frac{h}{\text{chi}}$
----------------------------	------------------------

Igbo lexical items are used as head nouns while the English items modify the head words in the subject positions

5.5.2 IGBO ITEMS USED AS HEAD NOUNS IN SUBJECT POSITION (PLURAL)

- (c) "The other ozos had arranged themselves on both sides of the table in places where they would expect to see and be seen" (Danda, 22).

In the nominal structure:

$\frac{(m)}{\text{The}}$	$\frac{(m)}{\text{other}}$	$\frac{h}{\text{ozos}}$
--------------------------	----------------------------	-------------------------

The Igbo item which is the head word has an English plural morpheme.

5.5.3 IGBO ITEMS USED AS BOTH MODIFIER AND HEAD IN A SUBJECT NOMINAL GROUP

- (d) "The Agbogho Mmonwu did not dance but merely walked the ebe spraying the crowd with maize ears for fertility" (Danda, p.18).

$\frac{(m)}{\text{The}}$	$\frac{(m)}{\text{Agbogho}}$	$\frac{h}{\text{mmonwu}}$
--------------------------	------------------------------	---------------------------

5.5.4 IGBO ITEMS USED AS COMPLEMENTS

- (e) $\frac{S}{\text{"That}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{is}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{my ogu...}}$ (TOS, p. 99)

- (f) $\frac{S}{\text{"The white man}}$ $\frac{P}{\text{has eaten}}$ $\frac{C}{\text{the amosu}}$ (Danda, p.80).

- (d) "His only offence then, as now, was that he advised his sister to accept a suitor and leave Nnanna to the care of his chi"
(TOS)

The phrases or groups constituting the adjuncts can be analyzed as follows:

- | | | | | | |
|-----|----------------------------|----------------------|----------------------|---------------------|------------------|
| (a) | <u>Preposition</u>
on | <u>(q)</u>
coming | <u>(m)</u>
oye | <u>h</u>
day | |
| (b) | <u>Preposition</u>
up | <u>(Det)</u>
the | <u>(m)</u>
sacred | <u>(m)</u>
umune | <u>h</u>
leaf |
| (c) | <u>Preposition</u>
with | <u>(Det)</u>
my | <u>h</u>
ogene | | |
| (d) | <u>Preposition</u>
of | <u>(Det)</u>
his | <u>h</u>
chi | | |

In 30 (a) and (b), Igbo items occur as modifiers while in (c) and (d), they occur as heads in adjunct positions.

5.5.7 IGBO ITEMS USED AS COMPLEMENTS IN POSSESSIVE CONSTRUCTIONS

- 31 (a) "They looked at each other, and then around the small open hall which was the old one's obi" (B.W., p. 61)

- (b) "Obieke sat all alone in his Obi, the small roomless hut in front which he had inherited from his father along with the compound itself" (B.W., p. 95)
- (c) "Obieke's obi was about the least impressive in the extended family of thirty or more sub-families, all descendants of Udemezue of burning eyes" (B.W., p. 95)

The underlined nominal groups- one's obi, his obi and Obieke's obi- exemplify the use of mixed items in possessive constructions. In 31 (a), (b) and (c), the Igbo elements function as complement in possessive constructions. Language mixing, therefore, is a major source of creating IE structures.

5.6 THE IGBO NARRATIVE DEVICES

Igbo narrative devices include proverbs, idioms and imagery. They are adopted in speeches or narratives in order to convey specialised kinds of information. These devices express specific meanings which derive from the socio-cultural contexts of the speech community. Their meanings can be interpreted on two levels - the literal and the metaphorical (Ugwu, 1990). The literal meaning is deduced from a combination of word meaning and sentence. The metaphorical meaning, on the other hand, is derived from a

consideration of some extra - linguistic factors such as pre-suppositions, socio-cultural contexts and attitude of speakers which may influence the overall meaning of the utterance.

The proper interpretation of their meanings relates to Halliday's functional model of language use. According to Halliday (1973), the situation in which an utterance is made affects the final form of the utterance in terms of its content and grammatical structure. Halliday states further that the meanings that a particular utterance wishes to convey must first of all receive an input from the situation in which it is performed. It is on the basis of this observation that we consider the structures of Igbo proverbs, idioms and imagery used in the prose texts as IE structures.

The literal meanings of utterances essentially rely on the transitivity system which operates in them.

5.7 TRANSITIVITY

Transitivity has been identified as a grammatical component of the ideational function of language (Halliday, 1973:39). Halliday also defines transitivity as "the interpretation and expression of the different types of process of the external world including material, mental and abstract processes of every kind" (p.39). Transitivity

here deals mainly with action or state of the verbal group of an utterance.

In traditional English grammar, transitivity is regarded as a verbal feature. Here, verbs are usually classified into two major categories - transitive and intransitive verbs. A verb is said to be transitive in any utterance, if it takes an object. Example:

	S	P	C
(32)	Ike	sells	oranges

On the other hand, a verb is intransitive whenever the verb does not take an object. Example:

	S	P	A
(33)	Ada	ran	away

The complement in (32) represents the object (oranges) while the complement is completely absent in (33).

But transitivity in a modern systemic grammar is regarded as a feature of the clause and not just of the verbal group. This is because transitivity is determined by the presence or absence of a complement. To this extent, sentence (32) above with the structure SPC is transitive while sentence (33) with the structure SPA is intransitive. Transitivity is, therefore, viewed as a system that shows the behaviour of verbal groups as well as the way clausal

elements of subjects, predicate, complements and adjuncts relate to each other.

Transitivity choices are choices between different processes, different participants and different circumstances. For instance, in the English grammar, choices are made between different types of process, between different types of participants, between different types of circumstance, between different roles for participants and circumstances, between different ways of combining processes, participants and circumstances (Berry, 1977). There is a choice between three main types of process: a physical or material process; a mental process; and a relational process.

In English (as in many other languages), the unit clause acts as entry condition to the transitivity systems. Each clause chooses between a number of different types of process. For example, each clause chooses between material process as in:

34 (a) Uche bought a book

Mental process as in:

(b) Ike likes Ngozi

and relational process as in:

(c) Chike is a doctor

We will now investigate ~~the manifestation of the transitivity system~~
in proverbs, riddles and imagery.

5.7.1 THE TRANSITIVITY SYSTEM OF PROVERBS

A number of statements have been identified in these novels as proverbs. The Igbo refer to proverbs as "the palmoil with which words are eaten". "Talking in proverbs," according to Emenyonu (1978:157) "enables the speaker to display his wit, wisdom, and his distinctive ability to manipulate the language". Proverbs are living vehicles of situational statements (Nwoga, 1975:197), and are commonly employed in Igbo narratives and dialogues.

The examples below illustrate how IE structures have been created in the novels through translation. We will analyze the transitivity choices of the proverbs.

35 (a) I.E: "Like a chicken transported to a strange environment, you should stand on one leg till you are sure of your ground" (T.F.S., p. 9)

IGBO: Dị kà òkụkọ̀ bīārā ọhụrū, ì gà-èjì otù ụkwū wèrè kwurū tupu ì matachaa àlà.

E.E: As a new comer, you should be careful.

(b) I.E: "There is a proverb which says that chicken can never forget the person who plucks the feathers of its tail during the rainy season" - (T.F.S., p. 21).

IGBO: A nà-àtụ ilū sị nà ọkụkọ a nāghī echefu onye fōrō yā ọdụ n' ụdu mmīrī.

E.E: You should not forget someone who assisted you in times of difficulty.

- (c) I.E: "Our people say that the bulge of pregnancy cannot be concealed for long" (TOS, p. 85).

IGBO: Ndị be ānyī sị nà àdighī ekpuchi afọ imē ākā

E.E: The truth cannot be concealed for too long.

- (d) I.E: "Our people say that nobody is another's chi" (TOS, p. 112).

IGBO: Ndị be ānyī nà-àsi nà ọ dighī onye bụ chi ibè ya.

E.E: Everybody has a different destiny.

- (e) I.E: "Where the runner reaches, there the walker will reach eventually" (Danda, p. 42).

IGBO: Ebe ọgba ọsọ gbarurù kà ọje ìje gà-èru.

E.E: The end justifies the means.

- (f) I.E: "... that which is in the pot should be in the belly" (Danda, p. 123).

IGBO: Kamà ọ gà-àdọ n' ìtè kà ọ dọrọ n' afọ

E.E: It is better to eat all the food available than to spare it.

- (g) I.E: "It is those whose legs go to the river that the river can drown" (TPW, p. 70)
 IGBO: Ndi mmirī hùrù ụkwụ hā nsō kà ọ nà-èri.
 E.E: Familiarity breeds contempt.
- (h) I.E: "The man who is murdered by his kinsmen does not bleed" (TPW, p. 81).
 IGBO: Onye nwannē yā gbùrù adīghī àgba òbàrà.
 E.E: One does not take action against oneself.
- (i) I.E: "The bread fruit which chooses to fall on the day of festivity has not fallen early enough" (TPW, p. 146).
 IGBO: Ụkwā dārā ụbòchì emume adàghì n' ogè.
 E.E: It is always good to do something in good time.

The above proverbs are all contextually relevant traditional Igbo proverbs. Though they have been rendered into English, they retain the vivid imagery and culture of the Igbo language which make them IE. We shall now undertake an analysis of transitivity choices in the IE variety of the proverbs.

Proverb No	Type of Process	Process itself
36. a	Material process	should stand
b	Mental process	can never forget
c	Mental process	cannot be concealed
d	Relational process	is
e	Material process	will reach
f	Relational process	should be
g	Relational process	is
h	Material process	does not bleed
i	Material process	has not fallen

What is the grammatical marker of each process? Material process relates to the process of doing or happening e.g. jump, play, run, resign, faint, go, break, etc. Mental process relates to the process of feeling, thinking and perceiving e.g. like, know, notice, forget, fear, see, hear, etc. Relational process relates to attribute or identity e.g. is, are, was, were, seem, etc.

The processes - stand in 36 (a), reach in (e), bleed in (h) and fallen in (i) are all grammatical markers of material process. Similarly, forget in (b) and conceal in (c) are markers of mental process while is in (d) and (g) and be in (f) mark relational process.

All the proverbs above are declarative sentences. They are more closely related to the ideational function than either the interpersonal or textual function. So, the function of these proverbs reflects their grammatical structure.

5.7.2 PROVERBS WITH RHETORICAL QUESTIONS

Generally, interrogative sentences are made in anticipation of immediate responses. To that extent, they perform interpersonal function. However, rhetorical questions are employed as a speech device aimed at impressing the audience or to achieve some effect. No answers are expected. As a result, they cannot be said to be interrogative sentences. Hence the ideational-function is emphasized more than their interpersonal function. Consider the following proverbs:

37. (a) I.E: "Does one need to tell a deaf man that war has broken?" (Danda, p. 15)

IGBO: À nà-àgwa òchi ntị nà agha ēsūlā?

E.E: One does not need to be told of the reality of an impending danger.

(b) I.E: "Was it not the bed bug who asked its children to be patient because what is hot will eventually be cold?" (TFS, p. 56).

IGBO: Ọ̀ bụ̀kwà àkpị̀rị̀ gwàrà ụ̀mụ̀ ya nwèe ndidi màkà
nà ihe dī̀ ọ̀kū̀ gà-èmechā̀ juo oyī̀?.

E.E: With patience, one can survive all difficult times.

(c) I.E: "Why lick your fingers in a hurry, are you going
to hang them in the ceiling?" (TFS, p. 56).

IGBO: Ị̀ nà-àgbà ọ̀sọ̀ aracha mkpị̀sị̀ akā̀ ị̀ gà-afanye yā̀
n' ụ̀ko?

E.E: Why rushing over what belongs to you?

(d) I.E: "A bird that gives off twenty droppings while
still in the air, how many will it give off when
it lands on its two feet?" (TFS, p. 73)

IGBO: Nnụ̀nụ̀ ebēghī̀ ēbē nyuọ̀ ọ̀gụ̀ àkpālā̀, ọ̀ gà-ànyuzi
ōlḕ mgbè̀ o betuò ebetuò?

E.E: If one starts showing signs of bad behaviour
when one has not fully been accepted, what
happens after the person has been fully accepted?

(e) I.E: "Whoever tells a grown up man to come out of
the sun?" (TFS, p. 73)

IGBO: À̀ nà - àgwa okènyè̀ pùta n' anwū̀?

E.E: You don't remind an adult of what hurts him.

- (f) I.E: "Is it that the razor is not sharp or that Mgbekē does not know how to share with it"? (TFS, p.95)
- IGBO: Ọ̀ bù nà agùma adìghì ñkọ̀ kà ọ̀ bù nà Mgbekē amāghì ētū esì akpụ isì?
- E.E: What could likely be the cause of the problem?
- (g) I.E: "Had he, like the doomed dog lost the sense of smell? (TFS, p. 163)
- IGBO: Ọ̀ juna inū isì nsì dī kà mgbè nkītā gá-anwụ?
- E.E: Whatever is destined to happen cannot be prevented.

Let us now describe the transitivity choices made in the IE variety of the rhetorical proverbs listed above.

Proverb No	Type of Process	Process itself
38 a	Material process	has broken
b	Relational process	was/will eventually be
c	Material process	Lick
d	Material process	give
e	Material process	tells
f	Relational process	is
	Mental process	does not know
g	Material process	lost

The processes - broken in 43 (a), lick in (c), give in (d), tells in (e) and lost in (g) are the grammatical markers of material process. In the same manner, was and be in (b) and is in (f) are markers of relational process while known in (f) marks mental process.

As we have stated earlier, although the mood of the clauses of the rhetorical proverbs is interrogative, they do not require answers. They perform ideational functions. A study of the proverbs given in (37) and (38) shows that Igbo proverbs portray various aspects of Igbo values and attitudes which emanate from the Igbo world view and culture. By reflecting Igbo culture and environment, Igbo proverbs contribute to the process of Igbonizing Nigerian English in Igbo English prose fiction.

We have also seen that the Igbo social context which has influenced the meaning of the proverbs reflects the internal structure of the utterances. Although these proverbs are rendered into IE through translation, the constructions are grammatically correct. They are also different from typical standard English forms.

5.7.3 TRANSITIVITY SYSTEM OF IMAGERY

The authors have drawn images (through metaphors, similes, etc.) from the indigenous cultures of the Igbo and have incorporated them into English also through translation. Some of the images identified in the novels include:

- 39 (a) I.E: "You have come like a man" (Danda, p. 123).
 IGBO: ! bīānā kà nwokē
 E.E: You have exhibited an act of bravery
- (b) I.E: "Now you pant like a lizard that has just dropped from a high wall" (TOS, p. 29).
 IGBO: ! nà-ekù rahij kà ñgwere siri n' elū dà.
 E.E: You are breathing very profusely.
- (c) I.E: Women are fire coals which a man open-eyedly heaps on his head" (Danda, p. 132).
 IGBO: Ụmụ nwaànyị bụ ntụ ñkè nwokē mèghèèrè anya kposa n' isi yā.
 E.E: Women are an, unavoidable, evil.
- (d) I.E: "Tell us, strong one, the dried meat that fills the mouth" (Danda, p. 116)
 IGBO: Kòrọ anyị dikē, anụ kpōrō ñkū na-eju ọnū.
 E.E: You, though small but a mighty or , tell us.

- (e) I.E: "I am two bodies" (TOS, p. 172).
 IGBO: Adì m` ahụ` abụō
 E.E: I am pregnant.
- (f) I.E: "This is a bad wind which has come into our land"
 (TOS, p. 120).
 IGBO: Ihe à bụ` ikuku ọjọō kubatara n' ala ānyī.
 E.E: This is a bad omen for our town.

We will here (just as we have done in the analysis of proverbs) examine the transitivity options of the IE structures of the above listed images.

Proverb No.	Types of Process	Process itself
40 a	Material process	have come
b	Material process	pant
c	Relational process	are
d	Material process	tell
e	Relational process	am
f	Relational process	is

The grammatical markers of the material process in (45) are come in (a), paint in (b) and tell in (d) while are, am and is mark relational process in (c), (e) and (f), respectively.

The three macro-functions of language-ideational, interpersonal and textual-seem to be represented adequately in the structure of the images above. Sentences (a), (b), (c), (e), and (f) are declarative constructions. Although (d) is without a question, one will still observe that a response akin to what we have in interrogative constructions is expected. It, however, appears that their structures are more textual than both ideational and interpersonal. This is because the sentences are comparative in nature and as a result employ the use of anaphoric and personal pronouns which mark references.

The presence of the comparative item like and the anaphoric pronoun you in 40 (a) and (b) illustrates the textual functions of the two sentences. Though there is no comparative item in (c), the structure is, however, comparative. In addition, the presence of his which refers to man is textual.

Strong one is in apposition to the dried meat that fills the mouth thereby illustrating its textual aspects in (d). The comparative nature of (e) and the presence of the pronoun this in (f) truly exemplify textual aspects.

It can, therefore, be stated that the dominantly textual functions contained in the images above are reflected in their structures.

5.8 THE STRUCTURE OF RIDDLES

In Igbo society, riddles are mainly used for entertainment, especially by children. According to Finnegan (1970), the African riddles are in the form of statements which involve an analogy of meaning, sound, rhythm and tone. The answer to a riddle involves the identification of the object of the riddle by abstracting it from the metaphysical or poetic content of the initial question.

Of the three authors under consideration, only Chukwuemeka Ike has translated Igbo riddles into English. From TPW (p. 145), we have the following riddles and their answers.

- 41 (a) I.E: (Question): "Riddle expert, tell me what sounds kporotokpoto on a wealthy man's pear tree?". (p. 145)
- (Answer): "The rope for tethering a cow".
- IGBO: (Question): Gwa m gwà ì gwa m, gwa m̄
 ̄the na- ebe kporotokpoto n'ùbe
 ògàrànyà?
- (Answer): Ogbu ejirì kedo ehī
- E.E: (Question): Could you tell me what makes that big noise on the wealthy man's pear tree?
- (Answer): The rope used for tethering a cow.
- (b) I.E: (Question): "Riddle expert, tell me what dog was seen running down Eke Ngodo? (p. 145).
- (Answer): "A ball of foofoo travelling down your gullet".
- IGBO: (Question): Gwa m gwà ì gwa m, gwa m̄ nkītā
 a hūrù kà ọ nà- àgbadā Eke Ngōdō?
- (Answer): Otū Okpoko ụtàr? na-agbada n'
 àkpirī.

E.E: (Question): Could you tell me what travels to the stomach through the gullet?

(Answer): A ball of pounded cassava going down through the gullet.

(c) I.E: (Question): "Riddle expert, tell me what is it that God fills with water in the sky?" (p. 145).

(Answer): The coconut

IGBO: (Question): Gwa m gwà ì gwa m, gwa ì mmiri
Chukwu d'òwàrà n'elū?

(Answer): Akị b'èkēē.

E.E: (Question): Could you tell me the fruit of which tree has a large quantity of water in it?

(Answer): The coconut.

(d) I.E: (Question): "Riddle expert, tell me what can climb an iroko tree without any contrivance?"

(Answer): A snake. (p. 145).

IGBO: (Question): Gwa m gwà ì gwa m, gwa ì ihe
gba aka àrì òjì?

(Answer): Agwọ.

E.E: (Question): Could you tell me what climbs a big tree without any contrivance?

(Answer): A snake.

These riddles are self-explanatory, and an insight into the correct answer can be gleaned from the culture and physical environment of the Igbo speech community.

They are all interrogative statements. In other words, they involve the performer who asks the questions, and the audience or listener that provides the answers. To this extent, the riddles essentially perform interpersonal functions. Therefore, the function of the riddles reflects their structures.

So far in this section of chapter five, we have been able to use the systemic functional grammar to analyze the IE structures of speech functions, colloquial utterances, temporal adverbs, de-personalized utterances, the structure of codemixing, proverbs, imagery and riddles. Apart from illustrating the structures of IE in the prose texts, these Igbo speech habits also contribute to Igbonizing Nigerian English.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION

6.0 INTRODUCTION

We have so far treated style as the choice of language use. This means that style connotes the choice which the author must exercise among the phonological, lexical and grammatical possibilities that the language affords him. The writer's text can best be described in terms of those choices.

As we have noted earlier, the Igbo writer uses English as a second language. In any second language situation, interference is bound to take place. The direction of interference is usually that the mother tongue which the language user has acquired (in the early stages of his life) interferes with the second language which he has learnt to use. The result of this kind of interference is the emergence of a variety which incorporates the linguistic habits of the first language into the second language.

The kind of interference that is described in this work can easily be observed from the identification of Igbo elements in English structures. Patterns of identification regularly relate to transference, translation and transliteration.

We have, therefore, found that the attempt by the authors to transfer, transliterate or translate Igbo speech habits has caused interference in their use of English. This interference which is here

a stylistic device of the authors has resulted in Igbo English. IE is a variety of NE with Igbo influence. So, the English or style of the authors - Chukwuemeka Ike, Nkem Nwankwo and John Munonye - as demonstrated in their novels, can be termed IE. It is therefore, a study of the dialectal variety of NE through the prose texts.

The use of contrastive analysis through translation has enabled us to compare the syntax and lexico-semantics of Igbo and English with a view to identifying the nature of interference. Viewed from this perspective, the study of style can be said to be a study of distinctions - looking at what is said against what might have been said (Haynes, 1989:9). When we relate this to our study, we find that "what was said" is represented by IE and "what might have been said" is represented by EE. The Igbo version as represented in our analysis helps to show the direct sources of interference since it is essentially a work on the Igbo influence on English.

We have also found that both English and Igbo mutually influence each other. The English influence on Igbo is manifest in the way the educated Igbo mix their mother tongue with English. It is common to hear such usages as:

- 42 (a) This life di egwu (This life is wonderful)
 (b) O di kwa risky (It is risky)

- (c) I di sure? (Are you sure?)
 (d) Sorry, biko (Sorry please)

Other influences on Igbo include: the presence of English loan-words or loan translation such as foto (photo), windo (window), kop (cup), etc.; the existence of non-Igbo sound patterns such as the presence of such spellings as Onitsha, Nsukka, Orlu, Awka, etc; and the adoption of consonant clusters in place of the insertion of epenthetic vowels in such words as sweta (sweater), dosta (duster), etc. However, we have in this study, concentrated on the Igbo influence on English and found that this influence has resulted in IE at the lexico-semantic and syntactic levels of linguistic description.

6.1.1 LEXICO-SEMANTIC LEVEL

At this level, we identified transfer (including mixed transfer and literal transfer), semantic extension of certain lexical items, borrowings and neologisms as some of the processes of creating IE lexical items and meanings. We found that these features have also contributed to igbonizing NE at the lexico-semantic level. Examples of the use of mixed transfer or mixed formation in creating IE lexical items include ozō title (Danda, p.7), okwe tree (TPW, p.29), oye day (TOS, p.102), ogbono soup (TFS, p.97), etc. There is the semantic extension of the verb know in M.M. p.137) where to know book in IE means to be educated.

6.1.2 SYNTACTIC LEVEL

Here, we have identified certain Igbo speech habits such as Igbo speech functions, colloquial utterances, de-personalized utterances, temporal adverbs, language mixing, proverbs, riddles and imagery as some of the sources of IE syntax which have also contributed towards igbonizing NE at the level of syntax. Some of the examples of IE structure include:

	S		P		C
43	(a)	"The white man	has eaten	<u>the amosu"</u>	(<u>Danda</u> ,
		p.80).			

- (b) "Obieke's obj was about the least impressive in the extended family of thirty or more sub-families, all descendants of Udemezue of Burning eyes" (B.W, p.95).

- (c) $\begin{array}{c} \text{P} \\ \hline \end{array}$ "Go $\begin{array}{c} \text{A} \\ \hline \end{array}$ home straight and $\begin{array}{c} \text{P} \\ \hline \end{array}$ think $\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ \hline \end{array}$ yourself $\begin{array}{c} \text{A} \\ \hline \end{array}$ to death"
(TOS, p.124).

In 43 (a), Igbo item amosu is used in the complement position while the Igbo element obi functions as complement in a possessive construction. In (c), the verbal item think is used transitively in the IE structure thereby deriving its influence from Igbo. The verb think is used intransitively in EE.

So, this study has identified two major dialectal varieties of English used in Nigeria. They are: the national variety of Nigerian English (NE) and the ethnic variety exemplified here with Igbo English (IE). NE is perceived here as a variety of English which is used in Nigeria as distinct from those varieties of English used in Britain, USA, India, Australia, Ghana, Canada, etc. Standard Nigerian English is characterised by three important features - nativization (linguistic, pragmatic and creative), the influence of Americanisms and the influence of Biblical language. This has been discussed in detail in Chapter two.

On the other hand, IE which is one of the ethnic dialects of NE is distinguished essentially by 'igbonization' or Igbo influence. There are three aspects of igbonization—phonological, lexico-semantics and syntactic. Phonological igbonization is achieved by such phonological processes as vowel harmony, consonant elision, epenthesis, Igbo-induced syllable structure, vowel reduplication, and sound substitution. Lexico-semantic igbonization is created by such processes as transfer, semantic extension of words, lexical borrowings and neologisms. Syntactic igbonization is achieved by the process of translating Igbo speech functions, colloquial utterances, de-personalized utterances, temporal adverbs, proverbs, riddles and imagery into English. It is also achieved through language mixing. All the processes of igbonization listed above have been discussed extensively in chapters four and five.

The IE expressions used by the novelists are found to have obeyed the rules of English grammar. Any ungrammatical usage in the English of the writers which is not a stylistic device should be treated as a grammatical error and not as a feature of IE.

Igbo language has been found to be the source of IE pronunciation, syntax and lexico-semantics. Since IE is a dialect of NE, Igbo can be said to have affected NE linguistically, pragmatically and creatively.

6.2 THE CODIFICATION OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH

There is no doubt that as we have British English, American English and Canadian English, we also have Nigerian English. Also like American and British English, NE has its own varieties which include dialectal variety such as Igbo English (here studied) and diatypic variants one of which is the Nigerian Army English studied by Amafa (1990).

A true picture of the developments of English in Nigeria has rightly been presented by Bamgbose (1993) in his observation that:

The English language has undergone modifications in the Nigerian environment. It has been pidginized, nativized, acculturated and twisted to express unaccustomed concepts and modes of interaction. As a result, it is now a Nigerian English at par with other world Englishes... The challenge we now face is to intensify research on this English and codify it appropriately.

The need for codification and the model for examining have been further stressed by Odumuh (1987), Kujore (1993) and were also extensively discussed at a conference in 1993 to mark the 50 years of the British Council in Nigeria.

There is a feeling that one way in which newly independent nations can assert their nationhood is through the use of English language in a way which is distinctly Nigerian, Ghanaian, Kenyan, etc. (Odumuh, 1987:4). It is by so doing that English will become

'indigenous' to the peoples of these countries and also serve as national languages for purposes of oneness.

But the task of establishing a standard Nigerian variety which will be distinct from British English is not an easy one. Kujore (1993:3) captures the attitude of scholars in this manner:

Generally and among scholars, attitudes to those varieties in particular, whose distinctive features are yet to be thoroughly investigated are both positive and negative, ranging from outright condemnation of the supposedly emerging standard through caution and scepticism, to enthusiastic acceptance. At one extreme are those who consider the departures from the model as a bastardization of the standard, and at the other extreme are those who welcome the departures as an enrichment of the model.

It has to be pointed out here, if only to dispel the fear of some people, that no standard is static. Substituting the Nigerian standard for the British standard will not lead to deterioration. It will instead lead to the improvement of the existing standards. English has proved that it is normal in its development that other standards should emerge. This was how American English, Canadian English, Australian English, and only recently Indian English became acceptable dialects of World Standard English.

What should be done now is to seriously look at the features which are peculiar to NE, especially the variety used among the

educated people (including students in tertiary institutions), and with these features begin to compile grammars, dictionaries and reference materials. The dictionaries should be organized under such areas as lexicon, borrowed words, proverbs, riddles, idioms, speech functions, colloquialisms and mixed formations.

6.2.1 THE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIAN ENGLISH

Literature depends primarily on language. There is also a close relationship between literature and cultural contexts. This means that the writer's relevance in developing, enriching, and popularizing the standard Nigerian English should be utilized.

It is a well-known fact that the vast knowledge of several other cultures helped William Shakespeare to contribute immensely towards enriching English. Nigerian writers' efforts in translating their multilingual and multicultural experiences into English should be commended. In the attempts to codify NE, reference should be made to the works of such Nigerian writers as Achebe, Soyinka, Nwankwo, Munonye, Osundare, Ike, Aluko, etc. The ethnic dialects of NE with which they write should not be thought of as creating problems of intelligibility because "there are standardizing factors that put pressure on most speakers to conform to this variety" (Bamgbose, 1993).

English and Nigerian languages (the writers' mother tongue) will continue to mutually influence one another positively as long as they continue to exist side by side.

Apart from popular Nigerian writers, the role of the print and electronic media in popularizing and enriching NE expressions (by constantly using them) should be utilized.

6.3 THE USEFULNESS OF THIS STUDY TO LANGUAGE POLICY FORMULATION

Although language planning is the concern of both monolingual and bilingual societies, it is of top priority for multilingual societies such as Nigeria. Planning is a conscious effort that is designed to take care of the language needs of both the present and the future. In other words, language planning requires positive efforts towards promoting language development.

Against the background that over 400 indigenous languages exist in Nigeria (Bamgbose, 1992), there should be a good language policy which in Adeniran's (1992) consideration, should serve the following objectives:

- (i) increased inter-ethnic communication leading to national integration through (a) common indigenous language (s);
- (ii) increased communication efficiency in our public institutions;

- (iii) increased and easy access to knowledge of varying degrees of technicality;
- (iv) equal access to information in the public system leading to opportunity to participate in the system; and
- (v) increased access to our indigenous literary arts, and opportunities to participate in, contribute to and propagate them.

Unfortunately, there does not exist any clear language policy for the nation. Government's efforts at having a national language policy is implied in two policy documents. The first is the language provisions for education in the National Policy on Education (N.P.E.). The other is the provision of language for the conduct of the business of the National Assembly in the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria also revised in 1989. Paragraph 1 (8) of the National Policy on Education of 1977 (later revised in 1981) provides for the learning by every Nigerian child of one of the three major Nigerian languages - Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo, in addition to the child's mother tongue. Similarly, clause 51 (1) of the 1979 constitution (revised in 1989) provides for the use of English as well as the three major Nigerian languages for the conduct of the business of the National Assembly "when adequate arrangements have been made therefor".

Summarizing the NPE, Bamgbose (1977) observes that the policy rests on two main planks with regard to language:

- (a) the issue of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction in early formal education; and
- (b) the requirement that every Nigerian child should learn one of the three major Nigerian languages in addition to his own language and English.

Commenting on the government's approach to language policy, Banjo (1992) states that the language provision in the NPE is "government's cautions and indirect approach to what is potentially an explosive national question with a hidden agenda". In Adeniran's (1992) view, since education is the intellectual catalyst of development, we could hold on to whatever proclamations are contained in the educational policy statement as government blueprint. This is the present attitude adopted by scholars towards the language policy. Ufomata (1991) seems to agree with Adeniran's suggestion and observes further that the national language question and the question of language in education are intricately interwoven, the end result of the education system being to evolve and inject into the polity language attitudes and habits which will help to achieve political cohesion and ease communication.

6.3.1 PROBLEMS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL LANGUAGE POLICIES

The implementation of the two policies mentioned above failed for certain reasons. The most important reason is that of the manner of implementation itself. Bamgbose's (1977) assertion that "the best policy is bound to fail if its implementation is haphazard", applies to the Nigerian context. With regard to the NPE, although the policy is supposed to have nation-wide application because of its potentiality for the attainment of the national objective, the Federal Government left the implementation committees in the states to their discretion. This policy requires a child to study one of the three major Nigerian languages in addition to his mother tongue. This policy was briefly implemented in some of the states that fall within the major language groups. In almost all the linguistic minority areas of the country, there does not seem to be any effort at its implementation. Some states even from the major linguistic groups are implementing it insincerely. Some complain of funds while others complain of shortage of good teaching personnel.

Another problem with the implementation of the policy is the attitudinal factor. The language planners did not consider the attitude of the linguistic minorities before designing the policy.

These linguistic minority groups in turn seem to be sabotaging the implementation of the policy. The attitudinal problem has persisted and speakers of minority languages have always been suspicious of the intentions of the policy. Banjo (1992) blames the failure here on... communication in addition to the problems of logistics. Policies of this form should ensure that not only is enough money available for the provision of adequate infrastructure, but that teachers of the right quality are provided in sufficient numbers. It was only recently that the National Institute for Nigerian Languages was established in Aba and charged with the responsibility of training teachers of indigenous languages. The idea to establish the institute came up several years after the policy had been unsuccessfully implemented.

Political instability could be a possible explanation for the delay in the implementation of the language policy in the National Assembly. After the initial drama in the National Assembly where a member from the North was ridiculed and shouted down for attempting to speak Hausa whereas a good number of members did not understand his language, the Assembly recommended the recruitment and training of bilingual staff as well as other modalities that would aid the use of the indigenous languages in the house.

This recommendation was yet to be carried out when the second republic fell. The third republic was also short-lived. It was even doubtful if members from outside the three major language areas would have given it a chance.

6.3.2 THE NEED FOR A COMPREHENSIVE LANGUAGE POLICY

The need for a comprehensive language policy for the country has been stressed by many Nigerian linguists and scholars who see the choice of a national language as being fundamental to the development of the nation. Banjo's observation vividly reflects the feelings of these scholars:

The choice of a national language is, in turn, expected not only to do a lot for the national psyche but also facilitate national mobilization for development which, in turn, will enhance the production of more wealth and launch the nation into the world's top league of developed nations (1992:7).

The question of a national language has been one of the issues which have kept recurring in the country ever since the attainment of independence. Several options that have been suggested include:

- (i) That one of the Nigerian languages be substituted for English as the official language for the country.

- (ii) That English be retained as the lingua franca.
- (iii) That Nigerian pidgin be adopted.

Those who support (i) above argue that national independence also entails linguistic independence, and that Nigeria should promote one or more of its indigenous languages to the position of a national language. The superiority and advantages which the whites seem to enjoy over the Africans, argues Obeamata (1992), can be attributed to the fact that the Africans learn the language and culture of the whites and at the same time are meant to compete with the whites in their own language on equal basis. Also commenting on the disadvantages of using a foreign language as an official language, Adeniran (1987, 1992) points out that:

Development efforts and scholarship in Africa especially have hardly even been original; instead they have been mostly imitative of the West. And they could not have been original because they have been and continue to be conducted in the medium or mediums of the West.

He further adds that since this state of affairs has been observed to be peculiar to peoples in the former European colonies of Africa, it may have been part of the scheme long designed to perpetuate European imperialism on the continent. Banjo (1992:9) supports the views of Obeamata and Adeniran

while observing that "the dominance of English predisposes the nation to look at reality in an English kind of way and to adopt solutions to problems already tested in Britain and United States of America".

Those who support the retention of English as the official language, argue that if a Nigerian language is adopted, it should be expected that the ethnic group whose language has been chosen would emerge as the dominant group in the country. This will likely lead to arrogance and the exhibition of ethnic superiority as well as educational and other social advantages. This fear as expressed above, has led some people to rather prefer everybody to be equally disadvantaged than create an advantaged group in the name of lingua franca.

The call for the adoption or retention of English may also be due to the growing status of English both nationally and internationally. Both Banjo (1992) and Bamgbose (1993) agree that despite all the efforts at encouraging an indigenous lingua franca since independence through the promulgation of the national policy on language in education, English rather than diminish in status, has continued to wield more influence. The acceptance and influence of English in Nigeria have made Bamgbose (1971:35) note as follows:

Of all the heritage left behind in Nigeria by the British at the end of the colonial administration, probably none is more important than the English language. This is now the language of government, business and commerce, education, the mass media, literature and much internal as well as external communication.

Despite the problems posed by English as a medium of instruction and the initial difficulties encountered in the learning of it, the Nigerian child educated in English is better equipped to meet the world that is fast advancing upon him. The mastery of English ensures the ability of individuals to move into academic and intellectual circles at the highest possible levels. The claim of disadvantage by Africans may have been neutralized by the fact that some Nigerian writers of English such as Wole Soyinka, Chinua Achebe and Niyi Osundare have won international awards after competing with first language speakers of English.

Those who advocate the adoption of Nigerian pidgin do so claiming that majority of Nigerians are more disposed to using pidgin than either English or any other Nigerian language. Apart from being used effectively by Nigerians who speak different indigenous languages, it is further argued that Nigerian pidgin serves as a medium of communication between the educated and the illiterate members of the Nigerian Society.

6.3.3 THE LANGUAGE ATTITUDE FACTOR

The consideration of language attitudes enhances language planning strategies. Since language planning refers to the conscious approach to changes in language form and use (Rubin & Jernudd, 1971), language attitudes constitute a determinant factor in deciding the adoption of a common language. Language attitude in so far as it reflects inter-ethnic attitudes is crucial and central to language policy and planning. Lewis (1981) cited by Baker (1988) has summed up the importance of language attitude consideration:

Any policy for language especially in the system of education, has to take account of the attitude of those likely to be affected. In the long run, no policy will succeed which does not do one of these things: conform to the expressed attitudes of those involved; persuade those who express negative attitudes about the rightness of the policy; or seek to remove the cause of the disagreement.

6.3.4 THE INDIAN EXPERIMENT

Perhaps, the Indian experiment will assist us to avoid rushing into hasty and explosive decision. After gaining independence in 1947, the Federal Government of India (a country with about 800 languages) adopted Hindi in place of English as the official language of the Federation. Hindi was one of the most widely used languages,

especially in the Northern part of India. Regional Languages were adopted as the official languages of the states of India, while states also paid considerable attention to the further development of their respective major languages. This dual language policy of India failed because of the politically and religiously motivated opposition against Hindi. Consequently, English was adopted again as the second official language. The educational consequence is that many children have to learn two languages (English and Hindi) in addition to their mother tongue in school. Other children, speaking non-official minority languages, are taught three languages - English, Hindi, and the official language of the state in which they live. India has since then been developing their variety of English which has now been recognized as a dialect of world standard English.

6.3.5 RECOMMENDATION

There should be cautious approach towards the resolution of the national language issue. It is for this reason that this work agrees with Jowitt that acceptability and feasibility should really bother our minds in our march towards our linguistic choice.

The choice of an indigenous language will be frustrated by those whose languages are not chosen. The retention of English will

also continue to be criticised as long as English (especially in its present form) does not reflect adequately our culture and world-view.

The Indian experience will be useful to us. Here, we will avoid the mistake of having to subject a Nigerian language to 'trial' before adopting English. We will also avoid the adoption of English before indigenizing it. What seems best to do, for now, is to concentrate more effort in the codification of a Standard Nigerian English.

Objective assessment of arguments so far made reveals that people's reluctance to accept English stems from the fact of its being non-indigenous and of carrying the white man's culture. It is our belief that once English is 'indigenized', standardized and codified and used in such a way that we can call it "our own" just like the Americans, the choice of an acceptable and less controversial national language would have been facilitated. Even those who favour a return to an indigenous Nigerian language will certainly accept codified NE as a bridge between the indigenous language and English.

6.3.6 POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

The role of the National Institute for Nigerian Languages, Aba, should not be restricted to the production of indigenous language teachers in Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba, but should be expanded to

include the development and training of teachers in several other Nigerian Languages. It should also be assigned the task of codifying an acceptable NE as well as compile a dictionary in it.

However, the activities of language planning of this type should not be left for government or government institutions alone. Individuals or groups of individuals should also be involved in it. Speakers of other languages should be encouraged to promote their languages in competition with other languages. Individuals should also establish schools of Nigerian languages where speakers of other Nigerian languages are encouraged to learn to speak other languages. It is on this basis that one wonders why prominent Nigerian linguists who have devoted much time to indigenous language development have not thought it reasonable up to this moment to establish schools of languages for the teaching of their mother tongues and perhaps other Nigerian languages, just as the French, the Germans, etc. have been doing with their languages (in second language situations).

6.4. THE IMPLICATION OF THIS STUDY TO THE TEACHING OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA

We have tried to establish that there is a Nigerian English which is a national variety of World Standard English. We have also

established that there are ethnic varieties of NE one of which is Igbo English. As we have noted earlier, each variety of English spoken anywhere in the world is characterized by two linguistic features - the general 'common core' features of English and the particular linguistic features that distinguish it from the other varieties. Intelligibility is achieved by the fact that all standard varieties of English share some common core features of English such as the basic English vocabulary and grammar.

The Igbo cannot (and in fact, should not) speak or write like the English. In the same manner, the Igbo cannot speak and write English exactly like the Yoruba or the Hausa people of Nigeria. These Nigerians are different people because of different cultural background, indigenous languages, etc. Their cultures and indigenous languages influence their use of English. This is a fact which English language teachers in Nigeria have failed to recognize, perhaps, because they want to teach learners to speak exactly the same way like the English man. Here is exactly where the problem of teaching English as a second language in Nigeria lies.

In recent times, there has been public outcry over the falling standard of English in particular and education in general. The mass failure often witnessed in West African School Certificate

English can be blamed on the lack of an appropriate model for examining. What exactly is the acceptable standard to be used? Is it the British standard, the American standard, the Nigerian standard, or the mixture of all of them?

The situation is compounded by the fact that there is yet no documented acceptable standard and by the attitude of Nigerian linguists who view performance in English by Nigerians purely from the perspective of errors and deviance. Bamgbose (1993) has also noted here that most of those who refuse to accept the existence of NE are simply worried about the implication of accepting a Nigerian variety of English as an appropriate model, especially when it comes to language teaching. For now, examiners reject even contextually acceptable NE usages because they cannot be found in the dictionaries.

The only viable option left in the effort to choose the model of English to be used for teaching and examining is to begin to compile grammars and dictionaries based on the features which are peculiar to NE especially the variety used among the educated people. An educated NE speaker may be defined here as one who is intelligible not only to other Nigerian educated bilinguals, but also to the educated native speakers of English. It is only when standard reference works or dictionaries are compiled on the correct and

acceptable usages of NE that we can seriously begin to recommend the Nigerian standard usage for teaching and examining.

Efforts should also be intensified towards the training of teachers to teach this variety of English. NE language teachers should be trained to teach and examine students with the realization that the Igbo for instance, do not speak or use English exactly like the Yoruba or Hausa people. The responsibility of training NE language teachers should be assigned to the National Institute for Nigerian Languages. We also find it necessary to suggest here that performance in English by Nigerians should be viewed from the perspective of varieties and deviations rather than as errors and deviance.

So far in this study, we have examined the factors that have led to the implantation of English both as a second language and as an official language. We also demonstrated the features of Igbo English and Nigerian English, showing how IE is created at the levels of lexico-semantic and syntax, especially in the prose texts. Finally, we demonstrated the need for the codification of a standard Nigerian English which will serve as an acceptable and less controversial national language as well as serve as the variety for teaching and examining in educational institutions in Nigeria.

Future studies should explore the use of dialectal varieties of Nigerian English in poetry, drama and the mass media as well as intensify research on NE with a view to codifying and modernizing it appropriately.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

PRIMARY SOURCES

- Ike, C. (1965) Toads For Supper. Ibadan: University Press PLC.
- _____ (1973) The Potter's Wheel. Fontana/Collins.
- Munonye, J. (1966) The Only Son. Ibadan. London. Nairobi: Educational Books Limited.
- _____ (1978) Bridge to a Wedding. London: Heinemann.
- Nwankwo, N. (1964) Danda. Fontana/Collins.
- _____ (1975) My Mercedes is Bigger than Yours. Fontana/Collins.
- Tutuola, A. (1962) Feather Women of the Jungle. London: Faber.

SECONDARY SOURCES

- Aboderin, O. (1978) "Yoruba/English Codemixing and the Yoruba Educated Elite" M.A. Project, University of Ibadan.
- Achebe, C. (1965) "English and the African Writer" Transition, IV, 18.
- _____ (1975) "The African Writer and the English Language" Morning Yet on Creation Day. London: Heinemann Educational Books Limited.
- Acholonu, C. and Penfield, J.A. (1980) "Linguistic Process of Innovation in Igbo" Anthropological Linguistics, Vol. 22, No.3.
- Adejare, O. (1992) Language and Style in Soyinka: A Systemic Textlinguistic Study of Literary Idiolect. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) PLC.

- Adekunle, M.A. (1974) "The Standard Nigerian English in Socio-linguistic Perspective" Journal of the Nigerian English Studies Association. Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 24-37.
- (1979) "Non-Random Variation in Nigerian English" In E. Ubahakwe, ed. Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria. pp. 27-42, Lagos: African Universities Press.
- Adeniran, A. (1974) "A Functionalistic View of Stylistic Restriction in Nigerian English" Journal of the Nigerian Studies Association Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 15-23.
- (1979a) "Nigerian Elite English as a Model of Nigerian English" In E. Ubahakwe, ed. Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria pp. 227-241. Lagos: African Universities Press.
- (1979b) "Personalities and Policies in the Establishment of English in Northern Nigeria (1900-1943)" International Journal of the Sociology of Language 22, pp. 57-77.
- (1987) "Language Planning and Practice in Africa: the Need for Political Intervention" African Notes Vol. XI, No. 1, pp. 1-7.
- (1990a) "The Role of the Mother Tongue in Second Language Learning" Journal of the Nigerian Studies Association pp. 78-94.
- (1990b) "Yoruba-English Codemixing and Codeswitching in Conversational discourse: Some Communicative Motivations" Paper presented at the 19th West African Languages Congress, University of Ghana, Legon Ghana.
- (1992) "Language Education Provisions in Nigeria's National Policy on Education: A Critique" Paper presented at a Weekend of Seminar in honour of Professor Ayo Bamgbose, Department of Linguistics, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.

- Adesanoye, F. (1973) "Varieties of Written English in Nigeria". Unpublished Ph.D thesis, University of Ibadan.
- _____ (1985) "To be or not to be: An outlook for English in Nigeria" In Asein, ed. Review of English and Literary Studies. Vol. 2, No. 2.
- Adetugbo, A. (1979) "Appropriateness and Nigerian English" In E. Ubahakwe, ed. Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria pp. 137-166. Lagos: African Universities Press.
- _____ (1987) "Nigerian English Phonology: Is there any Standard?" LARES, IX, pp. 64-84.
- Afolayan, A. (1968) "The Linguistic Problems of Yoruba Learners and Users of English" Ph.D. Thesis, London University.
- _____ (1987) "English as a Second Language: A Variety or a Myth?" Journal of English as a Second Language, No. 1, pp. 4-16.
- Ahukanna, J.G.W. (1985) "Bilingualism and Codemixing in Language Use in Nigeria: The case of Igbo English Bilinguals" Presented at the LAN Conference, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Ajulo, E.B. (1994) Investigating Lexis in English: Problems of Theory and Pedagogy. Lagos: Stirling-Horden Publishers (Nigeria) Limited.
- Akere, F. (1986) "Sociocultural Constraints and the Emergence of a Standard Nigerian English" In J.B. Pride, ed. New Englishes Rowley: Newbury House.
- Amafa, J.E. (1990) "The English Language in the Nigerian Army: A Situational and Linguistic Analysis" Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Amayo, A. (1983) "The Pronunciation of English as a Second Language" In A. Afolayan, ed. English as a Second Language, University of Ife Press.

- Amayo, A. (1992) "Contrastive Analysis in an ESL Situation: Some Problem Areas" Paper presented at the 60th Birthday celebration in honour of Professor Ayo Bamgbose, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Awoniyi, T.A. (1974) "Utilizing Children's Mother Tongue Experience for Effective English Language Teaching in Nigeria" Journal of the Nigerian English Studies Association, IV, No. 2.
- Awonusi, V.O. (1985) "Socio linguistic Variation in Nigerian English" Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, University of London.
- Ayodele, S.O. (1981) "An Evaluation of the level of Oral Performances of Grade Two Teacher Trainees," Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan,
- _____ (1983) "A description of the Varieties of Nigerian English for Pedagogical purposes" Journal of Language Teaching Vol. 21, No.2.
- Baker, C. (1988) Key Issues in Bilingualism and Bilingual Education, Clevedon, Philadelphia: Multilingual Matters Limited.
- Bamgbose, A. (1971) "The English Language in Nigeria" In J. Spencer, ed. The English Language in West Africa pp. 35-45. London: Longman.
- _____ (1977) "Towards an implementation of Nigeria's Language Policy in Education" Language in Education in Nigeria. National Language Centre, Federal Ministry of Education, Lagos.
- _____ (1982a) "Languages in Contact: Yoruba and English in Nigeria" Education and Development Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 329-341.
- _____ (1982b) "Standard Nigerian English: Issues of Identification" In B. Kachru, ed. The Other Tongue: English Across Cultures. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.

Bamgbose, A. (1992) "Speaking in Tongues: Implications of Multilingualism for Language Policy in Nigeria" Nigerian National Merit Award Winners' Lecture, Kaduna.

(1993) "English in the Nigerian Environment" Paper Presented at the British Council/University of Ibadan Conference on English Language and Literature. Ibadan.

Bamiro, E. (1991). "Nigerian Englishes in Nigerian Literature" World Englishes Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 7-17.

Banjo, A. (1969) "A Contrastive Study of Aspects of the Syntactic and Lexical Rules of English and Yoruba" Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan.

(1971). "Towards a Definition of Standard Nigerian Spoken English". Actes du de Congress de la Societe Linguistique de l' Afrique Occidentale, Abidjan.

(1979). "Beyond Intelligibility" In E. Ubahakwe, ed. Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria pp. 7-13, Lagos: African Universities Press.

(1982) "Aspects of Yoruba English Language Mixing" Journal Of Nigerian Languages, No. 1. pp. 17-26.

(1992) "On Language Use and Modernity in Nigeria" Paper Presented at the seminar in honour of Professor Ayo Bamgbose, Department of Linguistics, University of Ibadan,

(1993) "On Codifying Nigerian English: Research on Nigerian English So Far" Paper Presented at the British Council Anniversary Conference in Ibadan.

and Young, P. (1982). "On Editing a Second Language Dictionary of West African English" English World Wide, Vol. 3, No. 1.

Bateson, F.W. (1971). "Literature and Linguistics: Reply by F.W. Bateson" In Fowler, ed. Language of Literature, pp. 54-64. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.

Beattie, J. (1964) Other Cultures, Aims, Methods and Achievements in Social Anthropology. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.

- Berry, M. (1975) Introduction to Systemic Linguistics:1, Structures and Systems. London: Batsford.
- (1977) Introduction to Systemic Linguistics:2, Levels and Links. London: Batsford.
- Bloomfield, L. (1933) Languages New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Bokamba, E. (1992). "The Africanization of English" In B. Kachru, ed. The Other Tongue: English Across Cultures. Urban University of Illinois Press.
- Booth, J. (1981) Writers and Politics in Nigeria. London: Hodder and Stoughton.
- Brann, C.M.B. (1978). "Functions of World Languages in West Africa" West African Journal of Modern Languages. No. 3, pp. 6-28.
- Brosnahan, L.F. (1958). "English in southern Nigeria". English Studies Vol. 39, No. 3.
- Butler, C.S. (1985). Systemic Linguistics: Theory and Applications. London: Batesford.
- Catford, J.C. (1965) A Linguistic Theory of Translation. London: Oxford University Press.
- Chapman, R. (1973). Linguistics and Literature: An Introduction to Literary Stylistics. London: Edward Arnolds.
- Chatman, S. ed. (1971). Literary Style: A Symposium. London: Oxford University Press.
- Cheshire, J. ed. (1991). English around the World Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Corder, S.P. (1981). Error Analysis and Interlanguage. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Coulthard, M. (1977) An Introduction to Discourse Analysis. London: Longman.

- Crystal, D. (1987) The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- _____ and Davy, D. (1969) Investigating English Style London: Longman Group Limited.
- Dittmar, N. (1974) application. Sociolinguistics: A Critical Survey of theory and London: Edward Arnold.
- Dunstan, E. ed. (1969) Twelve Nigerian Languages. London: Longman.
- Ekong, P.A. (1978) "On Describing the Vowel System of a Standard Variety of Nigerian Spoken English" Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Ellis, J.N. (1970) "Linguistics, Literature and the Concept of Style" Word, Vol. 26, No. 1.
- Elugbe, B.O. (1990) "National Language and National Development" In E.N. Emenanjo, ed. Multilingualism, Minority Languages and Language Policy in Nigeria pp. 10-19 Agbor: Central Books Limited.
- _____ and Omamor, A. (1991) Nigerian Pidgin. Ibadan Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) PLC.
- Emenanjo, E.N. (1975) "Aspect of the Igbo Verb" In F.C Ogbalu and E.N. Emenanjo, eds. Igbo Language and Culture pp. 160-173. Ibadan: University Press Limited.
- _____ (1978) Elements of Modern Igbo Grammar: A Descriptive Approach. Ibadan: University Press Limited.
- _____ (1981) Auxiliaries in Igbo Syntax: A Comparative Study. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Emenyonu, E. (1978) The Rise of the Igbo Novel. Ibadan: Oxford University Press.
- Enkvist, N.E. (1964a) Linguistics and Style London: Oxford University Press.

- Enkvist, N.E. (1964b) "On Defining Style: An Essay in Applied Linguistics" In J. Spencer, ed. Linguistics and Style. London: Oxford University Press.
- _____ (1971) "On the Place of Style in some Linguistic Theories" In S. Chatman, ed. Literary Style: A Symposium pp. 47-61, London: Oxford University Press.
- Ervin-Tripp, S. (1973) Language Acquisition and Communicative Choice. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria National Policy on Education (revised) NERC Press, Lagos.
- Finnegan, R. (1970) Oral Literature in Africa. London: Oxford University Press.
- Fishman, J.A. (1989) Language and Ethnicity in Minority Sociolinguistic Perspective. Clevedon-Philadelphia: Multilingual Matters Limited.
- Fowler, R. ed. (1966a) Essays on Style and Language: Linguistic and Critical Approaches to Literary Style. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.
- _____ (1966b) "Linguistics, Stylistics, Criticism?" Lingua, XVI.
- _____ (1971a) Linguistics and the Novel. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.
- _____ (1971b) The Languages of Literature : Some Linguistic Contributions to Criticism. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- _____ (1979) "Preliminaries to Social Linguistic Theory of Literary Discourse" Poetics, Vol. 8, No.6.
- Freeman, D.C. ed. (1970) "Linguistic Approaches to Literature" In D.C. Freeman, ed. Linguistics and Literary Style pp.3-17, New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.

Goodenough, W.H. (1957) "Cultural Anthropology and Linguistics" In P.L. Garvin, ed. Report of the 7th Annual Round Table Meeting on Linguistics and Language Study pp. 167-173. Washington.

Gregory, M. and Carroll, S. (1978) Language and Situation: Language Varieties and their Social Contexts. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.

Halliday, M.A.K. (1961) "Categories of the Theory of Grammar" Word, No.17, pp.241-292.

(1964) "The Linguistic Study of Literary Texts" In H.G. Lunt, ed. Proceedings of the IXth International Congress of Linguists pp.302-307. The Hague: Mouton.

(1966) "Some notes on Deep Grammar" Journal of Linguistics, No.2, pp.57-67.

(1968) Notes on Transitivity and Theme in English, part 3", Journal of Linguistics, No.4, pp. 179-215.

(1970a) "Descriptive Linguistics in Literary Studies" In D.C. Freeman, ed. Linguistics and Literary Style, pp. 57-72, New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.

(1970b) "Language Structure and Language Function" In J. Lyons, ed. New Horizons in Linguistics. Harmondsworth, Penguin.

(1971a) "Language in a Social Perspective", Educational Review, No.23, pp. 165-188.

(1971b) "Linguistic Function and Literary Style: An Inquiry into the Language of William Goldings *The Inheritors*" In S. Chatman, ed. Literary Style: A Symposium. London: Oxford University Press.

(1973) Explorations in the Functions of Language London: Edward Arnold.

(1985) An Introduction to Functional Grammar. London Edward Arnold.

- and Hasan, R. (1976) Cohesion in English. London: Longman.
- McIntosh, A. and Strevens, P. (1964) The Linguistic Sciences and Language Teaching. London: Longman.
- Haugen, E. (1956) Bilingualism in the Americas. American Dialect Society.
- Haynes, J. (1989) Introducing Stylistics. London: Unwin Hyman.
- Hill, J.A. and Hill, K.C. (1980) "Mixed Grammar, Purist Grammar, and the Language attitudes in the Modern Nahuatl" Language in Society Vol.9, No.3, pp. 321-348. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hornby, A.S. (1974) Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary of Current English. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hudson, R.A. (1980) Sociolinguistics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hymes, D. (1964) Language in Culture and Society. New York: Evanston, and London: North Western University Press.
- _____ (1972) "On Communicative Competence" In J. Pride and J. Holmes, eds. Sociolinguistics, pp. 269-293. Harmondsworth, Penguin.
- Igboanusi, H.S. (1990) "Sociolinguistic Perspectives on Igbo English Codemixing among the Educated Igbo." M.A. Project, University of Ibadan.
- Ikara, B. (1987) "Minority Languages and Lingua Francas in Nigeria!" Keynote address to the opening session of the 7th Annual Conference of the Linguistic Association of Nigeria.
- Ikonne, C. (1986) "Nigerian English and International Intelligibility: The Situation in the United States of America" In S.O. Unoh, ed. Use of English in Communication: The Nigerian Experience. pp. 29-38, Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited.

- Jacobs, R. (1966) English Language Teaching in Nigeria. Lagos: National Universities Commission and Ford Foundation.
- James, C. (1971) "The Exculpation of Contrastive Linguistics" In G. Nickel, ed. Papers in Contrastive Linguistics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jibril, M. (1979) "Regional Varieties in Nigerian English" In E. Ubahekwe, ed. Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria. pp. 43-53, Lagos: African Universities Press.
- _____ (1982) "Phonological Varieties in Nigerian English" Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Lancaster.
- _____ (1986) "Sociolinguistic Variation in Nigerian English." English World-Wide, Vol.7, No.1.
- Johnson, A.C. (1981) "Language and Society in West African Literature: A Stylistic Investigation into the Linguistic Resources of West African Drama in English" Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Jowitt, D. (1991) Nigerian English Usage: An Introduction. Nigeria: Longman.
- _____ (1993) "Nigeria's National Language Problem: Choices and Constraints". Paper presented at the British Council/ University of Ibadan Conference on English Language and Literature. Ibadan.
- Kachru, B.B. (1965) "The Indianness in Indian English" Word Vol.21, No.3, pp. 391-410.
- _____ (1978) "Towards Structuring Codemixing: An Indian Perspective" International Journal of the Sociology of Language. 16, pp. 27-46.
- _____ (1982) The Other Tongue: English Across Cultures. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
- Kennedy, C. (1976) "Systemic Grammar and its use in Literary Analysis" Mals Journal New Series, No.1, pp.17-38.

- Killam, G.D. ed. (1973) African Writers on African Writing. Evanston: Northwestern University Press.
- Kirk-Green, A. (1971) "The Influence of West African Languages on English" In J. Spencer, ed. The English Language in West Africa. London: Longman.
- Kirkwood, H.W. (1966) "Translation as a basis for Contrastive Linguistic Analysis" IRAL, IV/3 pp.175-182.
- Klein, W. (1986) Second Language Acquisition. London. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Kress, C. ed. (1976) Halliday: System and Function in Language. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Krzeszowski, T.P. (1971) "Equivalence, Congruence and Deep Structure" In G. Nickel, ed. Papers in Contrastive Linguistics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kujore, O. (1985) English Usage: Some Notable Nigerian Variations. Ibadan: Evans.
- _____ (1990) "Nigerian English Usage: Analogies, Abbreviations, and the Tyranny of the 'Idea'" Journal of the Nigerian English Studies Association Vol.10, No.1-14.
- _____ (1993) "Whose English?" Paper presented at the British Council/University of Ibadan Conference on English Language and Literature, Ibadan.
- Leech, G.N. (1965) "This Bread I Break: Language and Interpretation" Review of English Literature. VI, 66-75.
- _____ (1966) "Linguistics and the Figures of Rhetorics" In R. Fowler, ed. Essays on Style and Language. pp.135-156. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.
- _____ and Short, M.H. (1981) Style in Fiction: A Linguistic Introduction to English Fictional Prose. London and New York: Longman.

- Le Page, R.B. (1968) "Problems of Description in Multilingual Communities" Transactions of the Philological Society.
- Lewis, E.G. (1981) Bilingualism and Bilingual Education Oxford: Pergamon.
- Lindfors, B. (1975) Critical Perspectives on Nigerian Literatures. London: Heinemann.
- Lyons, J. (1968) Introduction to Theoretical Linguistics. London: Cambridge University Press.
- Mach, V. (1971) "Comparative Analysis of English and Czech Phonology and Production of Errors in Learning" In G. Nickel, ed. Papers in Contrastive Linguistics. pp. 103-106. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mackey, W.F. (1968) "The Description of Bilingualism" IN J.A. Fishmann, ed. Readings in the Sociology of Language, pp. 554-584. The Hague. Paris: Mouton.
- Mazrui, A. (1975) The Political Sociology of the English Language: An African Perspective. The Hague: Mouton.
- McLaughlin, B. (1987) Theories of Second Language Learning. London. New York: Edward Arnold.
- McIntosh, A. and Halliday, M.A.K. (1966) Patterns of Language: Papers in General, descriptive and Applied Linguistics. London: Longman.
- McTear, M.F. (1979) "Systemic Functional Grammar: Some Implications for Language Teaching" IRAL, XVII/2, pp.99-122.
- Merio, K. (1978) "The Psycholinguistic Analysis and the measurement of interference errors" IRAL, XVI/1.
- Muir, J. (1972) A Modern Approach to English Grammar: An Introduction to Systemic Grammar. London: B.T. Batsford Limited.

- Mukavovsky, J. (1970) "Standard Language and Poetic Language" In D.C. Freeman, ed. Linguistics and Literary Style, pp. 40-56. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.
- Nemser, W. (1971) "The Predictability of Interference Phenomena in the English Speech of native speakers of Hungarian" In G. Nickel, ed. Papers in Contrastive Linguistics, pp. 89-96. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ngara, E. (1982) Stylistic Criticism and the African Novel. London: Heinemann.
- Nickel, G. ed. (1971) Papers in Contrastive Linguistics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Nickel, G. and Wagner, K.A. (1968) "Contrastive Linguistics and Language Teaching" IRAL 6, pp. 233-256.
- Nida, E.A. (1975) Language Structure and Translation. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Nwabueze, B.O. (1985) "The Igbos in the Context of Modern Government and Politics in Nigeria: A call for self-examination and self-correction" 1985 Ahiajoku Lecture, Owerri.
- Nwaozuzu, B.S.C. (1980) "Igbo Folklore and Igbo World-View" NSAL, No. 3, pp. 207-218.
- Nwoga, D.I. (1975) "Appraisal of Igbo Proverbs and Idioms" In F.C. Ogbalu and E.N. Emenanjo, eds. Igbo Language and Culture, pp. 186-204, Ibadan: University Press Limited.
- Obeamata, I.O. (1992) "Language and the Intelligence of the Blackman" An inaugural Lecture delivered at the University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Obiechina, E.N. (1974) "Varieties Differentiation in English Usage" Journal of Nigerian English Studies Association, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 77-94.
- (1975) Cultural, Tradition and Society in West African Novel. London: Cambridge University Press.
- Odlin, T. (1989) Language Transfer: Cross-Linguistic influence in Language Learning. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Odumuh, A.E. (1987) Nigerian English (Nig.E). Zaria. Ahmadu Bello University Press Limited.
- _____ (1993) Sociolinguistics and Nigerian English. Ibadan: Sam Bookman.
- Ofuani, O.A. (1987) "A Stylistic Analysis of Okot P'Bitek's Poetry" Ph.D Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Ohman, R. (1964) "Generative Grammars and the Concept of Literary Style" Word, Vol.20, No.3.
- Olagoké, D.O. (1981) "Lexical Deviation in Nigerian English" JLAC, Vol.2, Nos. 3 and 4, pp.35-57.
- Oluikpe, B.O.A. (1978) English in Igboland: A Contrastive Study of English and Igbo Syntax. Africana Educational Publishers.
- Omoniyi, T. (1988) "The Acquisition of Lexical Proficiency in English Usage: Cultural diffusion and Variation in the use of Kinship terms and address forms in an ESL context" Ife Studies in English Language, Vol.2, No.2, pp.67-77.
- Onwubu, C. (1976) "Language and Literature: Transliteration in Neo-African Literature", West African Journal of Modern Languages 2, pp.45-54.
- Osundare, N. (1979) "Bilingualism and Bicultural Aspects of Nigerian Prose Fiction" Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, York University, Toronto, Ontario.
- _____ (1987) "Style and Literary Communication in African Prose Fiction in English" In S.O. Unoh, ed. Topical Issues of Communication Arts.
- Oyeleye, M.L. (1985) "The Language of Achebe's Early Novels (in the Context of Nigerian English): A Study in Literary Stylistics" Ph.D Thesis, University of Ife.
- _____ (1988) "Language and Character Presentation in Achebe: The Example of No Longer At Ease." In ODU 33, pp.189-200.

- Oyesoro, O.O. (1988) "A Contrastive Lexicological Study of Five Semantic Fields: Yoruba and English". M.A. Project, University of Ibadan.
- Pike, K.L. (1948) Tone Languages: a technique for determining the number and type of pitch contrasts in a Language. Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Platt, J., Weber, H., and Ho, M.L. (1984) The New Englishes. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.
- Pride, J.B. ed. (1982). New Englishes. Rowley: Newbury House.
- _____ and Holmes, J. eds. (1972) Sociolinguistics. Harmondsworth, England: Penguin Books Limited.
- Quirk, R. (1962) The Use of English, London: Longman.
- _____, Greenbaum, S., Leech, G. and Svartvik, J. (1972) A Grammar of Contemporary English. London: Longman.
- Riffaterre, M. (1959a) "Criteria for Style Analysis" World, 15, pp. 154-174.
- _____ (1959b). "Review of S. Ullman's Style in French Novels" Word XV, pp. 404-413.
- _____ (1960) "Stylistic Context" Word XV, pp. 207-218.
- Ross, D. Jr. (1978) "Stylistics and the testing of Literary Hypothesis" Poetic, Vol. 7, No. 4 North Holland Publishing Company.
- Rubin, J. and Jernudd, B.H. (1971) Can Language be planned? Honolulu: East West Central Books.
- Sacks, S. (1978) On Metaphor. The University of Chicago Press.
- Schmied, J. (1991). English in Africa: An Introduction. London and New York: Longman.

- Sciarone, A.G. (1970) "Contrastive Analysis: Possibilities and Limitations" IRAL, VIII/2, pp.115-131.
- Shelton, A. (1969) "The articulation of traditional Modern Igbo Literature" The Conch 1,1.
- Short, M.H. (1976) "Why we sympathize with Lennie" MALS Journal, New Series, No.1, pp.1-9.
- Sinclair, J. MCH. (1966) "Taking a poem to pieces" In R. Fowler, ed. Essays on Style and Language London: Routledge and Kegan Paul Limited.
- _____ (1968) "A technique of stylistic description", Language and Style, No.1, pp.215-242.
- Smith, M.S. (1979) Strategies, Language Transfer and Simulation of the Second Language Learner's Mental Operations" Language Learners, Vol.29, No.2, pp.345-361.
- Spencer, J.B. ed. (1964). Linguistics and Style. London: Longman.
- _____ (1971) The English Language in West Africa. London: Longman.
- _____ and Gregory, M.J. (1970) "An Approach to the Study of Style" In D.C. Freeman, ed. Linguistic Approaches to Literature, pp.73-95. New York: Holt, Rinehalt and Winston Inc.
- Sridhar, S.N. (1978) "On the Functions of Codemixing in Kanada" International Journal of the Sociology of Language. 16, pp. 109-117. Mouton.
- Taiwo, O. (1979) "Varieties of English in Nkem Nwankwo's Novels" In E. Ubahakwe, ed. Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria, pp.54-76. Lagos: African University Press.
- Taylor, B. (1975) "The Use of Overgeneralization and Transfer of Learning Strategies by elementary and Intermediate Students of ESL" Language Learning. 25, pp.73-107.

- The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1979) Apapa: Times Press Limited.
- The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1989) The Directorate for Social Mobilization "MAMSER", P.M.B. 27, Abuja.
- Thorn, J.P. (1965). "Stylistics and Generative Grammars" Journal of Linguistics 1, pp. 49-59.
- Tiffen, B. ed. (1969) A Language in Common: A Guide to English Language Teaching in Schools and Colleges. London: Longman.
- Tiffen, B. (1974) The Intelligibility of Nigerian English. University of London, Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis.
- Todorov, T. (1971) "The Place of Style in the Structure of Text" In S. Chartman, ed. Literary Style: A Symposium, pp. 29-44. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Tonade, K. (1989). "Towards Deciphering the Filial Complex: A Stylistic Analysis of John Munonye's The Only Son". M.A. Project, University of Ibadan.
- Ubahakwe, E. ed. (1979). Varieties and Functions of the English Language in Nigeria. Lagos: African Universities Press.
- Ufomata, T. (1991). "Englishization of Yoruba Phonology" World Englishes 10" 1, pp. 33-51.
- Ugwu, A.N. (1990). "A Study of Some Aspects of Nigerian English In Nigerian Prose Fiction". Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Ullmann, S. (1959). Style in the French Novel. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- _____ (1964) Language and Style. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Weinreich, U. (1953). Languages in Contact: Findings and Problems. New York, Linguistic Circle of New York.
- Whiteley, W.H. ed. (1971) Language Use and Social Change. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Whorf B.L. (1941) "The Relation of Habitual Thought and Behaviour to Language" In L. Spier et al, eds. Language, Culture and Personality: Essays in Memory of Edward Sapir, pp.75-93, Menasha: Sapir Memorial Fund.
- (1956) Language, Thought and Reality: Selected Writings of Benjamin Lee Whorf, J.B. Carrol, ed. Cambridge: Technology Press and New York: MIT and Wiley.
- Widdowson, H.G. (1974) "Stylistics" In J.P.B. Allen and S.P. Corder, eds. The Edinburgh Course in Applied Linguistics, Vol.3.
- (1975) Stylistics and the Teaching of Literature. London: Longman.
- Wilkins, D.A. (1972) Linguistics in Language Teaching. London: Edward Arnold.
- Young, P. (1969) "The Language of West African Writing in English with special Reference to Nigerian Prose Fiction". Ph.D Thesis, University of Durham.